

**EXPLORING THE PERCEPTIONS OF SERVICE USERS TOWARDS
SERVICE PROVIDER'S DARK BEHAVIOURS BASED ON THE
CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT PRACTICES**

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Abstract

While customer relationship management (CRM) has received a significant amount of attention from academics in the field of management and relationship marketing, it has been studied extremely unilaterally. The sole focus has been placed on the successful implementation of CRM and its benefits, while possible CRM strategy failure, its causes and consequences have been ignored.

The failure of CRM begins with firm's inability to understand and differentiate between CRM as a strategy and CRM as a tool that collects, stores and manages data acquired through customer touchpoints. CRM strategy holds a bigger picture where firms does all of the above using CRM tools, and also constantly create and add value through learnings generated from customers data and use those learnings to give value back to the customers, which is known as win-win situation (Nguyen et. al., 2015, p.4). Often, the benefits offered by CRM lures the firms towards gaining bigger slice of the cake that leads them to involves in activities like misusing and exploiting customer data, hidden charges, exploiting vulnerable segments, neglecting customer privacy favouring profitable customer segments and so on. These activities lead to decrease service users' trust and raises perceptions of being unfairly treated and exploited. Such unfair practices that hinder buyer-seller relationship, have been recognised as dark sides of CRM. It is therefore crucial for the service providers to track and monitor their CRM activities to ensure that the trust and transparency element is well addressed and that no CRM activities pose a risk of misusing and damaging the customer relationship.

This study has two aims. The first main aim of this research is to understand whether mobile service users in the UK are aware of the unfair and hidden activities that are being practiced by their service providers; activities that go beyond the aim of implementing customer relationship management, and to identify what dark activities are being practiced in the name of CRM. The second aim is to recommend a framework that can be implemented in order to eliminate the identified dark side activities through this study and encourage a fairer and transparent CRM activities. This will result in value co-creation and a win-win situation for both the service providers and service users.

Providing personalised experiences based on individuals' needs and one-to-one service customisation is the key idea behind CRM, as it creates opportunities for cross-selling, upselling and profit maximisation through a long-term relationship. However, service providers need to formulate strategies in such a way that they do not entail the differential treatment and favouritism of a certain segment of customers over others. Feelings of inequality and unfair treatment are what lead service users to perceive these CRM activities as being dark ones.

This study identifies that practices such as the favouritism of certain customer segments, unequal behaviour, ignorance about vulnerable customer segments and price discrepancies between loyal and new customers result in perceptions of unfairness. This leads to customers opting out of relationships, circulating negative word of mouth on social media and in online communities or engage in the activities that damages the reputation of the firm. The study will also explore dark activities being practiced by the service users. Despite there being such visible detrimental consequences, little attention has been paid to understanding this side of CRM; hence, the researcher is exploring this realm of marketing and customer management.

This research is carried out in the UK Mobile Network Operator (MNO) industry, and the data collection was conducted using a mixed methods approach that included Netnography data observation (qualitative method) and an online survey (quantitative method). Qualitative data was collected through the observation of MNOs' Facebook and Twitter pages, while the online survey was conducted by posting the survey link on the Facebook pages of each MNO—except for O2, which restricts customers from making a post on their Facebook community. Therefore, the researcher posted the survey link in O2's community forum instead.

Overall, this study contributes to both theory and practice. The study identified that there are several forms of dark side CRM practices prevalent amongst service users and that not many service users are aware of them. The lack of awareness about and visibility of such activities often encourages practitioners to continue practicing them and exploiting customers' trust and relationship with the firm. It also identified that when some service users realise that they are in a disadvantaged position, they often

retaliate through certain forms of dark behaviours themselves: these include engaging in negative word of mouth, abusing employees, using foul language in public platforms and terminating the relationship entirely.

Hence, this study is an effort towards bringing the dark side practices in light so that the practitioners and policy makers can manage the CRM practices in the most ethical and fairer way possible. It also calls the service users to be vigilant on the activities practiced by their service providers as well as to be responsible buyers, by reading terms and conditions, acquiring as much information as possible before buying, checking the bills and timely reporting the service providers if any unsolicited activity is identified.

Chapter 1: Introduction and Background to the Thesis

Introduction

This chapter is particularly focused on discussing the structure and planning of the overall study. It discusses the reasons behind the choice of research topic, examines the current situation in the area of research, identifies the gaps that this research intends to bridge and outlines the research problem, research objectives and the research questions. Furthermore, an outline of the research methodology is presented and, lastly, the contributions of this research are concisely outlined.

1.1 Aim Statement

Relationship marketing and customer relationship management are the most popular fields of study in the current marketing world. Customer relationship management strategy aims to resourcefully administer the acquisition, development and retention of customers by developing and continuing long-term relationships. The advancement in technology have facilitated better customer relationships as it offers the possibility of collecting significant volume of customer data from various customer touch points, along with the ability to manage and implement those data profitably. As advantageous as the implementation of CRM strategy can be for both parties; namely, service providers and service users, it also has some negative consequences as a result of service providers' inefficient practices (Nguyen and Simkin, 2009; Payne and Frow, 2013). Studies have stated that the improper implementation of CRM results perceptions of unfairness amongst service users that may result into buyers withdrawing from relationships, engaging against the brand negatively, spread negative word of mouth, or practicing the actions that may hurt the firm (Xia et al, 2004; Gregoire and Fisher, 2008).

Despite the popularity of CRM, very little scholarly attention is given to examining the poor implementation of relationship marketing by service providers and how their intended or unintended behaviours can severely cost customer relationships (Nguyen & Mutum, 2012, Nguyen, Jaber and Simkin, 2020). It is therefore important to explore how consumers both feel about and perceive such shadow behaviours that are engaged in by the brands and service providers that they trust and believe to be a part

of. After identifying such hidden behaviours, this study will propose strategies by which service providers can eliminate practices of such hidden behaviours and foster fairer practices that lead to a win-win situation for all involved parties.

1.2 Research Topic and Interest

Customer relationship management (CRM) received a huge amount of attention from practitioners and academics when firms realised the importance of customer retention and profitability in relation to long-term customers. Firms believed that CRM implementation was the key to success and hence, they adopt CRM strategies and technologically enhanced software to store and gain customer behavioural insights based on the data collected through CRM systems. Firms are however observed inclined towards using those data and information collected through customers themselves in order to maximise their profitability, ignoring the point of value co-creation through customer data and thus failing the objective of CRM implementation as a whole and rather practicing with 'dark' motive (Nguyen, 2011). Nguyen introduced the term 'dark sides' in his research in the field of CRM and several studies have been conducted ever since, and they are still calling future researchers to further explore and administer the dark side concept more systematically, particularly, the elements of dark side behaviours concerning the customer relationship management. (Nguyen, Jaber and Simkin, 2020).

CRM views firms' relationships with their existing and potential customers as a key to their success; however, managers often miss the point of managing that relationship. Most CRM software and methods used today are utterly product- and business-centric, meaning that firms place an emphasis on achieving increased transactions while ignoring aspects such as adequate customer support and value co-creation (Gronroos, 2011). This greed and focus on transactions lead firms to misuse customers' data and information, ultimately resulting in unwanted behaviours that are referred to as the 'dark side' of CRM (Boulding et al., 2005) and to date, efforts towards building a theoretical framework towards the various forms of unfairness have been extremely limited.

On the one hand, there are customers who trust firms with their personal data and information, and let firms use their information in order to grow and improve, while firms use such customer information for upselling, cross selling and increasing their profitability over time. On the other hand, there are other customers who view firms' use of their information differently. They understand that their data and information is being used by the firms for purposes beyond what's agreed only to generate significant income stream and competitive advantage (Nguyen et. al, 2015). Unclear and never-ending terms and conditions, price differentiation, differential treatment between existing and new customers, information asymmetry, online behaviour tracking, sharing information with unlimited numbers of third parties, and so on, are only some recognised examples of how the customer data are misused, beyond the objective of what they were originally collected for (Nguyen et. al, 2015). These practices may seem ethical from firms' perspectives, but from the customers' perspectives they view them as being unfair. Hence, empathising the disadvantaged position of service users who are often deliberately unfairly treated and taken advantage of through activities like abuse and misuse of data, unfair treatment, false advertising, customer lock-in and so on, the researcher aims to undertake this research.

This thesis aims to understand how CRM, which is almost a mandatory strategy that every service firm adopts today, contains a hidden side that might look ethical and transparent from firms' points of view, while appearing to be the reverse from the customers' perspective. Such a difference might not only hinder existing relationships between service providers and service users; while it might also keep away the potential new customers through negative word of mouth. Likewise, possibility of losing potential new customers may also increase as the negative word of mouth is understood to be extremely powerful tool in digital marketing today. Studies across several industries have been carried out to examine CRM, implementation and its development, predominantly focused on the positive effect of CRM implementation and the overall objectives of implementation; the darker sides, ethical issues, customer biases and favouritism, information asymmetry, information misuse, and so on, exist, but are rarely cited in such studies (McKinley, 2012). Some of the past studies bluntly expressed on how service users are being taken advantage of by their service providers by 'binding them with contracts, bleeding them with fees and

confounding them with fine print' (McGovern and Moon, 2007, p. 80) and yet this issue hasn't got required attention from neither scholars nor the practitioners.

Thus, this study is dedicated to understanding the perceptions of service users with regard to the hidden activities that the service providers are practising neglecting the relational aspect of CRM. In recent years, CRM software has no longer been limited to being used as an operational tool that stores customers' data. Advanced technology, along with advancements in data warehousing and data mining, have made these tools powerful enough to analyse and generate extremely effective information about customers. Ability to understand how a customer responds to firm's CRM schemes enables firms to prompt customer sponsorship and a long-term sustainable income stream.

This research aims to understand whether service users are aware of the opaque or hidden practices used by their service providers to induce long term profitability: are they aware that these activities are intentionally practiced by firms to maximise profit? Do service users feel shaded by the brands that they have been trusting for years? Do service users feel disadvantaged or unfairly treated and, if they do, how do they react and respond to such behaviour?

1.3 Research Objectives and Questions

Hidden CRM practices and perceptions towards them have been studied to very small degree and therefore the literature within this field is still very limited. Through those limited studies, researchers have termed these latent and hidden behaviours as the 'dark sides of CRM' (Nguyen and Simkin, 2009; Payne and Frow, 2013).

Past researchers have also stated that the reasons for these hidden practices are service provider's focus on transactions over relationships, which results in the genuine aim of CRM implementation being completely misinterpreted. For an instance, in business-to-consumer (B2C) relationships customer 'lock-in' has been considered as an appropriate strategy, being implemented with an aim to increase customer loyalty through prospects of cross-selling, keeping consumers bound to the business and eventually maximize profit through recurring incomes from existing sets

of customers (Farrell & Klemperer, 2007; Harrison et. al., 2012). Service providers are therefore attracted towards locking in their service users into relationships only to keep the transactions going, rather than focusing on mutually rewarding relationships.

As mentioned, very little attention has been placed on examining such behaviours and their consequences, which ultimately leads service providers to encourage the continuity of such practices. As a consequence, there are also instances when service users reject firms' dark behaviours when they realise that the service providers are keeping them in a disadvantaged position and are rather taking benefit of their trust and existing relationships. Service users' realisation and awareness of such disadvantaged position can result into negative word of mouth and dismissal, as harsh as relationship termination.

1.3.1 Research questions

- 1) What do customers perceive of the dark customer relationship management practices that are prevalent among UK mobile phone service providers?
- 2) What recommendations can be made regarding eliminating such dark behaviours and promoting transparent customer relationship practices?

1.3.2 Sub questions

- a) What kinds of service provider behaviours are termed as dark behaviours by service users?
- b) What behaviours do service users engage in after realising that they are in a disadvantaged position?
- c) What recommendations can be made with regard to establishing a win-win situation for both service providers and service users through transparent customer relationship management?

1.3.3 Research objectives

- a) To critically review current literature to identify gaps in the area of research.
- b) To examine the awareness of service users and their views on the perceived dark behaviours practiced by the MNOs.
- c) To outline the perceived dark behaviours being practiced by the MNOs.

- d) To identify the actions that service users take in response to becoming aware of their disadvantaged position.
- e) To recommend strategies for practitioners that can be implemented in eliminating such dark practices and encouraging fairer relationship behaviours.

1.4 Industry Background

Earlier research conducted by Payne and Frow suggested that Mobile operators and telecommunication companies are one of the most popular industry that are found to be practicing dark side activities of CRM (Payne and Frow, 2013). This includes confusing usage rate, vague pricing strategies, extremely unjustifiable penalty rates, misleading adverts and so on. As an answer to their call for future researchers, this research has selected UK mobile network operators as the industry in which to carry out this analysis. The United Kingdom's mobile market is the largest in Europe and has an approximate value of £14 billion annually (Gov, 2017), with 91.5 million mobile subscribers—as stated by Ofcom, the UK's national telecom regulator. The current report shows an increase of 1.6 million mobile phone subscribers since the last reported year (Ofcom, 2017).

In today's digital age, mobile devices and smartphones have become an essential part of people's daily lives. Aside from their use for voice calling and messaging, mobile devices also serve as mini-computers that provide people with access to entertainment, gaming, photography, education and more—and smartphone manufacturers are continuing to add and implement more innovative features as time goes by (Deloitte, 2020). As the demand for, and obsession with, mobile devices and smartphones grows, MNOs are capitalising the demand as an opportunity.

Competition with the UK mobile market is huge, and networks range from those provided by giants of the industry, such as British Telecom (BT), to smaller MVNOs like Sky and ID mobile. When choosing a mobile phone service and operator, there are key factors that consumers consider; these not only include performance—in terms of internet speed and network coverage—but also cost, handset type, quality of customer service and contract terms (Ofcom, 2017).

After a service user signs a mobile contract with their provider, they are obliged to stick with the brand for a minimum contract period. Customers often stick with their mobile network providers beyond the contract period if they are satisfied with the provider's customer service, the quality of the service, the brand's corporate social responsibility or simply as a result of their attachment to the brand. On the other hand, customers may be forced to stick with the brand due to exit barriers, such as switching costs, the contract period, the auto renewal of their contract, and so on. Firms often practice such behaviours to lock in their customers and to squeeze as much profit out of them as possible ignoring the relational aspect completely. There are evidence of service providers engaging in behaviours such as misleading customers, providing false information, misusing customer data, tracking customers' behaviour without their knowledge, and so on (Nguyen, 2012, Frow et. al., 2011). McGovern and Moon (2007, p. 80) stated that many firms are purposely taking advantage of customers by 'binding them with contracts, bleeding them with fees and confounding them with fine print'. They also identify that mobile phone service providers are one of the industries prone to such dark behaviours. Therefore, this study aims to explore the dark behaviours that are being practiced by mobile network providers in the UK in the name of customer relationship management. The researcher has chosen four leading mobile network operators in the UK, based on their popularity and number of subscribers: EE, O2, Vodafone and Three (Ofcom, 2017; Statista, 2020).

EE, previously known as Everything Everywhere and now part of the British Telecom Group, is the leading MNO in the UK and it has around 30 million customers/subscribers (EE, 2017). After rolling out 4G services in 2012, they reached a record number of subscribers. EE asserts that the 4G coverage it offers today covers more than 95% of the UK population. The geographical coverage of its 4G service is approximately 67%, and with an aim to cover 95% in 2020.

O2, the second largest MNO in the UK, has around 23 million subscribers. The Spanish telecommunications company Telefónica purchased O2 in 2006 when it was the part of the industry titan British Telecom. The company now handles half of Tesco Mobile's virtual network share, which operates on the O2 network in the UK. O2 started offering its 4G/ LTE service in mid-2013 and, in the third quarter of 2016, it declared that with its 4G service, it covered over 70% of the UK population.

Vodafone UK is the third leading MNO in the UK after EE and O2. It is the part of the Vodafone Group UK, which operating its network in 21 countries. Vodafone UK launched 4G in 2013 and has around 19.5 million subscribers. In June 2012, Vodafone and O2 signed a deal to pool their network technologies; thus, creating a single national grid of 18,500 transmitter sites (P3, 2016).

A subsidiary of Hutchison Whampoa, Three UK—which is known as 3—launched its mobile service in the UK in 2003. It is a comparatively young operator; however, after starting to offer its 4G/LTE service in 2013 it has expanded it swiftly all over the UK. The company has about 10.8 million subscribers and remains the smallest MNO in the UK; however, the company asserts that it carries over 40% of the country's data traffic (P3, 2018; Three, 2019). Given the fact that the company is the cheapest provider of 4G and unlimited data plans (excluding tethering), this claim is likely to be true.

Overall, according to P3 Communications, a Germany-based mobile network testing company, out of the four major mobile networks, EE and O2 are the biggest in terms of numbers of subscribers, followed narrowly by Vodafone, whilst Three is the smallest, which is strategically targeting customers with its aggressively-priced tariffs (P3, 2018).

1.4.1 Major failures of mobile network operators (MNOs)

Despite being identified as being the strongest players in the UK market, all of the so-called 'big four' MNOs have faced some major obstacles in terms of customer satisfaction and service failure that have inflicted significant damage to their customer relationship management. If viewed collectively, Vodafone and EE rule half the UK mobile market; however, they both score the worst in terms of customer satisfaction (Brignall, 2017). EE not only holds the record for the worst levels of customer satisfaction but also for value for money. Dissatisfaction is not limited to poor customer service (Ft.com, 2017); it extends to bill overcharging, breaching fundamental billing policy, and so on—for which the company was charged £2.7 million by Ofcom (Guardian, 2017). Records show that almost 40,000 consumers were swindled out of a collective sum of £250,000 (Ofcom, 2017a). However, Ofcom's recent figures

indicate that EE's customer service has improved following these penalties; it now has the third lowest number of complaints in the mobile industry.

Likewise, EE's rival Vodafone was given a similar penalty last year to the tune of £4.6 million, as the result of having ill-treated customers and overlooked complaints. It was found that the company's customer care team and customer service staffs required necessarily clear guidance and trainings on quality customer service. Additionally, they also failed on crediting the accounts of approximately 10,000 Pay As You Go customers who had topped up their accounts to the tune of £150,000 over 17 months (BBC News, 2017; Ofcom, 2017b).

On 6 October 2016, Three experienced an emergency service crash, which lead to the company being served a penalty charge of £1.9 million. As per the Communications Act 2003 (Ofcom, 2015, p.10), every communication provider must ensure that their emergency services are uninterrupted, and Three was found to be failing to comply (Ofcom, 2017d).

To add on similar malpractices, in 2003, a case was filed that stated that a number of MNOs, including Vodafone, were engaged in price fixing, price overcharging and applying termination charges (Subiotto and Snelders, 2004 p. 178–179).

Below are some facts and figures about the UK mobile industry that are compiled according to telecommunications market data released by Ofcom (Ofcom, 2020).

Facts and Figures

Mobile telephony services generated £3.4bn in retail revenues in Q3 2019, a £129m (3.7%) decrease from a year previously.

Average revenue per subscriber in Q3 2019 was £13.35, with post-pay subscribers generating more revenue than pre-pay subscribers (at £17.03 and £4.86 respectively).

The number of active mobile subscriptions (excluding M2M) was 84.9 million at the end of Q3 2019, up 0.9 million (1.1%) from a year previously. Over the same period, the number of dedicated mobile broadband subscriptions decreased by 0.1 million (1.6%), to 4.5 million.

The number of outgoing mobile voice calls minutes was 39.6 billion in Q3 2019, down 0.2 billion (0.6%) from a year previously.

The number of mobile messages (including SMS and MMS) continued to decline over the same period, down 2.7 billion (14.5%), while data usage continued to increase rapidly, up 245PB (38.3%) year-on-year.

Table 1. 1 Facts and figures (Ofcom, 2020, p.1)

1.5 Methodology of the Study and the Data Collection Procedure

This section aims to briefly familiarise readers with the research methodology and data collection processes that are used in this study. For clarity, it has been divided into four parts: research background, division of the analysis, research methodology and data analysis.

1.5.1 Research background

To understand the perceptions of service users towards dark practices, the researcher has selected the UK mobile network operator industry. Such latent and dark practices are prevalent in several other sectors, including retail and FMCG; however, the researcher has chosen MNOs as this industry involves a remarkably high investment from end users' perspectives in comparison to FMCG or the retail sector. While the positive impact of customer relationship management and relationship marketing are receiving a lot of scholarly attention, especially in the service industry, the use of unfair practices (both intentional or unintentional) are growing in parallel in practice.

Another reason for choosing the MNO industry for this study is the visibility of increasing popularity of customisation of offers in mobile network plans and contracts. Service providers are using consumer data collected through customer touchpoints, CRM tools and software in order to maximise consumer satisfaction and increase profitability through customisation of offers. CRM strategy may lead firms to offer some customers comparatively more favourably, as CRM principally advocated the notion of handling customers differently with an idea that each individual is different and has distinctive wants, and therefore, every individual customer will receive a distinctive offer. However, some of the offers may trigger question of equality and cause dissatisfaction ultimately resulting in mistrust that leads to break the relationship with existing service (Nguyen, Jaber and Simkin, 2020; Nguyen, 2012).

Data collection for this study, both qualitative and quantitative, has been conducted over the online brand communities, including Facebook Page, Twitter and Community forums. of the big four MNOs in the UK. The increasing interactivity and habit of using of Web pages and social media platforms during past decade has budded the concept of “online brand communities”. In this digitalized era full of information technology and ever emerging social platforms, OBCs are not just popular amongst global customers but also an impartial part of business and customer strategy for the businesses. Online brand community (OBC) has been defined as a “specialized, non-geographically bound community, based on a structured set of social relations among admirers of a brand” (Muniz and O’guinn, 2001, p. 412). Businesses do not only use these communities to interact and advertise their products and services, but also to learn about their customers, their behaviours and other customer knowledge, however businesses are also found manipulate OBCs for their benefit. There are many examples of firms who have been found to be deleting genuine comments that are negative or adding fake positive reviews and comments that rate their products or services more highly. A study by Zhuang et al. (2018) defined this as manufactured opinion. Few clues are available about the fact that manipulation is taking place in the case of businesses deleting information, as consumers do not readily suspect manipulative intent; thus, this manipulation results in higher purchase intention and adverse selection. However, consumers with substantial expertise in online shopping are less vulnerable to the influence of manipulation due to their heightened levels of suspicion.

Further on examining the scope of unfair activities and service provider's practices of opportunism, past studies have identified that the mobile industry has been engaging in hidden activities, such as complex pricing strategies, customer confusion and manipulation, especially in vulnerable segments of the population all fuelled by customer data and the insights created through CRM systems and strategies (Nguyen, Simkin and Canhoto, 2015). As scholars have outlined, oftentimes firms involve in unethical behaviours and dark activities as a result of negligence other than intent to exploit customers but despite the intent, customers are the victim and it is necessary for the firms to practice in such a way that they are not just legally bound but also ethically obliged to foster elimination of any dark sides associated with customer, customer relationship and relationship management.

1.5.2 Division of the analysis

The key focus of the analysis carried out in this study is mobile service users and their perceptions, which, in theory, comprises every individual who uses a mobile phone. As the study aims to understand customers' perceptions of service providers' behaviours, mobile service users are undoubtedly the best observers as they are the direct targets—and often the victims—of such behaviours. In order to achieve this study's aim and to best answer the research questions, a mixed methods research design is thought to be most suitable. Furthermore, the researcher has chosen Netnography as the qualitative research method and the use of an online survey as the quantitative method for this study.

In service marketing research, understanding customers' experiences is imperative. Service users are vocal about their experiences more than ever as a result of today's technological advancements. Through particular brand communities and related platforms, they can easily interact with service providers, share their concerns, complain or simply pass on feedback (Anderson et al., 2013). Such platforms therefore contain vast amount of customer data that both firms and researchers can capitalise on. A discussion of firms capitalising on customer data will follow in subsequent chapters. In this study, the researcher will use the experiences of service users as the main source of data. Netnography is often described as being a form of online ethnography, and it is comprised of the observation of data via the internet (Kozinets,

2018; Costello, McDermott and Wallace, 2017). The researcher has chosen Netnography mainly as a result of the ease with which data can be acquired and because of the richness and rawness of the data that it generates.

The researcher in this study uses Netnography as the basis on which to sample the respondents for both the quantitative and qualitative stages of data collection. The major benefit of choosing the samples through observation is the fact that there is a higher chance of the researcher gathering informative/purposeful samples for use in this study. Passively watching and analysing the comments and experiences shared on brand communities will give the researcher a first-hand raw view of customers' experiences. This is crucial because this study aims to explore the perceptions of service users. Based on accounts of its use, it is evident that Netnography has been implemented by the market researchers to study online branding strategies (Tynan et al., 2010; Rosenthal and Brito, 2017) and consumer engagement (Hollebeek and Chen, 2014). Furthermore, researchers have even recommended that service industry researchers and experts should use Netnography as a market research instrument (Heinonen, 2014; Heinonen and Medberg, 2018) as it offers vast opportunities for researchers to access unadulterated online data about customers in a process that involves expending less effort and fewer resources.

The samples/respondents for the quantitative online survey will be chosen from the brand communities as well; this will help the researcher to select samples from customers who actually have an opinion about their service providers. The use of open communication platforms and brand communities will enable the researcher to select the right respondents for the online survey. The initial period of observation played an essential part in the formulation of the research questionnaires for the survey.

The online survey was piloted among fellow researchers to ensure that the questions included in the survey precisely answered the research questions. Similarly, the pilot test also checked whether the online link to the survey worked well, and if the questionnaire was clear, easy to understand and presented in a consistent manner. The web-based online survey was then posted on the selected brand communities (Facebook for EE, Vodafone and Three) and community forum (O2) with a non-probability sampling.

1.5.3 Research methodology

In order to address and explore this neglected but extremely crucial area of CRM, a mixed methods research approach was felt to be appropriate. Generally speaking, the research on consumer behaviour follows a qualitative approach that follows the mantra of 'the deeper the insight, the better the findings'; therefore, the researcher included some quantitative data along with qualitative data, thus creating a mixed methods research design. Mixed methods research enhances the credibility and enrichment of the findings through the triangulation of data. If looked into past research, we can see the combination of Netnography with other methods such as ethnography (McGrath et. al., 2013), interviews (Bengtsson et al., 2005) and surveys (Chan and Li, 2010). The researcher has also chosen to combine Netnography with an online survey in this study.

The online survey includes a mix of open- and close- ended questions. The open-ended questionnaire structure is used to allow respondents to express additional views and experiences, which helps the researcher to generate rich data. For the qualitative data, as introduced above, the researcher makes use of Netnography and the data is collected through virtual observation of the big four MNOs' online brand communities.

With the objective of gaining informative participants the online survey will also be posted on the online brand communities of the four MNOs; particularly on their official Facebook page. The researcher selected Facebook as it is one of the most used social media platforms in the UK. Additionally, the use of Facebook adds further integrity to the responses as there are some people who do not like to post their comments publicly on brand communities but who are willing to share their experiences in private through surveys.

Online surveys include the combination of open- and close- ended questions; however, there is a significant focus on close-ended questions. Open-ended questions were included in order to gain descriptive insights from the participants. Those additional open- ended responses will be further analysed using thematic analysis and add on to the findings. The researcher targeted to combine quantitative (Netnography)

and quantitative data (online survey) from the same Online Brand Community to help to validate the observations (Chan and Li, 2010).

1.5.4 Data analysis

Data analysis in a mixed method research is potentially the most challenging step; as the researcher has to proficiently study both sets of data individually, as well as integrate the results generated from two separate analysis (Onwuegbuzie and Combs, 2011). This is complex in terms of both time and the effort required to complete such a task. This was a challenge in this particular study due to the fact that the time available to the researcher was very limited.

As mentioned by Creswell and Plano Clark (2007), “Data analysis in mixed methods research consists of analysing the quantitative data using quantitative methods and the qualitative data using qualitative methods” (p. 128). The data in this study will be analysed concurrently with no particular sequence or priority to one particular data set.

In addition, in terms of analysing data in the mixed methods research, equal priority can be given to the individual components of the qualitative and quantitative analysis or one analysis element can be given a comparatively higher priority than that of other. This often depends on the research question or aim of the research. In this research, despite the importance of both the quantitative and qualitative approaches, the researcher places a greater emphasis on the qualitative analysis; thus, yielding a qualitative-dominant mixed analysis as per the aim of the research as a whole. The motive for combining quantitative and qualitative analysis is purely on the grounds of complementarity and extension (Greene et. al., 1989; Greene, 2015).

1.6 Scope of the Research

As suggested earlier, no extant studies have been undertaken that examine how the implementation and motive of CRM is being altered; how firms are misusing customer data as a result of their focus on their own gains rather than customer value co-creation; and how firms are confusing and abusing the customer relationship through poor customer relationship management. Consequences of practicing such dark behaviours with malicious motives can cost overall buyer supplier relationship.

This research revolves around understanding the perceptions of customers, service users of UK MNOs, in relation to how the relationship with their service providers is being exploited by the firms; how the relationship instruments, including trust and loyalty, are being abused for firms' own benefit instead of for mutual benefit; and how concerns of unfairness and non-differential treatment are being ignored by the service providers.

The key focus of this study is to examine whether customers are aware of such behaviours or not, and if and how are they reacting to them. Are they questioning the service provider about their behaviour or are they letting them go unchallenged and switching service provider? Another area of interest in this study is the question as to whether customers may also be involved in dark behaviours, such as spreading negative word of mouth, verbally abusing front desk officers or customer service departments, providing incorrect information, and so on. A final area of interest is uncovering whether some portion of service users might not even be aware of what their service providers do with the data they provide or of the fact that their bills are higher than they are supposed to be. It is imperative for customers to be aware of any neglect and unfair treatment that occurs at the hands of their service providers. Acknowledgement of individual responsibility will not only cause the buyer-seller relationship to flourish; it will also add value to CRM as a whole.

Some of the notable works published in the area of dark sides of CRM include pitfalls of CRM, dark sides of CRM and unfairness among customers (Nguyen, 2020; Nguyen et. al., 2015; Nguyen & Simkin, 2012; Nguyen, 2009; Frow et. al., 2011); however, more light needs to be shed on this area of study through further exploration. Nguyen's recent research has defined four main drivers of the 'dark sides' of CRM that includes unfairness, distrust, opportunism and lack of transparency. They have called for future researchers to structure and manage the dark side concept more systematically, also considering properties of dark side behaviours in relation to CRM (Nguyen, Jaber and Simkin, 2020). Bearing that in mind, this study is being undertaken so that existing dark side activities prevalent in the UK MNOs can be identified and make the related stakeholders aware about them and their consequences.

1.7 Contribution of the Study

The theoretical contribution of this research will be relevant to the literature on the dark side of CRM; specifically adding to the knowledge of existing dark side behaviours. It will provide further information about service users' level of awareness about dark behaviours and how they respond when they become aware of their disadvantaged position. Users' awareness and them calling out about such dark practices will cause service providers to be more careful and to eliminate such concealed activities, and to instead concentrate on fairer practices that ultimately aim to improve the long-term firm-customer relationship (N'Goala, 2015). The researcher acknowledges that a lack of awareness about and the lack of visibility of such dark behaviours is encouraging service providers to continue to deviate from fairer practices in order keep maximising their profits.

In addition to filling the gap in the literature regarding the concept, practices and consequences of the dark side of CRM, this study focuses on the need of strategic implementation in eliminating dark sides practices. Phan and Vogel on their study stated that the businesses are implementing CRM applications without considering the trust and fairness, elements of relationship management, at the strategic level (Phan & Vogel, 2010) and findings of this study clearly supports those assertions. While the implementation of CRM is getting popular day-by-day, trust in the businesses, particularly the service providers, retailers and the media is diminishing (Huang & Wang, 2013), which is the result of the consumers increasing awareness of them being misused and violated by the businesses that they trust.

To focus on the practicality and strategic implication, this study proposes expanding the CRM strategy framework that has already been established by Payne and Frow (2013) and calls for the practitioners to implement an enlightened framework in their strategic decision making to eliminate dark sides of CRM. The expansion on original framework includes the addition of a few more essential processes to specifically address the new dark side behaviours identified through this research; these additions aim to both expand the CRM framework and to make it more holistic. The implementation of recommended strategic processes framework will ensure the fairer customer relationship practices as advised by the work of Payne and Frow and will

establish “learning relationship” between the service users and the service providers (Peppers and Rogers 2001, p. 151) which is that dual value co-creating that a successful CRM implementation seeks for.

Ever since initial days, marketing and the marketing related functions, including CRM and customer management, lacks positive character amongst customers, therefore, their effectiveness and success have always been the victims of such negative reputation. Studies have revealed that people hold negative views of marketing as a discipline in itself. Sheth et al. (2006)’s research showed that only 8% of respondents had a positive outlook on marketing. In another study, when asked to describe marketing, respondents used words such as ‘lies’, ‘invasive’, ‘intrusive’, ‘exaggeration’, ‘gimmicks’, ‘deception’, and so on (Nguyen et al., 2015). Such an outlook towards marketing certainly adds to the negative perception of firms if firms fail to meet customers’ expectations even to a small degree or if they fail to operate ethically. Therefore, it is imperative more than ever for firms to address fairness, transparency and ethical considerations, as consumers are more educated than ever and are aware of having the upper hand within the buyer–seller relationship spectrum. The rise of the internet and online information sharing capabilities is certainly responsible for increased customer power. Customers are aware of the role of customer knowledge in firms’ operations and profitability and are therefore equally concerned about how firms collect customer data, their use of behaviour tracking systems and how ethical and transparent they are in their CRM activities. Customers are also conscious of the issues related to data and customer exploitation in the name of customer management and look out for behaviours such as manipulation, deception tactics, privacy invasion, data mishandling, and so on. As scholars have outlined, firms oftentimes become involved in unethical behaviours and dark activities as a result of negligence rather than their desire to exploit their customers. However, despite firms’ intentions, customers are the victims, and it is necessary for firms to behave in such a way that they are not just legally bound but also ethically obliged to pursue the elimination of any dark sides associated with customers, the customer relationship and relationship management.

Despite CRM and the concept of customer relationship greatly revolving around moral factors like trust and emotions, the element of ethics, which is crucial a factor to build

trust in a relationship, has been greatly ignored (Bull and Adam, 2011). Scholars have established that the conventional CRM philosophy lacks a holistic approach and is mainly based on a narrow construct that fails to consider the ethical issues appropriately, which sadly has not been any different even after several studies highlighting the need of change. Organisations must implement holistic approach in CRM along with careful considerations of ethical elements.

Furthermore, the researcher believes that focusing on the need for awareness of, and the need to highlight, the existence of dark side behaviours in both service providers and service users will attract the attention of governing bodies and policy makers and lead them to develop superior rules and regulations. It is absolutely necessary for governing bodies and policy makers to formulate policies that cultivate fairer practices and encourage dual value co-creation through customer relationship management, which, at its core, is the fundamental idea behind the philosophy of CRM.

Overall, it must be understood that not all firms who collect customer data and build portfolios are to be blamed for using their customers' data and using it to gain insights and knowledge to deliver better products and services; however, they must be criticised if their intentions are manipulative and exploitative in any way. To explain this, Sheer (2011) stated that manipulation, deception and exploitation are immoral regardless of whether the invasive tactics harm customers and whether such actions are within the law. Oftentimes, despite being within the law, firm's intention to manipulate and misuse is 'wrong'. Awareness and understanding of such ill intentions is what gives the service users a perception that there is a 'dark' side to their relationship with their service providers. Studies have also revealed that practitioners/marketers are often unaware of the ethical issues associated with their actions, as they put their focus on whether they are legally right or not; however, such excuses are no longer tolerable, as the necessity of taking an ethical viewpoint, ensuring privacy and meeting moral obligations in CRM has been highlighted by scholars, independent researchers and even policy makers for a significant period of time (N'Goala, 2015). Furthermore, with regard to data and information misuse, a Harvard Business Review article (Morey, Forbath and Schoop, 2015) stated that although some companies practice transparent data strategies, a large number choose to keep consumers in the dark about the volume of data gathered and their

level of control over it being shared; such companies ask for forgiveness rather than permission in cases where customers find out about such misuses.

This study emphasises that dark side practices are primarily the result of treating CRM as a sales tool rather than a relationship-building mechanism; Müller stated in his study that it often offers a platform for service providers to practice dark side behaviours (Müller, 2014). To reiterate again, no CRM is manipulative or deceptive in itself, and the idea behind this research is not to discourage or eliminate the use of technologically advanced CRM applications, philosophies and approaches in any way, but rather to find the causes of dark side practices and to highlight the consequences and repercussions of what happens when such practices are engaged in by practitioners. In addition to identifying the dark side practices conducted by MNOs with the objective of raising awareness of them, this study will discuss the strategic considerations that can be adopted, and the organisational changes that can be introduced, by MNOs to eliminate the dark sides of CRM and enable them to achieve their fundamental objective of implementing CRM.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Introduction

This chapter contains an evaluation and review of the current literature that relates to and supports the objectives of this research. It provides an understanding of customer relationship management and the dark side behaviours that exist in the service industry and identifies the reasons behind firms' practice of such behaviours. Similarly, it also reviews the notion behind service user's awareness and 'perception' towards unfair behaviours and followed by magnitudes of their awareness. Overall, the content of this chapter revolves around a discussion of relationship marketing, customer relationship management, the dark side behaviours practiced by the service providers that can cost the buyer–seller relationship and an examination of the theories that will make it possible to answer the research question of this study.

This chapter is split into three sections. Firstly, the chapter provides an explanation of the significance of customer relationship management (CRM), relationship management and customer management as interrelated areas of marketing. After beginning by providing a review of the definition of CRM, the chapter discusses the evolution of CRM, the development of CRM offerings, the current situation of CRM and failures in CRM implementation, thereby revealing the possible gaps in the CRM literature that are significant to the current study.

Second, the researcher discusses the dark side behaviours prevalent in the service industry at the moment. This reveals the need for further exploration in this area, as there are several other prevalent practices that have not been researched. These dark side behaviours must become more visible through research in order to discourage the use of these unfair practices. Further, this section of the chapter discusses how CRM is related to customer data, transformation of data into knowledge and dual value creation. It also addresses customers' perceptions of the fairness of CRM by drawing on fairness literature and by introducing the concept of service quality and how service quality plays role of CRM. Service quality has been discussed as a separate concept due to the fact that a number of the dark behaviours practiced by service providers are the consequences of service quality and service delivery failure. Dark sides raised

by the service failures can be addressed by an effective implementation of service quality management process, which will be been introduced and discussed on the recommendation chapter later.

Third, the researcher highlights the theoretical foundations behind consumers' perceptions of unfairness and how they evaluate their position of being unfairly treated by their service providers. This includes theories such as equity theory, justice theory and the theory of opportunism. Additionally, the researcher also introduces the theory of reasoned action in order to justify why a service user behaves in a certain way when they realise that they have been treated unfairly by their service provider. The dark side behaviours engaged in by service provides can result in darker behaviours from the service users themselves. This section of the chapter will provide a summary of this issue that identifies the potential gaps in knowledge regarding advantaged and disadvantaged inequality judgements.

Relationship Marketing, Customer Relationship Management & Customer Management

Relationship Marketing (RM), Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Customer Management (CM) are correlated and often used as interchangeable concept, but it is vital to understand that they are three individual concepts that are functions to each other. The figure diagram below, created by Payne and Frow (2017, p.17), clarifies the overlapping and inclusive concept of customer relationship management.

Table 2. 1 Relationship Marketing, CRM and Customer Management, adapted from Payne and Frow, 2017, p. 12

2.1 Relationship Marketing

Built on the theory of economics, relationship marketing originates from institutional economics, which was later connected to marketing; it has a specific focus on exchange theory and includes disciplines such as sociology, psychology and political science (Palmatier et. al., 2008, Palmatier and Steinhoff, 2019). Relationship marketing has been under the research microscope for more than three decades after the term was coined by Berry, and it has been in existence since the 1983 (Tadajewski and Saren, 2009; Payne and Frow, 2017); the importance of relationships, their practical focus and substantial rise on scholarly attention confirms that RM's relevance is growing, and that there are many new avenues to explore.

Most of the existing definitions of RM emphasise the necessity of maintaining and managing relationships with and amongst all relevant stakeholders (Payen and Frow, 2013; Gummesson, 2004; Morgan and Hunt, 1994). In practice, the focus is mostly limited to firm–customer relationships, while leaving suppliers, human resources and other stakeholders frequently ignored. There are some exceptional views, such as those of Sheth (1996), who argues that the concept should be confined to satisfying the needs of customers only. Studies later revealed the importance of stakeholder relationships and interdependencies in value creation (Adner and Kapoor, 2010; Kapoor, 2018). Additionally, the increasing interdependencies and collaboration in the network today, which are also the result of the development of and dependency on

digital technologies in the industry, clearly reflect the need for RM to embody a broader range of relationships (Payen and Frow, 2017).

The concept of RM was originated in the realm of industrial marketing (Levitt, 1983) and further adapted into service marketing (Gummesson, 1977; Grönroos, 1983). It was Berry's use of the exact phrase 'relationship marketing' that generated interest and resulted in the real visibility of the term to academics and practitioners (Berry, 1995). Since then, various studies in the RM discipline have been undertaken that do not limit study to sellers and end consumers; rather, they incorporate a much broader range of stakeholders (Christopher et. al., 1991; Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Payne and Frow, 2013). Researchers have however argued on how attention is limited to its maintenance of relation than its commencement, especially considering the fact that how relationship has been initiated affects the overall stability and strength of relations (Gummerus et. al., 2017).

RM is often represented as a paradigm shift in marketing (Berry, 1983; Gummesson, 1997). It evolved in response to firms' realisation that there was a need to secure returning customers and extend their lifetime value. Researchers studied RM as firm's move from transaction to relational exchange (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) which was then explored in relation to the complementary concepts like customer satisfaction, trust and commitment, value co-creation and so on (Berry, 1995; Morgan and Hunt, 1995). As much as the positives of customer relationship and the need of customer retention are deemed essential, they were also questioned by researchers like Jackson (1985) who through her research defined relationship marketing as an opposed idea to the transaction marketing but drew a conclusion that although firms target long term relationship through relationship marketing, short term perspectives can be ideal sometimes. Jackson later backed up this argument by stating that everything depends on the situation. Later on, Gummesson (1999, p. 185) also presented the concept 'service paradox', which advises that the most loyal customers do not always mean the most profitable.

In regard to critics, some studies have questioned relationship marketing for the efforts that a firm need to apply to build the relationship with customers and if the outcome is worth those efforts (Gummesson, 2004). Likewise, Harwood and Garry (2006) also

identified that some relationship marketers have a feeling of 'Why bother?' when it comes to creating and sustaining relationships. Likewise, one of the studies also explored 'loyalty', an element of successful relationship that has practically always been viewed as being positive for businesses, can be disadvantageous at times (Glyn, 2011).

On the other hand, very few studies have been carried out to understand whether consumers actually like the relational aspect of marketing (Jones et al., 2015) and it has been uncovered that not all customers want to cultivate relationships with their service suppliers (Ward and Dagger, 2007).

2.1.1 Conceptual background - why relational exchange?

"There is only one valid definition of business purpose: to create a satisfied customer"
(Drucker, 1954, p. 37)

We are living in an era in which customers are not just unreceptive service receivers; rather, they are educated analysers and independent value creators (Grönroos, 2006) who examine all the available alternatives when deciding on the service provider they most want to be in a relationship with. Such knowledge of the available alternatives makes customers more empowered than ever. Therefore, if service providers aim to have a competitive advantage, they must provide service users with superior service. Service providers should move away from mere strategies to create loyalty and retention bases, rather focus on actual communication, information transparency, the cultivation of trust and overall relationship maintenance.

A relationship is not a hit and miss matter; nor is it something that happens overnight. It goes through series of stages that have their own characteristics, as is mentioned in the relationship cycle (Tzokas and Saren, 2004). In the simplest possible terms, as defined by Payne and his fellow researchers, a "relationship is a state of being connected" (Payne et. al., 2006, p. 856). Fundamentally, a relationship in RM is not limited to customers; rather, it incorporates firms' overall stakeholders, both internal and external. Consumers, however, are at the core, as is stated in the six markets identified in their stakeholder model (Christopher et. al., 1991; Payne et. al., 2006).

Figure 2. 1 The six markets model, adapted from Payne et. al., 2005, p.860

Undoubtedly, the phenomenon of relational exchange is the basis of marketing. Although most studies highlight the partnership between suppliers and customers, that is not the limit. The necessity of maintaining favourable internal relationships is often highlighted stating the strengths and outcomes of these relationships are said to be directly proportional to the strengths and outcomes of firms' relationships with external customers (Catlette and Hadden, 2001; Gummesson, 2000). Having said that, researchers and practitioners constantly ignore the impact of internal relationships on firms' profitability (Herington, Johnson and Scott, 2006).

While focusing on the development of RM, there is a visible shift. Having originated as a tiny concept within mainstream marketing, today it is a central pillar of marketing's paradigm shift; as Gummesson mentioned, "when relationship marketing, CRM, and services marketing are combined with a network view they become drivers of a paradigm shift in marketing" (2004, p. 139). Overall, the notion of relationship marketing has now developed from being a sub-discipline to a mainstream academic area of marketing (Vargo and Lusch, 2008).

RM has widely been defined as a process (Parvatiyar and Sheth, 2001; Palmatier et. al, 2008), and the processes involved in RM are based on the primary theory of customer value, which is a foundational concept because until value is created and

provided to customers, firms have no authentic motive for their existence, nor can they achieve their ultimate organisational goals (Drucker, 1999; Christopher et al., 1991). Likewise, the notion of customer value also incorporates customer satisfaction, which eventually leads to customer retention, which is the concept that RM revolves around (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999). For all these reasons, customer retention has been termed as the cause and effect of relationship marketing (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) and firms' overall long-term profitability.

2.1.2 Existing Definitions of Relationship Marketing

Ever since the concept was conceived by Berry, relationship management has been defined by various researchers in several ways.

Existing definitions of RM	Berry (1983, p. 25): "Attracting, maintaining and—in multi-service organizations—enhancing customer relationships."
	Porter (1993, p. 14): "Relationship marketing is the process whereby both parties— the buyer and provider—establish an effective, efficient, enjoyable, enthusiastic and ethical relationship: one that is personally, professionally and profitability rewarding to both parties."
	Morgan and Hunt (1994, p. 22): "Relationship marketing refers to all marketing activities directed to establishing, developing and maintaining successful relational exchanges."
	Sheth and Parvatiyar (2000, p. 9): Relationship marketing is "the ongoing process of engaging in cooperative and collaborative activities and programs with immediate and end-user customers to create or enhance mutual economic value at reduced cost."
	Grönroos (2007, p. 29): "[The aim of relationship] marketing is to identify and establish, maintain and enhance, and when necessary terminate relationships with customers (and other parties) so that the objectives regarding economic and other variables of all parties are met. This is achieved through a mutual exchange and fulfilment of promises."
	Gummesson (2008, p. 5): "[R]elationship marketing is interaction in networks of relationships."

Table 2. 2 Existing definitions of Relationship Marketing

Overall, most definitions of RM convey a core philosophy of mutually rewarding two parties, thus creating a win-win situation. Although it was previously contained within trust and mutual exchange, relationship exchange today has expanded its focus into sub-disciplines like customer lifetime value (via multiple transactions), customer satisfaction, customer value, value co-creation, loyalty and retention.

2.1.3 Relationship Marketing and the Service Industry

Originally, the idea of relationship marketing (RM) began within the area of service and industrial marketing (Christopher et al., 1991; Gummesson, 1991; Lindergreen et al., 2006). Even today, RM is comparatively eminent in the service industry; however, it is equally significant within the product industry. For a product manufacturer for whom the product and its ability to satisfy the need is the core objective, their definitive focus will be on selling to consumers at level higher than above their competitors. Grönroos (2006) therefore suggested vendors of consumer goods or industrial products to incorporate a service logic that concentrates on adding value through the processes in which those products are. In recent times, shift towards service led growth is widely popular (Kowalkowski et. al., 2017).

Relationship marketing has become a platform or a process through which customers are integrated into the betterment of products and services through their involvement in and consultation about the design, development, production and delivery of products. Specifically, in the service industry, service quality is a major factor of customer satisfaction, which is then followed by loyalty and retention. Even during the early days of RM, the organisation's main focus would be on improving service quality in order to meet customers' expectations, which resulted to the development of several methodologies and management frameworks (Zeithaml et al., 1996), one of them being total quality management (TQM).

Although the popularity of RM is wide-spread, for both the industry experts and academics, RM is still understood as a tool by which to measure and manage loyalty programs and to segment the market on the basis of customer profitability analysis based on loyalty (Sheth, 2017). The analysis are measured in terms of numbers like

retention rate of ROI in terms of recurring purchase ignoring the emotional, relational and communication aspect of customers.

2.1.4 Do customers actually want relationships?

Amid the recent hype about relationships and their competitive advantages for firms, it is necessary to examine whether customers really want to be in a relationship with firms and service providers or not. Not many studies have explored this side of relationship management; however, Dowling (2002) has challenged the concept that every customer wants to develop a bond with the businesses that they custom from. Put simply, people do not see relevance or have time and drive to build relationships with every brand they make transactions with. In a study published in *Harvard Business Review*, Freeman and his colleagues further argued that this issue is one of the myths about what customers really want (Freeman et al., 2012). In their study, they also pointed out that it is important for firms to understand who wants a relationship and who does not. They revealed that 77% of consumers did not want relationship with brands; thus, highlighting that there is no correlation between consumer interaction and their likelihood of sticking with a brand.

2.2 Customer Relationship Management

Customer relationship management originally evolved as a functional marketing tool in the mid 1990s, following the economic recession of the early 1980s and the entry of computerisation into service sectors (Sheth, 2017); within three decades, CRM has become an integral part of marketing strategies and decisions (Kumar and Reinartz, 2012). This growth in interest on CRM and CRM system implementation, in recent times, has been enabled by foreseeable development in web and internet technologies (Gummerus, Koskull and Kowalkowski, 2017; Greenberg, 2001).

Once termed as a top business buzzword (Storbacka and Lehtinen, 2000), CRM is still interchangeably used with RM; however, it is crucial for them to be considered as being interrelatedly distinct (Shukla, 2010). CRM views relationships with existing customers and prospects as being key to firms' success, but managers often miss the point of managing these relationships. Most CRM software and methods used today are utterly product and business centric, meaning that firms place an emphasis on

selling more and that they eventually ignore aspects like customer support and value co-creation (Grönroos, 2008). Such a complete focus on transactions can lead firms to misuse customers' data and information, ultimately resulting in unwanted behaviours that are referred to as the 'dark side' of CRM (Boulding et al., 2005).

2.2.1 CRM definitions and myths

While the interest and implications of CRM is increasing globally, there is still no universal definition of CRM and that its meaning has several interpretations (McKie, 2000; Abbott, 2001; Buttle, 2009; Zablah et al., 2003). Until some years ago, CRM was taken as a core operational function; however, this belief is changing over time. People are now looking at CRM as being part of the strategic and analytical functions of business and the shift has been credited to the development in internet and technologies. As mentioned by Chikweche and Fletcher (2013), CRM has experienced a paradigm shift mainly because of the propagation of online communities and as a result of the overall development, and use, of the internet.

While this paradigm shift is being established, researchers are neglecting the fact that CRM is not only a technological solution. Even though some studies have identified being 'technologically centric' as one of the reasons behind CRM failure, academics and practitioners seem to be overlooking this issue (Crosby, 2002; Rigby and Bilodeau, 2009). As mentioned by Crosby, practitioners should understand that 'technology' is just an enabler of CRM. Technology can bring about the expected outcomes only if it is holistically integrated with the people and processes that are generally employed in collaboration with the ultimate business mission. Ironically, it is mostly the case that employees are the last ones to be conferred with about the use, structures and returns associated with implementing CRM systems within businesses. However, it has been recognised that employees are the central pillar of the delivery of CRM systems and their overall activities; without suitable human interface and collaboration with these processes and systems, the returns on investment in CRM are a huge gamble. It has also been identified that relationships and the impact of people in the overall marketing realm is the least attended to area within this discipline; thus, it requires scholarly attention (Vorhies and Morgan, 2005).

Some of the most significant definitions of CRM that have evolved since its origination are listed below:

Existing definitions of CRM	Anton (1996): CRM is an integrated approach to maintaining relationships.
	Xu et al. (2002, p.442): “[CRM is] an all-embracing approach, which seamlessly integrates sales, customer service, marketing, fieldwork support and other functions that touch customers.”
	Payne and Frow (2005, p. 168): “[CRM is] a strategic approach that is concerned with creating improved shareholder value through the development of appropriate relationships with key customers and customer segments. CRM unties the potential of relationship marketing strategies and IT to create profitable, long-term relationships with customers and other key stakeholders.”
	Sin et al. (2005, p. 1266): “[CRM is] a comprehensive strategy and process that enables an organisation to identify, acquire, return and nurture profitable customers by building and maintaining long-term relationships with them.”
	Buttle (2004): CRM is the central business strategy that brings together internal processes and external networks to produce value directed towards customer benefits.
	Ernst et al. (2011): CRM is an approach implemented with the objective of improving new product development and overall performance.
	Boulding et al. (2005, p.6): “CRM relates to strategy, managing the dual-creation or value, the intelligent use of data and technology, the acquisition of customer knowledge and the diffusion of this knowledge to the appropriate stakeholders, the development of appropriate (long-term) relationships with specific customers and/or customer groups, and the integration of processes across the many areas of the firm and across the network of firms that collaborate to generate customer value.”

Table 2. 3 Existing definitions of Relationship Marketing

Despite the fact that CRM has been accepted by academics for a significant amount of time, there is not any holistic definition of CRM. On a positive note, this might indicate the emergent nature of CRM and the fact that it is in a state of constant development. From the definitions stated above, some key aspects of CRM are customer-centric strategies, integrated approaches, process involvement and technological empowerment. Among all of these aspects, the customer-centric focus is the key theoretic facet of the CRM system.

The extensive association of CRM definition to technology has given a technologic centric understanding to the practitioners. Payne and Frow (2005, p. 168) raised this issue by stating that the “definition [of CRM] significantly affects the way an entire organization accepts and practices CRM”. In order to reduce such misinterpretations and confusions about CRM and CRM technology, Payne and Frow came up with a continuum (see below), that simplifies and presents the most easily understandable interpretation of CRM.

Figure 2. 2 The CRM Continuum, adapted from Payne and Frow (2005), p. 168

Researchers have identified several limitations in relation to CRM, often referred to as myths (Crosby, 2002). Crosby through his study listed several myths in CRM that require closer considerations and further academic exploration. He pinpointed the fact that companies can become over-dependent on technology, can fail to see CRM's its strategic perspective, practice faulty matrices, ignore the importance of market segmentation, neglect brand perspectives, get overwhelmed by the quantity of data, and so on. Management needs a clear picture of what a CRM as a strategy involves

and it is equally important for both the management and employees to understand that CRM is not just a quick-fix solution (Crosby, 2002) but an ongoing inclusive process. Functional integration and organisational learning plays a dominant role in the success of CRM implementation.

2.2.2 CRM Components

CRM has shifted significantly from the time when it was understood as a cycle of people, process and technology implemented to recognise the customers better (Chen and Popovich, 2003; Christopher et al., 2003). The foundation of CRM still lies in these three core elements, studies there are other essential components too. For an instance, a study found an organisational culture to be one of the central components, for a effective CRM implementation (Rahimi, 2017; Chen and Popovich, 2003; Iglesias et al., 2011). Implementing a CRM strategy certainly involves a change in the organisation culture towards sharing information and knowledge more freely; however, effective communication throughout regarding the tasks and people involved can definitely help to ease the change. A study has also indicated that along with internal components, CRM success requires careful consideration of changing business environment (Finnegan and Willcocks, 2007). Payen and Frow (2005) asserted the importance of change management towards CRM success. Overall, the integration and alignment of organisational functional process is centre to CRM success.

A survey cited by Rigby (2004) identified that 87% of CRM programs are unsuccessful due to the lack of adequate change management within the organisation. Regarding the reasons for CRM failure, Rigby et al. (2002) also stated that one in five executives completely discard CRM implementation when they attribute CRM to be responsible for driving away valuable customers instead of strengthening the firms' relationship with them. This issue was also identified by AMR Research (as discussed in Payne and Frow, 2011), which found that 20% of CRM initiatives damage customer relationships. Some reasons for why firms abandon CRM implementation are identified by Mckim (2002) and Kale (2003), and these include the lack of readiness; inability to precisely specify the business problem to be addressed; lack of a collective definition of CRM; absence of fitting measurement; and failure of customer communication and so on. Later on researchers like (King and Burgess, 2007)

emphasised firms' failure to focus on the human and social sides of both the employees and customers as key reason CRM strategy failure.

Companies often fail to understand the importance of this approach and to accept that it is important to integrate people, processes and technology in CRM implementation (Boulding et al., 2005). Likewise, an effective implementation is inarticulate to most companies, mainly as they fail to accept that CRM entails a company-wide, cross-functional and customer-focused business process re-engineering (Chen and Popovich, 2003). Other than these factors, CRM demands efficient leadership, sourcing, targeting and evaluation strategies if its implementation is to be successful (Bull, 2003).

Overall, CRM is a compound strategy that sources customer data from all the possible customer touchpoints, thus forming a distinct yet inclusive view of a customer while creating key customer profiles by analysing their purchase behaviour and consumption patterns. Technology aids in the tracking, monitoring and analysis of these behaviours and allows companies to classify their existing customers and new prospects. They can then concentrate their marketing efforts and narrow down business strategies accordingly. Retention is possible only if the firms understand their existing customer, while also understanding the patterns of customers' behaviours helps them to attract prospective customers.

2.2.3 Types of CRM

If seen from the strategic perspective of customer relationships, technology is essentially an enabler. Together with people and process, the use of technology echoes the firm's aims of building, developing and retaining customer relationships. It is imperative for both management and staff to realise how these factors interlink with each other and result in relationship after-effects. Whatever type of CRM system is implemented, these components need to complement each other.

Several studies have discussed and presented the different types of CRM. In their individual studies, Reynolds (2002), Minna and Aino (2005) and Dyche (2002) have highlighted three types of CRM that include operational, analytical and collaborative CRM. Later on, Buttle (2009) introduced strategic CRM as the fourth type of CRM.

The section below briefly discusses the different types of CRM. These will help readers to understand how companies implement CRM based on their objectives:

- a. Operational CRM: Used to capture customer data from wherever their touch points occur. Dyche (2002, p. 13) also called operational CRM a “front office CRM”. Touch points include telephone calls, websites, emails, store sales, and so on, from which customer data can be collected. This type of CRM involves recording and storing these collected data. Customer touchpoints for the MNO industry would include telephone calls, promotional emails, in-app push notifications, promotional texts, retail stores, interactive advertisements about new products, websites, and so on. Buttle (2009) also stated that sales force automation is the perfect example of operational CRM.
- b. Analytical CRM: As suggested by the name, analytical CRM seeks to understand the activities and behaviours of customers through their data. Technology plays a huge role in this kind of CRM. These CRM systems involve the acquisition and transformation of customer data into useful knowledge and use those knowledge towards selling more goods or services or towards doing it more efficiently. Data and analytics are part of knowledge management. According to Buttle (2009), analytical CRM involves data mining and data intelligence, both of which will be discussed in relation to knowledge management in a separate section below.
- c. Collaborative CRM: As an enabling interface for communication between customers, enterprise and its employees, as stated by Payne and Frow (2009), a collaborative CRM brings together different departments. These systems administer and incorporate communication channels and customer interaction touch points.
- d. Strategic CRM: A relatively newer concept, strategic CRM works more closely towards developing a customer-centric culture in a firm. According to Buttle (2009), it aims to attain and hold the most profitable customers and create long term shareholder value throughout the customer lifetime. Through the analysis, business will invest in resources to create and deliver better customer value than its competitors.

The value of data collected through CRM systems depends on how they are converted into insightful knowledge. The next section explains the process of creating and

transforming data into knowledge as customer knowledge is the actual asset in CRM, and its efficient management is what offers competitive advantage to the firm (Khodakarami and Chan, 2014).

2.3 CRM, Knowledge Management and Customer Knowledge Management

By nature, the relationship marketing process includes communication, which leads to the creation of knowledge (Rowley, 2004). Likewise, the data collected do not serve as information itself until they are studied and analysed, which is possible through techniques like data mining. The actual essence of CRM implementation lies in the application of customer knowledge that is generated from data collected from several customer touch points. The use of customer-related knowledge is a core means of achieving CRM's objectives. As stated by Gebert and fellow researchers (2003), CRM manages knowledge for, from and about customers. Despite this realisation; namely, that this knowledge is where the success of CRM lies, it has received the least amount of attention from academics and researchers. This is surprising given the fact that knowledge has been labelled by Drucker (1999, 2003) as one of the main assets of organisations, while Crie and Micheaux (2006) identified it as source of better customer value, a key driver of organisational performance (Riege, 2007) and as providing the ultimate competitive advantage.

The concepts and foundation of CRM and KM are embedded. People, process and technology, which are often referred to as components of CRM, are also three of the four components of KM; the fourth component of KM is knowledge itself (Desouza and Paquette, 2011). Despite the fact that both approaches emphasise allocating resources to related business processes in order to achieve competitive advantages, CRM and KM are explored in isolation and are treated as separate disciplines even by researchers, which is what often leads firms to fail in producing and delivering augmented customer value (Boulding et al., 2005; Chen and Li, 2006).

Researchers' insights on necessity of concept integration led to develop customer knowledge management (CKM), which is referred to as a medium by which to integrate customer relationship management and knowledge management (Gibbert et al., 2002). Overall, CKM is about procuring, distributing and magnifying the knowledge

that exists within customers for the mutual advantage of both customers and businesses; as such, CKM might seem like a synonym for customer relationship management (CRM) or knowledge management (KM). Overall, CKM intensifies the role of customers by shifting them from being mere passive receptors of products and services to being powerful knowledge partners (Paquette, 2006). The table below indicates how CRM, KM and CKM differ from one another.

	KM	CRM	CKM
Knowledge sought in	Employee, team, company, network of companies.	Customer Database.	Customer experience, creativity, and (dis)satisfaction with products/ services.
Axioms	'If only we knew what we know.'	'Retention is cheaper than acquisition.'	'If only we knew what our customers know.'
Rationale	Unlock and integrate employees' knowledge about customers, sales processes, and R&D.	Mining knowledge about the customer in company's databases.	Gaining knowledge directly from the customer, as well as sharing and expanding this knowledge.
Objectives	Efficiency gains, cost saving, and avoidance of re-inventing the wheel.	Customer base nurturing, maintaining company's customer base.	Collaboration with customers for joint value creation.
Metrics	Performance against budget.	Performance in terms of customer satisfaction and loyalty.	Performance against competitors in innovation and growth, contribution to customer success.
Benefits	Customer satisfaction.	Customer retention.	Customer success, innovation, organizational learning.
Recipient of Incentives	Employee.	Customer.	Customer.
Role of customer	Passive, recipient of product.	Captive, tied to product/ service by loyalty schemes.	Active, partner in value-creation process.
Corporate role	Encourage employees to share their knowledge with their colleagues.	Build lasting relationships with customers	Emancipate customers from passive recipients of products to active co-creators of value.

Table 2.4 CKM versus KM & CRM (adapted from Gibbert et al., 2002, p. 461)

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that profitability is not defined by numbers or rate of customer retention. CKM, therefore, focuses on generating business growth through the acquisition of new customers and by winning them via an active and value-creating interaction with them, unlike KM and CRM in isolation.

Among the several definitions and classifications of customer knowledge, the classification by Gibbert et al. (2002) has been most popular amongst scholars. It includes knowledge for customers, knowledge about customers and knowledge from customers. Customer knowledge has been similarly categorised by researchers

including Bueren et al. (2005); however, Crie and Micheaux (2006) later came up with two types of customer knowledge; namely, behavioural (or quantitative) and attitudinal (or qualitative) customer knowledge.

Knowledge for customers refers to knowledge that is created by organisations with the intention of supporting their customers and helping them to know their products or services better (Gibbert et al., 2002). Knowledge about customers refers to acquired knowledge, including firms' understanding of their customers' backgrounds, desires and product preferences (Chen and Su, 2006). These are the insights gained by organisations through historical purchase data and customers' movements and interactions in various channels and touchpoints. Knowledge from customers refers to the amount of knowledge that inhabits within the customers. It comprises information about firms' products and services (Gibbert et al., 2002), the margin of improvements, substitute/ competitors' products and services and customers' ideal means of communication. It also includes suggestions, feedback and reviews, which also give firms indications regarding how to segment their market more effectively and how to develop better customer, marketing and overall business strategies.

These classifications reflect how the roots of customer knowledge, KM and CRM are interconnected and how their integration helps firms to achieve their organisational objectives. Several studies have been undertaken (Bose and Sugumaran, 2003; Bueren et al., 2005; Campbell, 2003; Gibbert et al., 2002) to establish and examine the relationship and association between knowledge management (KM) and customer relationship management (CRM). However, none of them are broad and inclusive enough to combine all of the dynamics into one single framework. The lack of such an integrated platform prevents firms from achieving 100 percent, even though they have vast amounts of data and information about their potential and existing customers.

2.3.1 From data to knowledge - the technological perspective

Data and information are often interchangeably used and understood. By using the raw data gathered from random touch points, businesses can identify their prospects, valued customers and forecast the potential behaviours; this enables firms to make practical, knowledge-driven judgements and formulate the strategies accordingly. Enabled by global technological advancement, there are several information systems

and processes available in market today that are used by firms to organise and manage data. It is vital to appreciate that the overall journey of data to the knowledge lies in two major concepts; data mining and data warehouse. Let's briefly discuss these concepts.

Data Warehouse

In order to become functional, CRM requires data to be collected from each transaction and every customer activity; the analysis of such data enhances total business processes. Data Warehouse as defined by (Chen and Popovich, 2003) is the repository of overall customer data that includes customer profile, transactional data, operational data and so on. It not only combines data from several fragmented functional databases within the company; it also constantly extracts information about customers, thus eliminating the necessity for conventional marketing research instruments, like customer surveys and focus groups. Researchers claim that data warehouse is the enabler of CRM as it combines, correlates and converts raw customer data collected from heterogeneous sources into customer intelligence and knowledge that offers a deeper understanding of customer behaviour (Chen and Popovich, 2003).

Data Mining

Data mining (DM) originated with the storage of data on computers and continued with data access and improvements; now, there are technologies that permit users to pilot through real-time data. The whole transformation process is all about extracting unseen predictive information from large databases and this particular process is known as data mining (Agrawal et al., 1993; Chen, Han and Yu, 1996; Chen and LI, 2006). Data mining, which is an imperative part of the overall CRM process, consists of interactions with the stored data (data warehouse) on the one hand and communication with campaign management software on the other.

Data mining usually involves the use of techniques such as predictive modelling, forecasting and descriptive modelling techniques through which an organisation can manage and retain customers, select the right prospects, segment customers more accurately and define pricing and other strategies accordingly. Put simply, data mining helps companies to aggregate information from large-scale client/server applications, better understand customers' needs by analysing their historic purchase patterns and

support decision making (Lee and Siau, 2001). Overall, data mining aids knowledge management in two ways: firstly, to establish the context of business intelligence obtained from the data miner, and, secondly, to discover customers' buying behaviour and patterns from the sales databases in order to increase human knowledge (Wang and Wang, 2008).

2.4 Relationship Instruments

As discussed above, RM and CRM are focused on the concept of the buyer–seller exchange relationship, which is based on firms developing their marketing, selling and overall business strategies with the aim of maintaining and boosting their relationship with their buyers. After determining these strategies, the factors and activities that influence the buyer–seller exchange relationship must be considered. Some activities that influence customers include sales tactics, media advertisements, direct mail, internet advertisements, bonus and loyalty schemes and so on (Yi and Jeon, 2003) that has also developed to e-marketing and social media influencer marketing today.

Several elements have been acknowledged that help to form a relationship; these include trust, commitment, satisfaction, uncertainty, dependence, fairness and symmetry (for example, Smith et al., 1999; Britton and Rose, 2004). Similarly, several frameworks have been developed to identify the factors that influence relationships and RM. One of these is the Relationship Marketing Tactics (RMT) framework by Peng and Wang (2006); which builds on the concept originally used by De Wulf and Lacobucci (2001). This framework has been introduced in this research as understanding of these elements helps researchers to ascertain an idea of how customers build their perceptions of a brand or a firm. This framework incorporates pricing offers, product and service quality, marketing communications, customisation (Nguyen, 2009) and reputation (for example De Wulf et al., 2001; Verhoef, 2003; Peng and Wang, 2006) which are the components behind establishing a relationship between a customer and a firm (Peng and Wang, 2006).

Researchers have used the term 'instrument' to describe these elements that support maintaining and reinforcing the firm-customer relationships. They are also the dynamics that firms implement to influence their existing customers and prospects.

The same idea is typically described using the term 'tactics' by most researchers, and it was also referred to using the term 'CRM offerings' by Nguyen (2009) in his research.

Despite the lack of an universal definition of CRM yet, there are some vital concepts, such as one-to-one marketing, the learning relationship, value co-creation, customer knowledge, trust and satisfaction, customer retention, and so on, that every definition incorporates—and these actually shape CRM and its objectives. These are also the elements that help the researcher to understand how a fair CRM practice can turn into a darker practice. Understanding those concepts and instruments is therefore vital, and they are briefly introduced below.

a. One-to-one Marketing

One-to-one marketing describes firms' tailored communications with their customers that are engaged in with a belief that such individual interactions promote customer loyalty and improve return on investment (ROI). In his work, Renner (2000) mentioned how important it is to understand each customer to optimise customer relationships, be they profitable or non-profitable; and, based on these understandings, business processes are re-organised in order to behave with customers exclusively based on their individual wants and perceived values.

In the case of one-to-one marketing and based on the relationship that they have and the information they exchange with firms, customers anticipate firms to calculate their needs and to deliver a service beyond their expectations as a result. If this happens then the result is customer loyalty. However, comparison enabled by visibility through social media, one-one treatment is also one of the factors that raises concern of unfairness through differential treatment. Practitioners therefore need to be very careful when implementing customised offers. Based on Frow et. al (2011) it is observed that customer often compare the prices and offers with what other customers are receiving; and any unequal treatment will lead them to perceive unfairness which may impact their existing relationship with the service provider.

b. Learning Relationship

CRM is based on the notion of building a learning relationship with each individual customer (Peppers et al., 1999; Galitsky and De la Rosa, 2011), and learning

relationship refers to the communications between a firm and its customers that the firm takes part in for mutual gain (Peppers and Rogers, 2010). The overall give-and-take of such collective interactions aims to achieve a win-win situation (Nguyen, 2009). When considering the time and effort required, firms believe that such a learning relationship increases the switching costs that customers experience, thus ultimately increasing their likelihood of staying with their current firm rather than switching to a competitor. A learning relationship is thus believed to increase customer value and customer loyalty (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2000; Yi and Jeon, 2003).

c. Value Co-creation

Firstly, as suggested by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004), it is significant for the firms to understand that value is not created for consumers but is rather co-created with consumers. Likewise, consumers are also capable of creating value for themselves as well as that for others as defined by Vargo and Lusch (2004). 'Others' refers to existing customers, potential customers and for the firm itself. Therefore, a well-developed business strategy acknowledges the fact that value is no longer created by the firm alone, but that it thrives in partnership with its resourceful consumers; especially when consumers are enthusiastic about being a part of the value chain (Friedman, 2006; Tapscott and Williams, 2006). Although value co-creation is viewed as being the apex of customer-centric marketing and is central to Payne and Frow's conceptual framework (2005), the concept is completely embedded with customer knowledge; thus, data collected via customer interaction and overall touchpoints is imperative. On one hand, researchers are realising consumer involvement and collaboration in value co-creation while on the other hand, some researchers studied consumer involvement in value co-creation as as being treated as an unpaid labour, as consumer exploitation, customers as commodities and so on (Cova, Dalli and Zwick, 2011; Zwick and Denegri Knott, 2009).

d. Trust and Satisfaction

Trust, as a concept, has been linked and reviewed in several disciplines. In the marketing and business management field, it refers to the "degree of confidence or certainty the [...] [customer] has in [...] exchange options" (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2000, p.327).

When it comes to relationship marketing, customers' trust and confidence in the chosen service provider is the key. Likewise, customer satisfaction is another element that is followed by the customer's decision to be loyal to the chosen service provider; however, that decision is prominently defined by the firm's service quality. The ability to manage customer relationships effectively and efficiently results in increased customer satisfaction and overall retention proportions (Reichheld, 1996). In their study, Chen and Popovich (2003) added that companies who successfully implement CRM will secure rewards, in terms of customer loyalty, that lead to long term profitability. The positive relationship between trust and loyalty was also identified by Verhoef (2003).

e. Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention

CRM revolves around the idea that fostering long-term relationships with existing customers is the best way to create customer loyalty (Reichheld and Scheffer, 2000); thus, companies ultimately aim to retain customers for as long as possible.

f. Customer Knowledge

The principal notion of CRM is that firms build customer knowledge for reasons including, but not limited to, effectively segmenting their customers and prospects, building and continuing relationships with profitable customer segment, defining effective ways to handle less profitable customers and tailoring offerings and promotional efforts (Srivastava, Shervani and Fahey, 1998). Superior customer knowledge, if utilised correctly, results in improved customer relationships and increased loyalty over time.

g. Service Quality

Parasuraman and his fellow researchers described service quality as the difference between expectations and their perceptions of service (Parasuraman, Zeithamal and Berry, 1991); it is often regarded as the stairway to competitive advantage. Cronin and Taylor (1992) further described service quality as customers' verdicts about service suppliers, customer interactions and the service itself. Service quality is often regarded as being one of the determinants of customer loyalty; thus, service quality has been studied in relation to CRM (Sigala, 2008).

2.5 CRM Implementation

Implementation of a CRM strategy involves a broad array of people, including front desk admins, operational experts, sales, marketing, after sales service experts, business analysts, engineers and IT professionals and a range of managers. The management must ensure that each involved department is aware of the new strategy as it incorporates a significant change in the organisation culture.

Companies invest significant amount of money in executing CRM systems (Ahearne, Hughes and Schillewaert, 2007). However, studies have highlighted the fact that these companies criticise about CRM implementations not living up to their anticipations (Rigby et al., 2002; Zablah et al., 2004). From Monster.com's CRM failure and loss of a million dollars in 1991 (Rigby, 2002) to a study in 2012 of large CRM projects that discovered that there is a 28% failure rate (Mieritz, 2012), these examples clearly illustrate the fact that CRM is not simply a technological installation.

2.5.1 What makes CRM implementation a success or a failure?

The success, failure, consequences, and antecedents of CRM implementation are a topic of interest among academics and researchers. Studies have found that "approximately 70 percent of CRM projects result in either losses or no bottom-line improvements" (Reinartz et al., 2004, p. 293). A report by The Economist also stated that 80% of CRM implementation projects fail to produce the actual goal, thus barely justifying the cost of operation (Lindergreen et al., 2006).

CRM success is defined as "an integrated and balanced approach between technology, people and processes" (Mendoza et al., 2007, p. 914). Payne and Frow have pinpointed four crucial elements for successful CRM implementation: (1) CRM readiness assessment, (2) CRM change management, (3) CRM project management, and (4) employee engagement. Researchers also have various opinions with regard to the failure of CRM systems. Day believes that the lack of strategic groundwork before implementing of CRM leads to CRM system failure, while Maseli (2001) identifies reasons for failure that include a lack of organisational collaboration and customer focus (Foss et al., 2008; Day, 2000). Jain and his fellow researchers also identified that the poor design, development, and measurement of CRM projects lie

behind CRM failure, while many other researchers believe that CRM disasters are largely induced by the firms' lack of resources to incorporate CRM technologies to their functional processes (Jain, Jain and Dhar, 2007; Speier and Venkatesh, 2002; Foss et al., 2008). Interestingly, post implementation, firms and employees do not seem to understand what CRM actually means or what the purpose of its execution, which comes with gigantic investment, actually is (Rigby et al., 2002); this commonly results in CRM implementation failure (Bolton and Tarasi, 2006).

Furthermore, there are cases where CRM implementation fails as a result of technology misfit (Willcocks and Finnegan, 2007); however, researchers have argued that the difficulties associated with CRM implementation are not mostly technical (Willcocks and Finnegan, 2007).

Nguyen also highlighted the fact that CRM implementation failure was "... mostly due to lack of knowledge and research, lack of project management skills, lack of commitment from the executive management, etc. To avoid wasting money and time, organizations before implementing CRM system should be aware of the difficulties, traps, and mistakes that can lead to failure" (Nguyen et al., 2007, p. 113). Due to the lack of effort from higher level management in providing adequate knowledge about what the CRM initiative constitutes, what processes are involved and what changes can be expected, employees commonly regard overall CRM initiative as mere departmental obligations ultimately leading to failure.

2.5.2 Benefits of CRM implementation

The benefits or purposes of implementing CRM basically revolve around ensuring profitability through the management of customers, and it is combined with a belief that "it is hard to find new customers, but it is just as difficult to keep existing ones" (Nguyen et al., 2007, p. 103). According to Swift (2001), the benefits of implementing CRM are generally found in one of the following areas:

Benefits of implementing CRM	Lower cost of recruiting customers
	Higher customer profitability
	Increased customer retention and loyalty
	Reduced cost of sales
	Integration of the whole organisation
	Superior customer service (Nguyen et al., 2007)
	Evaluation of customers' profitability
	Superior information management (Nguyen et al., 2007)
	Rapid response to customer needs (Anderson, 2006)

Table 2. 5 Benefits of implementing CRM, adapted from (Swift, 2001)

After being tempted by all these potential benefits, firms tend to make use of their marketing energies and put their focus on customers who they assume will generate more profit over their customer lifetime (Rust and Bhalla, 2010; Kumar et al., 2010). This is when firms tend to misuse the CRM system, as the system not only records and produces reports but produces critical information. The exploitation or inappropriate use of CRM has been discussed by few researchers in the past. They highlight the fact that such actions might result in perceptions of unfairness, that makes buyers opt-out of relationships, spread negative word of mouth about product/ services or the brand as a whole, or participate in behaviours that might harm the firm (Campbell, 2007; Xia et al., 2004; Grégoire and Fisher, 2008). Despite the fact that such detrimental consequences may arise, unfairness in CRM practices has been very much ignored; however, most recently those practices have been discussed as the dark side of CRM by some scholars (Frow et al., 2011; Nguyen, 2012). The emergence of dark sides and their consequences will be discussed in an upcoming section of this chapter.

2.6 CRM implementation and related theories

The degree of an organisations' success in today's aggressive business world is significantly determined by its ability to competently and encouragingly administer its

relationships both internally and externally (Berry, 1983). This is the reason why firms, and especially service firms, implement CRM tools and software. Implementation can only guarantee success if there is real cross-functional integration of people, operation, process and marketing proficiency supported by technological advancements and applications (Abdullateef and Nyadzayo, 2018; Payne and Frow, 2013; Richard and Jones, 2008). Most of the definitions discussed in the previous section highlighted terms such as 'cross-functional', 'customer-driven' and 'technology-integrated'. Process integration itself, however, has been considered as being the most challenging aspect of the competitive business environment (Giachetti, 2004).

Several theories have been linked to CRM implementation and its success. For an instance, change management theory plays a huge role in CRM and its implementation, viewing CRM implementation as technology enabled cultural change (Willcocks and Finnegan, 2007).

The researcher has introduced two CRM theories below that shed light on the implementation process of a CRM strategy. Unfortunately, no prior studies have focused on the CRM process in relation to service providers' behavioural intentions. There is a necessity to provide realistic evidence regarding what makes service providers practice dark CRM activities, if they practice any deliberately. Future studies therefore need to investigate the CRM implementation process and identify at what point service providers divert towards practicing latent behaviours.

2.6.1 The IDIC Model of Customer Relationship Management

Based on the relationship instruments one-one marketing and relationship explained above, this model, or framework of CRM, was developed by Peppers and Rogers (2010). It indicates that there is an iterative process of learning and customisation involved in managing a customer relationship. This framework frames the process of transforming an existing customer into a loyal one through establishment of one-one relation and effective engagement.

Figure 2. 3 IDIC Model of CRM, adapted from Buttle (2009)

1. Identify: The foremost step of CRM implementation is the firm's ability to understand who their prospective customers are and to construct a thorough understanding of them. A firm needs to identify its customer's needs and likings. Knowing a potential customer's desires lets the firm to produce new products and strategies focused towards customers (Azad and Ahmadi, 2015). It is equally important to let the customers know that you as a brand hear them.

2. Differentiate: Firms should separate their customers and classify the ones who hold the biggest value. Such categorisation allows better understanding of customer expectations, and according implement segment-based customer strategies. Loyal customer segment's complaints and feedbacks are often seen as valuable insights to introduce new product line or to improve the existing product and services (Srivastava and Sharma, 2013).

3. Interact: Interaction is the key in order to understand what customers actually expect from the brand they are in relationship with. This also offers an opportunity for the firms to evaluate customers' level of attachment to the brand. Effective customer communications enable firms to establish a better insight into customers' needs and preferences which is integral for a successful CRM.

4. Customise: Once customers' preferences are understood, firms are able to customise their products and services accordingly. As stated by Peppers and Rogers (2010), in order to engage a customer or a prospect in a beneficial relationship, firms need to modify some of their behaviours towards customers according to their individual needs and preferences. This is referred to as customisation. However, while implementing customization strategies, firm need to consider whether the offers are fair to rest of the customers too. Often, customised offers and differential practices raises perception of unfairness which may lead an existing relationship to fail (Nguyen et. al., 2014).

The steps outlined above are part of an ongoing process, that helps better understand customer expectations and the value that they add to the firm. The IDIC framework has been introduced to emphasise the fact that customer relationship management as a business strategy can be successful only if continuous learning is practiced. This framework serves as a guide to how initial relationship building, management and continuity can be achieved.

2.6.2 CRM Strategy Framework: The Five-process Model

For any firms to succeed in CRM and their CRM implementation strategy, it is fundamental for firms to understand and accept the fact that CRM is a cross-functional strategy. Past studies have revealed that this is where firms are falling short and losing on ROI through CRM implementation. Boulding and his fellow researchers argued that CRM "relates to strategy, managing the dual-creation or value, the intelligent use of data and technology, the acquisition of customer knowledge and the diffusion of this knowledge to the appropriate stakeholders, the development of appropriate (long-term) relationships with specific customers and/or customer groups, and the integration of processes across the many areas of the firm and across the network of firms that collaborate to generate customer value" (2005, p. 6).

Figure 2.4 CRM strategy framework: The Five-Process Model, adapted from Payne and Frow (2005, p.171; 2013, p. 30)

Boulding's definition acts as the foundation for the framework developed by Payne and Frow, which accurately illustrates the fact that CRM is comprised of cross-

functional associations between the key divisions of a firm (Payne and Frow, 2013). Prior to Payne and Frow's framework, other CRM models were identified (Winer, 2001); however, they lacked elements of cross-functionality and the incorporation of one metric or another. Let us now examine the details of the processes involved in the framework.

1. Strategy Development Process:

The implementation or introduction of any new strategy in a company should be aligned with the company's mission, vision and objective(s). The CRM implementation process incorporates the overall business strategy along with the customer management strategy. The rest of the processes in the CRM implementation model are largely shaped by the strategy development process. This process answers the following questions:

Strategy Development Process

— Who are we as a business?

— What goal(s) do we want to achieve?

— How do we achieve it/them?

2. Value Creation Process:

Value co-creation is one of the main objectives of CRM implementation and marketing as a whole. Firms' performance and success are determined by the resources implemented to create value. The value creation process answers the following questions:

Value Creation Process

— Who are our customers?

— How do we deliver value to our customers?

— How do we maximise the lifetime value of our customers?

3. Multichannel Integration Process:

The multichannel integration process is crucial, and specifically in the current era, as there are significant and multiple means by which firms can connect with customers. These include, but are not limited to, direct store sales, telephone/call centres, e-commerce, mobile commerce and, most importantly, social media. More specifically, for firms in the service industry, it is crucial for them to monitor customer touchpoints extremely closely due to the intangible nature of the service. The multichannel integration process answers the following questions:

**Multi-channel
Integration
Process**

— What are the best ways to reach our customers and how can they best reach out to us?

— What does an outstanding customer experience look like?

4. Information Management Process:

This process incorporates the collection and storing of data accumulated from several customer touchpoints and transforming them into knowledge that is used to enhance customer experience. This process, which is aided by technology, is the core objective of CRM implementation. This is because, holistically speaking, CRM aims to increase mutual value. The information management process includes the use of data, data warehouse and data mining in order to generate knowledge. It can answer the following questions:

**Information
Management
Process**

— How do we best organise customer information?

— How do we maximise value co-creation using customers' insights?

5. Performance Assessment Process:

The systematic monitoring and tracking of the general performance of a firm is crucial to ensuring that there is no diversion from the core objective(s). Likewise, this process ensures that the firm's CRM activities are being carried out and that objective(s) are being delivered as planned. The performance assessment process answers the following questions:

**Performance
Assessment
Process**

— How do we measure results and improve overall performance?

— How do we maximise shareholders' value and overall profitability?

To support the five business processes discussed above, Payne and Frow also outlined four key implementation elements. These are briefly reviewed below.

a. CRM Readiness Assessment

The first and foremost component of CRM implementation is to identify whether the company is ready to implement a CRM strategy/system. Assessment includes measuring the extent to which the company is using customer information in value co-creation and whether the company is ready to make an investment in value creation.

b. CRM Change Management

Executing an extensive CRM system comprises a huge change internally, which is critical for the initiative to be successful. The company requires changes to be made at both the individual (i.e., employee) and organisational level. Lack of attention to change management can cause the overall initiative to fail; therefore, firms are urged to implement change management strategies and frameworks such as the McKinsey 7S Framework (Waterman and Peters, 1980), Lewin's Model of Change (Lewin, 1951; Burnes and Cook, 2013) and Kotter's Change Management Model (Kotter, 2012). In adoption of change, McKinsey's 7S model has been recognised as one of the most popular and effective model that ranges from the practitioners of leadership to cybersecurity most recently. However, management need to consider the factors like degree of change, what's the expected impact to the stakeholders, how long does the change take to be into effect, and how does the change align with the objectives of the company.

c. CRM Project Management

Despite the size of CRM initiatives and management's approaches to CRM implementation, it is necessary for companies to invest in CRM project management.

Depending on the size of the companies, such as the Big Four mobile network providers, there can be several projects in place at one time.

d. Employee Engagement

Change management and project management are predominantly reliant on the quality of employees. The delivery of superior customer experiences requires better employee engagement and commitment, especially from customer-facing employees who are working with customers both physically and virtually. It is therefore important for employees to understand their responsibilities and the impact of their behaviour in order to bring about overall CRM success. This also entails the implementation of employee empowerment through training, education and continuous performance assessments.

The previous section has discussed CRM, its implementation and its benefits for firms' overall profit maximisation. Failures in any of the processes and elements of CRM implementation result in dark side practices, which can be both intentional and unintentional. Dark practices are the result of going beyond moral standards are applied in marketing decisions, behaviours and institutions. The section below reviews the literature on marketing ethics in relation to RM, CRM and the role of ethics in dark sides of CRM.

2.7 Marketing Ethics and CRM

Ethics and ethical concerns lie at the heart of marketing, and particularly relationship marketing, where there is a basic notion that the development of any human relationship and its longevity depends on the ethical stance of the involved parties (Murphy et al., 2007). Relationship marketing is primarily about developing revenues through long-term relationships with the most profitable customers over a certain period of time. Despite the notion that long-term relationships are established with moral and ethical foundations, existing studies in CRM and RM have often highlighted elements such as trust, transparency, loyalty, and so on, without openly introducing the ethical angle. It is therefore necessary to include ethics as a major element of CRM and RM.

The earliest literature review on marketing ethics was published by Murphy and Laczniak in 1981, since then, research in the field of ethics has been quite extensive; however, it has focused mostly on the social responsibility aspect rather than ethics in managerial decision making and marketing strategy implementation. For instance, misleading advertising, hiding details about products, unsafe products and the abuse of channel power are the concerns in marketing that have been identified and discussed for more than half a century and are still relevant topics of discussion. However, there has not been enough research around these areas. In addition, emerging ethical issues such as manipulation, invasion of privacy, misinformation, disinformation, etc., have also been discovered, and they are primarily associated with and facilitated by the latest advancements in technology. Some of these practices were introduced by relationship marketing scholars as 'dark sides of CRM' (Nguyen, Simkin and Canhoto, 2015). By addressing the concept identified by Nguyen, Simkin and Canhoto (2015), this research aims to elaborate on and identify the additional dark sides of CRM prevalent in the MNO industry in the UK.

Despite the evident prominence of ethical practices in marketing in relation to consumer trust, relationship building, brand loyalty, and so on, only a handful of studies have been carried out to examine the marketing mix strategy from an ethical viewpoint by addressing the ethical issues associated with each element of the marketing mix and how those issues must be addressed. The meta-analysis of journals and research in marketing ethics carried out in 2009 showed that there is an extremely disproportional amount of research undertaken in the field of ethical issues in relation to the four Ps of marketing. It was identified that the studies of ethical issues in relation to promotion, with particular attention paid to advertising ethics, are dominant, while the ethical issues related to product, price and place are ignored. The authors identified that only 25 of the more than 500 papers analysed in the study were focused on ethical issues in relation to product, price and place (Schlegelmilch and Oberseder, 2009).

Despite the popularity of studies of the ethical issues associated with promotion amongst researchers and scholars, it has also been the most criticised element of the marketing mix from an ethical viewpoint (Feenstra and Esteban, 2019; Zayer and Coleman, 2015). Several big names have been called out for their questionable

practices and penalised for disregarding the importance of ethics. It is therefore important for future researchers to not limit their research findings to academia but rather to expand the implications of such findings to practitioners.

Ethics, in general, is a moral human compass, defined as a discipline that deals with what true and false is (Shea, 1988). When it comes to marketing ethics, this incorporates how moral standards are applied in marketing decisions, behaviours and institutions. Researchers have stated that marketing ethics cover “the societal and professional standards of right and fair practices that are expected of marketing managers in their oversight of strategy formulations, implementation and control” (Laczniak and Murphy, 2006, p. 159). When any practitioner practices behaviours that are not transparent, which serve motives other than those declared and mislead customers into making a certain decision, and so on, the ethics of the practitioner – be it the brand or an individual – are questioned. This research will identify such ethically incorrect behaviours from the consumer’s point of view in the UK MNO industry.

Ethics primarily relate to personal values, while business ethics explain what corporations should or should not do. Marketing ethics is a function of business ethics, although they are often interchangeably used. When it comes to business ethics, systems come into play to decide what different functions/departments of the corporation should do and not do; however, the personal ethics of decision makers play a huge role. Business ethics is an umbrella term that includes decisions such as how you are marketing your product, how you are keeping children and minors protected if your advertising targets them, how your marketing strategies are targeting vulnerable customer segments, whether there is forced labour or any labour abuse in your supply chain, whether the raw materials and other resources used in your product(s) are sourced ethically, and so on. Peppers and Rogers stated that “failing to take a properly balanced approach not only penalizes good management practices but also undermines corporate ethics by encouraging managers to ‘steal’ from the future to fund the present” (2011, p. 309). Past studies have also shown that unethical practices, engaged in after going down an unethical path as a result of greed, directly result in the loss of sales (Weber, 2012). This is more relevant today because of increasing consumer awareness and word of mouth facilitated by the rise of the

internet and online social platforms where consumers can voice their opinions transparently. The section below further explains ethics in relation to technology and CRM tools.

2.7.1 Ethics, Technology and CRM

There is plenty of research that focusses on the ethical dilemmas and unfairness in relation to relationship marketing and CRM that are enabled by the technology involved. Although technology is not deceptive and unethical in itself, CRM tools and applications, if implemented without addressing trust and fairness issues at the strategic level, can certainly cause complications (Phan and Vogel, 2010). For example, the investment in CRM tools with the aim of achieving superior customised advertising can lead to utter failure if other elements, such as consumer privacy and fairness, are ignored. Past studies have clearly indicated the ways in which some industries including mobile phone services, banks, online retailers, credit card companies and some others have exploited and disheartened customers by intentionally forcing them into a contract, exploiting them with fees or confusing them with fine print (Frow et. al., 2011; McGovern and Moon, 2007).

Prior studies have also mentioned the implementation of the most advanced technologies for 'immoral purposes' (Nguyen et al., 2020; Cambra-Fierro et al., 2017) and the fact that consumers are more aware and analytical about businesses and their behaviour today than ever before. Facilitated by the internet and technology, consumers are more educated and proactive in expressing their complaints and opinions (Weber, 2012; Lau and Ng, 2009), which clearly impacts on sales. Furthermore, we have seen plenty of examples of how brand communities, anti-brand communities and online groups have reshaped the fate of some companies as a result of rebellions against a particular brand's unethical practices. In 2018, the Australian Competition and Consumer Commission (ACCC) cautioned Vodafone Australia about one of their adverts and use of the term 'unlimited' to promote their mobile data plans (McDonnell, 2018). Recently, a similar issue was raised in the UK, where the Advertising Standards Authority (ASA) barred some adverts for Vodafone's new 'unlimited data' mobile plans because of a lack of transparency. Their advertisement failed to display the fact that the unlimited data deal would be impacted by broadband

speed (especially on 5G). This example also highlights how companies use legal loopholes to get out of trouble: including details in the fine print or several clicks away are some of the popular practices that companies use to back up their actions.

In a similar context, the food manufacturer Heinz was fined \$2.25m in penalties for their misleading advertising (CMO, 2018). Heinz was found to be misleading the public by asserting that one of its toddler snacks was nourishing and healthy, while in reality the food contained over 60% sugar. Likewise, the supermarket giant Coles paid \$2.5m for their advertisement claiming that their bread products were 'baked today' or 'freshly baked in-store' (Christensen, 2015). Such false, misleading and deceptive statements fall under unethical promotion. Likewise, pricing strategies that take advantage of increased demand for certain products during crisis situations and raise the prices of last-minute services are some notable unethical pricing strategies.

Particularly in an online context, sellers and suppliers are now aware of the significance of word of mouth and how customer reviews impact on buying decisions. Research has shown that people often hesitate to buy products if they do not see reviews about them. This has forced sellers to ensure that their listed products are reviewed by consumers, which is not something that happens overnight. Therefore, some suppliers have been tempted to write or commission fake reviews, which is another unethical activity reflective of 'deception' and a well-known dark side activity in CRM. Such alteration of information content has been established as one of the deceptive tactics in CRM by Ngoala (2015) and particularly in a digital interface where it is relatively easy to manipulate information in real time.

These behaviours have been studied in terms of how such unethical marketing practices tend to damage customer relationships and how they negatively impact new customers, who do not wish to be associated with the brand or the product. These behaviours have been studied as the dark sides of CRM.

2.8 The Dark Sides of CRM

The foremost aim of this study is to examine how MNO's CRM activities are failing to address ethical aspects in relation to relationship management and CRM activities that's being practiced by the mobile service providers / MNO industry in the UK and

identify the level of awareness that service users have with regard to this issue. Bull and Adam (2011) argued that the notion of mainstream CRM and its implementation is grounded on a confined theory that fails to address the ethical issues properly. This matter has been further studied by Nguyen and Mutum (2012): in their research, they highlighted the fact that CRM systems and advancements have, more recently, tended to deplete customers' faith and to ignore aspects such as fairness and trust. They also made the argument that firms have been failing to realise the ethical considerations toward service users.

Nguyen (2012) highlighted some of the underlying causes of the dark sides of CRM. He stated that customers perceived themselves as being oppressed by firms' biased CRM systems and practices. Customers' realisation of being in an unfair situation certainly poses a risk to firms in terms of failure in the long term. Klaus and Nguyen (2013) further explored customers' perceptions in the retail sector specifically and identified that pricing was a factor of the perception of unfairness. Additionally, researchers have acknowledged that customisation and personalisation are also factors associated with perceptions of unfairness. Payne and Frow (2011), when examining the Australian mobile market, underlined the fact that data collection and usage are further elements associated with perceptions of unfairness. All these findings suggest that there are many factors that might make service users feel unfairly treated in terms of how service providers implement their marketing tactics.

Although the foundation of CRM implementation lies in identifying individuals' needs and fulfilling them accordingly, there is a paradox in the area of individualised offers and how these can make consumers feel prejudiced against and unfairly treated. Perception is a subjective sense of judgement; therefore, customisation and personalisation strategies, when used in the individual treatment of customers, may trigger favouritism (Nguyen and Simkin, 2009). In addition to customer's perceptions of fairness and unfairness, Nguyen and Simkin also conducted a separate study to explore advantaged and disadvantaged customers (Nguyen and Simkin, 2013).

Additionally, trust and transparency are other issues that have caused customers to raise their eyebrows in relation to CRM schemes and marketers' RM tactics. The emphasis of today's CRM systems is on creating an interactive relationship with

consumers through communication and interaction, so that a firm can discover more and more about its customers' individual requirements. Interaction is just another method by which to engender more data, which eventually turns into knowledge that is implemented to tailor products/services that meet the individual's needs on a one-to-one basis. A firm's differential marketing strategy is based on such one-to-one relationship learning.

Interactive relationships are aided by other CRM and RM strategies that are implemented by firms. The popular customer tool towards interactive relationship includes bonus campaigns, loyalty schemes, dynamic pricing techniques, offers and deals, social media, brand communities and internet blogging/vlogging (Greenberg, 2009; Kaplan, 2015; Peppers and Rogers, 2011). Interactive relationship eventually leads to long term buyer–seller relationship as it eventually adds on trust and reliability on each other.

All these techniques, as effective as they are in creating relationships, carry equal risks of backfiring within the relationship. Despite having realised the significance of fairness as a subject matter in CRM (Nguyen and Mutum, 2012), only a handful of issues have been highlighted to date and they include customer tracking systems, information misuses, unfairness in individual customisation, favouritism of profitable customers, dynamic pricing, hidden fees and surcharges, and so on (Xia et al., 2004; Boulding et al., 2005; Nguyen, 2011). Some other issues have been identified as being neglected issues of CRM rather than its darker sides; these mostly cover ethical aspects.

One of the prominent ideologies in CRM implementation is the development and management of customer relations through targeting tactics. Such targeting approach is based on the notion that individual customers hold dissimilar value and expectations. Based on their nature, customers are divided into transactional and relational customers. As suggested by the name, transactional customers hold low potential to be loyal as they are primarily driven by low cost and they may switch to any other competitors as the switching cost is low, while relational customers are characterised as those with the potential for sustained loyalty (Chan et al., 2014).

Therefore, a firm's ability to identify these types of customers is key, and developing strategies and targeting them based on their motives is crucial.

Studies have shown how dark behaviours are practiced in several industries, including retailing and FMCG, and in the next section we will briefly look into their relevance in the MNO industry. Overall, firms think that a confused or an ill-informed customer can end up making a poor purchasing decision, thereby yielding a higher profit to the firm. As a result of their greed, firms deliberately make terms and conditions and buying policies too complex for a layman to understand. In order to discourage such practices, it is absolutely vital to know whether customers are aware of such concealed practices, whether intentional or unintentional, and to identify what kinds of behaviours they perceive as being hidden and unfair. A later section describes service users' perceptions of fairness and the currently identified dark sides of CRM in detail.

2.8.1 Social CRM and dark sides

Customer relationship management has been on a journey that has evolved from traditional CRM to e-CRM and now to social CRM. The researcher is briefly introducing social CRM and where it is headed for two reasons. Firstly, the data collection for this research is based on MNOs' social media platforms and secondly, past studies of the dark sides of CRM have shown that businesses' inability to manage their social media presence and failure to align their social media objectives with their broader CRM strategies has led to some dark sides of CRM. The information generated through customer engagement on social media has been proven to be vital.

The mammoth amount of data offered by social media platforms enables brands and companies to develop insights about their customers and make favourable strategic decisions guided by those insights. Similarly, businesses are provided with an opportunity to make marketing decisions based on evidence rather than perceptions.

Thanks to the rise in internet, social media and technology development, today's customers are more informed than ever and also demand maximum transparency and interactivity from the businesses they deal or partner with. They also hold a stronger position when compared to their business counterparts in the sense that the

information and experiences shared by fellow customers are valued much more than the information shared by the businesses themselves. Creating a platform for customers' shared experiences is one reason why businesses are inclined to maintain a social media presence nowadays. Collaborative experiences and value-driven conversations are two elements of today's relationship management practice. The addition of social media tools and technologies to businesses' CRM strategies has therefore been referred to as social CRM.

Rapp and Ogilvie (2016) conducted a research work on CRM in relation to social media, which provides a critical viewpoint on the evolution of CRM brought about by the development of social media tools and the relationship development that is possible through social interactivity. While conceptualising social CRM, they also identified how traditional forms of CRM are different to social CRM and how crucial it is for businesses to acknowledge these differences and adapt accordingly to avoid failure. Businesses have seen the opportunities that social media has created today; however, the incorporation of social media tools requires social strategies that fit within businesses' CRM strategies as well as the broader marketing mix of the firms. Businesses are implementing social CRM with traditional CRM strategies, which is what leads to failure. Rapp and Ogilvie's work outlines how businesses are failing to adapt to the latest technologies and updates, how they are practicing customer engagement without concrete benefits, how they are mishandling and misusing communications and how they are basically considering social media as a 'one-way street'.

2.8.2 Justification of the use of the term 'dark sides'

As mentioned in the section above, in the past few years, academics have shifted their focus towards researching the dark side of CRM (Grandinetti, 2017); however, despite the increase in the number of studies, there is very limited theoretical and empirical evidence regarding its drivers and consequences. The area of CRM's dark side oddly lacks a broader review (Nguyen et al., 2015), which is probably due to the complexity of the subject, given that CRM's dark side literature ranges across an extensive set of areas including information systems, service marketing, organisation behaviour, psychology, sociology and economics. Furthermore, the available literature also

reflects the vagueness and inter-relativity of the taxonomy associated with the dark sides of CRM. Therefore, it is vital for future research to explore and establish the terminologies associated with the dark sides of CRM.

In one of the most recent research papers published by Nguyen et al., in which they reviewed the development of knowledge in the area of the dark sides of CRM over the years, they mentioned that concerns about the dark sides of CRM are “at worst ignored and at best considered as an inconvenient afterthought” (Nguyen et., al., 2020, p.2). Therefore, this research is an attempt to contribute to the body of knowledge on the dark sides of CRM by providing a crucial viewpoint on why awareness of these dark practices is important and why broader research across various industries is required.

We are currently in the most technologically advanced state of society, which is a fact that highlights the timeliness of this research work. Although there are many positives associated with CRM and the use of technologically advanced tools, they have also led to businesses misusing technology by ripping off customers by misusing their data, customising offers by invading their customers’ privacy, and so on. Along with such developments, information about such misuses and forms of exploitation is spreading amongst customers too, which is facilitated by the rise of the internet, technology and social media platforms and takes the form of word of mouth. A further example of the power of social media platforms and their usage is that of people taking a stand against unruly stakeholders, including customers, businesses and also policymakers (Abdelhadi, Foster and Whysall, 2014) and holding them accountable for their actions. Journalists have also criticised businesses for not questioning, and merely reacting, to the dark side of CRM (Wong, 2018a; McGoogan, 2017).

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) policy introduced by the UK and the EU is a prime example of an effort being made to ensure customer data protection and privacy management. Consumers’ awareness of the misuse of their data and privacy, combined with constant communication about the need to address such misuse and exploitation of data, is what led policy makers to act upon it and introduce the GDPR policy. This example suggests that it is crucial for practitioners to understand and consider consumers’ perceptions of the activities carried out by service providers. This study therefore aims to look into the perceptions of service

users with regard to several immoral and unspecified activities that are being practiced by service providers in the name of CRM. However, despite having policies in place and charging hefty fines for any sort of violation, some companies are still found to be ignoring the policies and practising data breach and misuse beyond service user's consent of use. For example, EE Limited was fined £100,000 for sending over 2.5 million direct marketing messages to its customers without their consent (ICO, 2019). Such penalties are not only levied to punish wrong doers but also to warn any companies who may be contemplating engaging in such actions in the future practitioners.

In one of the earliest studies of whether ethics in marketing is a utilitarian approach, Bull and Adam suggested that if the satisfaction of consumers is the actual objective of marketing, and if practitioners are focused on long-term consequences, then an ethical approach is key in marketing. Despite the issue being flagged up and argued about on several occasions by scholars, the element of ethics, which is a decisive factor in building trust in a relationship, has been critically ignored by CRM practitioners even today (Bull and Adam, 2011). In their study, Bull and Adam incorporated the concept of virtue ethics into CRM and projected that organisations could drastically gain success by implementing an alternative approach for CRM based on ideas adapted from MacIntyre's virtue ethics; however, not much development has been illustrated in recent studies of virtue ethics and its incorporation in CRM.

2.8.3 From Use to Misuse— the Rise of the Dark Sides

There was a time when firms were not able to capitalise on the benefits of CRM due to many reasons, that ranged from employee's failure to adopt the change to lack of understanding on what CRM actually means. Things are gradually changing as the practitioners are understanding the significance of CRM implementation, resulting increased customer loyalty, increased firm's ability to providing better customer service and experiences based on customers' previous purchase pattern, superior capacity to gather data and knowledge creation and so on. However, when these gains turn into greed, firms are inclined towards misusing the system. Service providers who practice such customer management activities, which can harm customer

relationships and lead to firms exploiting customers, have been conceptualised as engaging in the dark side of customer management: this includes RM and CRM (Nguyen, 2015). Several examples of this have been seen in the last decade; from Amazon's dynamic pricing to Ryanair's price unfairness. Awareness of these events outraged customers when they came to know how the brands were milking from their customer's trust, however it somehow alerted consumers towards firm's hidden practices.

The study of 'dark side behaviours' is not a new concept in academia, as it has been researched and conceptualised several times since the last few decades (Baranik et al., 2017; Linstead et al., 2014; Vaughan, 1999); especially in the field of management and organisational behaviour. Some of the studies relating to the dark sides of CRM include disciplines such as leadership (Judge et al., 2009; Tourish, 2013), international business (Batra, 2007), organisational behaviour innovation (Zibarras, Port and Woods, 2008), management decisions (Crane, 2013; Boddy et al., 2010) and organisation (Vaughan, 199; Linstead et al., 2014). Most recently, Daunt and Greer (2017) explored the growing deviant and dishonest marketing practices as dark sides of marketing.

Firms bizarrely concentrate on quantitative transactions over development and the maintenance of relationships, regardless of them claiming to implement relationship strategies. They seem to practice dark side behaviours that Sheth and Sisodia (2006, p. 3) describe as: *"Instead of acting as partners engaged in mutually rewarding co-destiny relationships, too many marketers and consumers continue to be locked into mistrustful, adversarial relationships in which there is a constant tug-of-war to determine which side can benefit disproportionately and unfairly"*.

2.8.4 What dark sides have been identified this far?

Dark sides and ethical issues have been long discussed and identified with regard to CRM implementation; however, very limited exploration has been done in this area. Customer trust and privacy (Deighton, 2005; Bart et al., 2005), customer fairness, differential treatment (Feinberg, Krishna and Zhang, 2002; Srinivasan and Moorman, 2005; Reitz, 2005) and information misuse are only some of the acknowledged

examples. In addition to the very limited number of studies that have been carried out, there is inadequate methodical evidence in terms of the impact of such behaviours on service users; these are behaviours that encourage service providers to remain ignorant and to continue practicing such latent behaviours. Therefore, this study steps forward into this research gap to explore this unmapped zone of relationship marketing, CRM and customer management as a whole.

Price-based Unfairness

In today's market, differential pricing based on customer segment is normal. When businesses implement differential pricing, they favour some customers at the cost of others, which creates perceptions of unfairness in the non-targeted section (Boulding et al., 2005; Nguyen and Simkin, 2013). Heath and Heath (2008) also addressed this issue and identified that it comprises deceptive marketing schemes that induce adverse attitudes between consumers.

Prior studies have identified the fact that discrimination is broadly prevalent in service industries where the service providers charge a different prices to certain customer segment for fundamentally the same quality service, to balance demand and maximise revenues (McMahon-Beattie, 2011; Wang, 2011). Feinberg et al. (2002) argued that the sense of someone else receiving a better deal for the same service evokes discontent and might make a loyal consumer revolt. Knowledge of a fellow service user paying a different price for the same service has been described as a strong source of perceptions of unfairness (Haws and Bearden, 2006). Such a practice has also been described as CRM-based pricing, which refers to customised pricing based on the knowledge gained from CRM as a result of analysing the customer's past purchase pattern (Shin and Sudhir, 2007).

While studies have revealed that the dynamic pricing can efficiently obtain consumer surplus and grow firms' profitability by up to 25% (Garbarino and Lee, 2003; Petro, 2015), there is equal chance of stirring up consumers' perceptions of unfairness. Li et al's study revealed that consumer's perceptions of unfairness is greater and lower levels of trust is lower when they come to know that the firm is charging different price to different customer (Li et al., 2017). CRM-based pricing, also known as the price differentiation strategy, has direct negative effects on existing customers' psychology

by making them feel punished for their loyalty (Fernandes and Calamote, 2015). Such a realisation makes existing customers react negatively, which raises a huge question mark regarding the practicality of differential pricing (Weisstein et al., 2013). Firms often disregard the necessity to balance customer retention and acquisition; failure to address these issues can lead customers to question the firm's fairness practice (Kimes and Wirtz, 2003), potentially making customers withdraw from existing relationships or to involve in a behaviour that might harm the firm to a greater extent (Nguyen and Klaus, 2013). Researchers have therefore urged practitioners to consider and expend efforts to manage consumers' perceptions of fairness, as these perceptions are emotionally associated with their trust and total satisfaction with the relationship, their brand loyalty, certainly and repurchase intent (Grewal et al., 2004; Haws and Bearden, 2006; Garbarino and Maxwell, 2010).

Few studies have been carried out that examine pricing-based perceptions of unfairness; however, they are mostly focused on the need for transparency. Ferguson (2013) underlined the fact that perceived price fairness is highly influenced by who reveals the price rise, the extent of the price surge and the degree to which the details behind the price rise are disclosed and associated with the costs.

Relationship Asymmetry

CRM as a philosophy promotes the concept of customer retention and win-win via relationship and co-creation (Boulding, 2005) which means that service providers and service users should gain mutual and equal benefits as a result of being in a relationship with each other. CRM demands the need for relationship symmetry, which reflects the level of equality amongst relationship members (Nguyen, 2012). On the contrary, asymmetric relationships challenge the concept of power equilibrium and motivate the stronger party to behave opportunistically; such conflicts of interest eventually result in less stable relationships.

Studies have explored how firms are encouraged to hold greater power than their service users by taking a bigger share of the value co-created in the relationship through the use of CRM applications. However, knowledge of being in a dysfunctional position can engender perceptions of unfairness amongst service users. Once they

are aware of, or experience, such issues, customers will deliberately hide their information or be careful about what information they share with the firm.

Customers share information and opt into company newsletters and subscriptions when they trust that their information can be of value to the brand they trust. In exchange, they also expect some return for providing their information, such as in the form of exclusive deals, news, offers, and so on. In order for a firm to achieve the most from their relationship marketing strategy, they must rely on customers providing their personal information; hence, firms need to ensure an environment of constant communication with their customers. In cases where customers get a hint of firms using their data and information to make excessive profits (i.e., more than the value they are receiving back), they might stop releasing their data or input incorrect information instead. This notion is backed up by the theory of Schemer's Schema (Wright, 1986), which states that customers hold instinctive views about firms' marketing strategies and therefore, in cases where they dislike what they experience from a firm, they tend to take action and amend their conduct. Customers also modify their information when they realise that their data is being misused or they feel that their privacy has not been respected by the firms they trust. Privacy invasion and information misuse are other identified dark side behaviours, and they are briefly discussed below.

Information Misuse

CRM aims to serve customers better by analysing the data collected from the customers themselves. Today, service providers are capable of collecting data from diverse sources and customer touchpoints that include both online and offline tracks. It has also been identified that customer data is often traded from one firm to the another without customers' consent or knowledge (Turow et al., 2015). Product or service customisation is possible if firms have detailed knowledge of customers' behaviour; however, firms often forget that such behaviour tracking carries high chances of weakening the position of the consumer. This is "because marketers can now survey and analyse consumer behaviour in such a detailed way that they achieve what has been unachievable heretofore: turning the consumer's interior inside out" (Zwick and Dholakia, 2004, p. 31).

Nguyen and Simkin (2015) defined information misuse as the incorrect use of collected information; this might range from collecting sensitive data without the explicit consent of customers, to selling this data to copious numbers of third parties and agencies who monetise such information in unknown ways. This is one of the most common practices in the service industry, including MNOs (Payne and Frow, 2005, 2011). Although few research studies have looked into this issue, they are limited to subjects like the impact of perceptions of fairness on high involvement versus low involvement purchases and advantaged versus disadvantaged customers (Nguyen and Simkin, 2017). It is crucial to understand the impact of the issues of information misuse in relation to other relationship constructs like satisfaction, loyalty and trust.

A *Harvard Business Review* article (Morey, Forbath and Schoop, 2015) stated that although some companies practice transparent data strategies, a large number choose to keep consumers in the dark about the volume of data gathered and their level of control over sharing, and they ask for forgiveness rather than permission in cases when customers come to find out about such misuses. In the same article, it was mentioned that companies are also quietly collecting personal data that are of no immediate use because they reason that they might be valuable someday. These practices are encouraged firstly by a lack of applicable laws and policies and secondly, because of consumers' lack of awareness. Therefore, in this research, the researcher aims to understand service users' level of awareness about such hidden behaviours.

Information Asymmetry

Limited information is also a form of manipulation. This form of unfair practice includes the amount of information provided to customers and its transparency, in terms of the details shared. Some researchers have identified that retailers tend to provide detailed information in relation to high-price products, while providing significantly less information in relation to low-price products. Unfortunately, this issue is widely prevalent in the MNO industry. When you enter a network operator's store, there is a chance that the sales assistant will treat you unfairly based on the value of the service/package you are looking for. The treatment given to someone who is looking for a high-end smartphone and the most expensive deal on offer is treated differently to someone who is looking for a low-end budget smartphone and a comparatively

cheaper deal. The details provided, along with the level of support and time invested in the two types of customers, is not the same.

The other type of information asymmetry includes the level of complexity of the details shared with customers. In such cases, the product or service details are explained in such a way that a normal, non-technical buyer cannot completely understand the offer being made. Such complexity results in customer confusion, which leads to them making a poor purchase decision. Customer confusion is discussed further in the next section.

Customer Confusion and Manipulation

According to Frow et al. (2015), this form of dark side behaviour includes firms' use of misleading or puzzling information or the practice of hiding the appropriate information from customers so that the customers end up making poor purchase decisions that keep them in a disadvantaged position. The practice of such strategies takes many different forms; from complex pricing to creating complicated company policies that are hard to read and understand. Vulnerable groups, including the young, the elderly and the poor, are mainly vulnerable to suffering as a result of such dark side behaviours (Sheth and Sisodia, 2006).

Some studies on the practicality and ethical issues associated with loyalty programs have also been carried out (Pez et al., 2017) exploring how loyalty programs, a form of relationship marketing, can exert pressure and make customers buy things they do not even have an immediate need for. Amongst the earliest research on the negative aspects of loyalty programs are a study by Stauss et al. (2005), where they explored the negative consequences of loyalty programs. On exploring the feelings of frustration that are generated via loyalty schemes, seven causes for frustration were identified; among them were including rewards that are very hard to achieve or are diminutive when compared to the effort required to gain them, biased procedures or point collection schemes that "dehumanize the brand–consumer relationship" (Pez et al., 2017, p. 72). Further studies have examined why some customers are against joining loyalty programs. In addition to the efforts that must be expended in order for a reward to be achieved, Palmatier and Steinhoff (2019) identified how customers

develop feelings of unfairness when they do not benefit from rewards, which eventually negatively impacts their loyalty intention and decision.

Furthermore, forced cross-selling and upselling strategies that target existing customers are quite common in the MNO industry. Service providers often send out promotional and offer emails, push notifications and, most commonly, make telephone calls with the aim of gaining more transactions from their existing customers. This not necessarily a source of pressure only on service users, but on internal employees as well. The management's demands regarding the implementation of CRM systems often impose pressure on staff with regard to upselling and cross-selling. As a result of greed sparked by incentives, employees may involve in exerting pressure to make customers buy the products or services that they do not need (Frow et al., 2011). Mis-selling, mis informing and forced selling are some of the prevalent dark sides in relation to manipulation. Lack of employee trainings and correct employee empowerment are the causes behind these dark practices, which will be discussed in the later section.

Furthermore, frequent price and rate alterations are other prevalent practices that can confuse both existing and potential customers. Before customers can fully understand and adapt to their new tariff, firms implement changed rates (Frow et al., 2011).

Opacity Regarding 'Third Party' Information

Although this matter is briefly addressed in the section above, the researcher would like to highlight it as a separate issue as a result of both its importance and relative ambiguousness. In recent times, almost on every contract an individual sign, there is a statement that states that their data will be shared with partners and third parties. However, there is further information on the nature and number of third parties involved. There is a high probability that all the nuisance calls that customers receive might be a result of their data being shared with so-called 'third-parties'. If examined closely, third party data sharing turns into an unceasing circle. Furthermore, it is necessary for customers to understand whether the third party involved has relevance to their data. It is therefore responsibility of the service provider to be as transparent as possible about their third party and how the customer data are managed.

Customer Lock-in and Switching Barriers

Customer lock-in, originally, was understood and practiced as a means to escalate customer loyalty through up- and cross-selling opportunities, keeping consumers with the business and ultimately gaining repeated proceeds from a uniform set of customers (Farrell and Klemperer, 2007; Harrison, Beatty, Reynolds and Noble, 2012). Although some business models suggest that firms should create customer lock-in strategies as they can bring about greater opportunities for value co-creation and long-term profitability (Pynnonen, 2008), it is companies who take the bigger chunk of the benefits by implementing such strategies. In most cases, consumers do not even realise that they are in a locked-in position. However, should they gain such knowledge, it will engender perceptions of unfairness.

As a strategic instrument by which to manage customer retention, switching barriers are significantly popular amongst scholars and practitioners (Chuah et al., 2017). Switching barriers refer to the struggles faced by customers (service users in this study) when they attempt to purchase products/services from another competitor. Prior research has identified that there are financial (e.g., termination fees involved), social (e.g., losing faith with existing provider) and psychological (e.g., lack of confidence about change) switching barriers (Blut et al., 2015; Jones et al., 2007; Kim et al., 2004). This is a prevalent practice amongst MNOs. Switching MNOs is intentionally made quite difficult as a result of the process involved in switching. For example, even after the end of a contract period, operators make it difficult for service users to switch to another MNOs if service users want to keep their existing number. The process involves getting a PAC code (Porting Authorisation Code) from their existing provider and giving that to the new MNO. MNOs increased the complications in this area by not issuing the PAC code easily; however, after 2017, Ofcom issued issues a new rule to simplify switching when they identified that getting PAC code was one of the biggest difficulties in changing provider and the customers face several unwanted attempts from current service providers to persuade you to stay (Ofcom, 2017).

This might reduce the switching barrier to some extent. Other than procedural barriers, consumers can go through many other hurdles when switching service providers; these include contractual, monetary and psychological costs (Burnham et al., 2003;

Jones et al., 2007). For a different perspective, the basic and most common example of switching barriers in the retail industry is the 'razor and blades' business model (Picker, 2010) where there is a practice of selling 'Razor handle' and 'blades' separately. Razors are purposefully sold in a lower price creating a market for the blades that are only compatible with their original razors. This model guarantees profit from recurring revenue and while also locking-in the customer. A practice that is specific to the UK MNOs sector is 'SIM lock' practice, which is one of the most prevalent forms of switching barrier. Mobile handsets are often 'locked' by the network providers from which the handset was bought; meaning that the handset is compatible with the SIM of that specific network provider only. If the service user wants to switch to another network and keep their current handset, the handset needs to be unlocked. UK MNOs have different provisions for Pay As You Go and Pay Monthly plans.

According to a report published by Uswitch, EE and Vodafone lock their handsets on both types of plans, while Three has been selling unlocked devices on both plans since 2013. In the case of O2, their Pay As You Go handsets are locked, while handsets on Pay Monthly plans sold after 2018 are sold unlocked. Also, there's no time limit and charges to unlock the pay as you go phone. Network providers can unlock handsets with or without charges, and the time it takes to unlock a handset and the charges for doing so also vary as per the plan. EE unlocks its Pay As You Go and 'out of contract' handsets without any charge, while it costs £8.99 for handsets on its Pay Monthly plans. In the case of Vodafone, the phones are sold locked to the provider, but they do not charge any amount for customers to unlock their devices (Minihane, 2020).

Wooing Customers

Researchers like Rigby et. al. warned about 'stalking, not wooing customer' stating that there are high possibility of upsetting potential customers or perhaps equally dangerous to annoy disinterested customers while trying to build relations with them (Rigby et al., 2002). The key point behind this danger is to understand that a CRM system allows firms to contact large numbers of potential customers; however, it is not necessarily advisable for them to do so. Failure to adhere to this advice may cause a firm's relationship strategy to backfire.

It is necessary to understand that, like any other relationships, customer relationships are two-way avenues. Firms might want to create more relationships with possible customers, while neglecting to understand whether or not such customers actually want a relationship with them. Firms also fail to develop relationships with customers who actually value them and, in such cases, they will lose such customers to a competitor. Likewise, firms who make an effort to build relationships with disinterested customers might be perceived by customers as stalking them, thereby upsetting prospective customers and changing them from potential customers into vocal critics. Therefore, as suggested by Rigby et al. (2002), whether or not to contact customer should be established based upon the firm's customer strategy rather than what the CRM system implemented can offer.

The other aspect that requires firm's consideration is whether or not the collected data are actually being used by the company. Many firms are thrilled by the amount of data they are able to collect, but they do not realise what a waste of resources it is if they do not analyse the data and derive meaningful interpretations from them. Therefore, it is necessary to determine what kind of data firms actually need and at what time; currently, firms tend to collect data that they do not even need on the assumption that the database might be useful sometime in the future. This is clearly against data regulations outlined by UK Information Commission Office (ICO), which state that collected data should be relevant, not excessive in volume and not be stored for longer than necessary (ICO, n.d).

Hidden Charges and Financial Exploitation

Another dark side behaviour is the intentional financial misuse of service users to increase the revenue. Unjust monetary fines, hidden fees and unexpectedly high bills are some common complaints that keep circulating among customers. In terms of the MNO industry, the most common form of financial exploitation is bills that are higher than the contracted amount. Ofcom receive thousands of complains regarding bills that have been charged beyond contracted price without the service users' knowledge. On a press release, Lindsey Fussell, Ofcom's Consumer Group Director, said that they keep an eye on how MNOs are billing their customers, and they penalise any careless mistakes when identified (Ofcom, 2017).

Another prevalent example includes service users having to pay significantly more if they choose to pay by cash or cheque instead of Direct Debit. It may seem unfair for someone who cannot use Direct Debit. Likewise, there are some network providers who charge an extra amount to produce paper or itemised bills for their customers, which is also completely unfair.

Auto renewal is another practice that is quite popular amongst MNOs. Ofcom, the regulatory body that oversees the UK's telecommunications industry, has stated that they receive abundant complaints about this practice. This behaviour is the result of a lack of transparency at the point of sale. Automatic renewal is used to exploit the ignorance of service users or to prevent them from switching to another competitor. Ofcom (2015) has released the following examples of renewal terms that are considered to be unfair:

Examples of unfair renewal terms	
	1. If the renewal terms on the contract are not visible at the point of sale;
	2. If the service provider fails to send a reminder notice at a sensible time before the renewal term actually takes effect;
	3. If the terms or renewal policy do not provide a clear and stress-free opt out option, without the customer having to go through needless formal procedures;
	4. If there is insignificant benefit for both the parties as a result of being in the contract;
	5. If there are other terms that need to be fulfilled in order to opt out; for example, a too long notice period; and/or
	6. If the service provider is applying unfair charges to the user (or charges that are so high that the service user is forced to stay with their existing network).

Table 2.6 Examples of fair renewal terms by Ofcom (2015)

Behavioural Tracking

Tracking the online behaviour of customers was established as one of the remarketing strategies, and it is a strategy by which firms can create offers for customers based on customers' behaviour. However, today's technological advancements have

enabled firms to track each and every movement of an online consumer, or those of a mere prospect who visits the website to gain knowledge only. It is widely established that firms can track location, gender, names, telephone numbers and email addresses based on the information input directly by consumers, but the power of CRM systems do not stop there. Technology has made it possible to track customers' online activity, including, but not limited to, the time they spent on one particular page of the website, the frequency of their visits to the website, information about the website of the substitute brands that they visit and so on. As advantageous as it is for firms in terms of transactions and profitability, it generates privacy concerns along with the feeling of threat for consumers, as every single online movement that they make is virtually spied on. Firms install CRM systems to gain greater insights into customer behaviour and their preferences, but they do not realise they are unknowingly violating the psychological contract of customers.

2.8.5 Summary of the identified dark sides

The aforementioned dark sides of CRM are only some of the dark side behaviours that are identified in the available literature. Looking specifically at the MNO industry, some of the most prevalent dark practices include price rises based on the retail price index or any other mid-contract term raise that is implemented without the prior knowledge of the customer; misleading and dishonest practices, such as connecting the customer to 3G, despite having promised 4G or 5G; misleading plans with hidden clauses regarding pricing, and so on. Recurring changes in price, contract auto-rolling, bill continuity, complex terms and conditions—for example, using numerous special cases, conditions and frequent changes—are some other examples that can be added to the list. Similarly, loyalty programs are a significant tool used in relationship marketing that have also been questioned over their tendency to exert pressure on consumers (Pez et al., 2017). The nature of loyalty as a marketing tool has been questioned with regard to how practitioners have been taking advantage of consumers through it. Instead of using it merely as a relational tool, firms are using loyalty to increase transactions and maximise their profitability ignoring the relational aspect of it. A study in dark sides of loyalty identified that loyalty schemes exert pressure to the consumers, which even negatively impacts their psychological well-being (Pez et. al., 2017).

Out of the very limited studies undertaken in this discipline, Payne and Frow’s work is momentous and it provides a foundation to this research. Their work has served as the basis by which to conceptualise dark side practices and to identify the gaps in knowledge that can be filled by the findings of this study. The Figure 4 illustrates the currently identified dark sides of CRM.

Figure 2.5 Dark Sides of CRM, adapted from Frow et. al., 2011, p.82

Although the study conducted by Frow et. al., (2011) differentiated dark side behaviours as being intended or unintended, there is no a basis on which consumers can distinguish what a service provider’s motives are. Despite the motive, when service users feel cheated and unfairly treated by their brands, the consumers react in a certain way, some of the behaviours from the service users being dark too. Ultimately, it is the buyer-seller relationship that will be affected. Therefore, it is vital to raise awareness about dark sides practices so that service providers will be discouraged from taking advantage of their consumers through loopholes; and rather drive them to actually focus on profitability through fairer and transparent relationship, which is a core philosophy of relationship management strategy.

Additionally, a study conducted by Lancelot-Miltgen, Mimouni Chaabane and Pez-Pérard (2019) discussed how firms divert from their actual objective of implementing CRM that results into dark sides unintentionally.

Objective sought by the company	Practices	Unintended consequences for the customer
Increased customer loyalty	Expenses incurred within the same brand to collect points and obtain a reward Performance metrics often exclusively related to spending and acceleration of purchasing behavior Too many “pushy” commercial solicitations	Lockdown Restriction of freedom Perceived pressure Oversolicitation
Rewarding the best customers	Rewards often perceived as low value Rewards often perceived as difficult to achieve Rewards often perceived as too exclusive	Frustration Perceived injustice
Increasing the value of the best customers	Priority allocation of resources to high value customers Development of hierarchical loyalty programs with risks of demotion	Discrimination between high- and low-value customers Disappointment of low-value customers
Improving the quality of the experience	Collection of customer data	Loss of control Intrusion Distrust

Table 2. 7 Main dark sides of customer relations (Lancelot-Miltgen, Mimouni Chaabane and Pez-Pérard, 2019, p. 221)

The table above reflects how businesses deviate from the actual objective of CRM and practice the activities that are perceived as being dark from service users’ perspectives. It is therefore even more crucial to adopt a holistic approach to the CRM implementation framework.

Despite the fact that CRM and the concept of customer relationships generally revolve around moral factors such as trust and emotions, the element of ethics – which is a

crucial factor required to build trust in a relationship – has been largely ignored (Bull and Adam, 2011). Scholars have established that the conventional CRM philosophy lacks a holistic approach and is mainly based on a narrow construct that fails to consider ethical issues appropriately. This state of affairs has sadly not changed, even after several studies have highlighted the need for change. Organisations must implement a holistic approach in CRM along with careful considerations of ethical elements.

In order to address the identified dark sides, Payne and Frow later introduced a process-based CRM framework (Fig 5) and explained how each interrelated business processes could be implemented by service providers in order to eliminate the dark sides that they had identified.

Figure 2. 6 Addressing 'dark sides' service provider practices - towards 'enlightened' CRM, adapted from (Nguyen, Simkin and Canhoto, 2015, p.31)

The limitations of Frow et al.'s work provide the researcher in this study with an opportunity to identify and expand on both the dark side behaviours and category. Although their dark sides identified by Frow et al., 2011 have been categorised on the

basis of the means used and the objectives of service providers, there is a very limited description as to what defines each particular category.

Researcher aims to identify the activities engaged in by MNOs that service users might perceive as being hiddenly practiced their network providers. Such an identification will make service providers aware of the consequences of these behaviours and it might potentially make them think of better alternatives to doing so, particularly if their activities are unintentional. On the other hand, if firms are deliberately practicing such behaviours merely to rip off profit from their service users, these firms might recognise the severity of the consequences of such behaviours and therefore refrain from continuing such activities.

The next section discusses the perceptions of fairness and service quality felt by the service users. As highlighted several times in the previous section, companies need to develop strategies aimed at maintaining customers who experience feelings of being treated unequally and unfairly.

2.9 Consumer Perceptions of Fairness

Previous research has identified the fact that treating customers differently carries the potential of inducing dissatisfaction and perceptions of unfairness (Boulding et al., 2005). As per some literature that has been published, fairness is outlined as “a judgment of whether an outcome and/or the process to reach an outcome are reasonable, acceptable, or just” (Bolton et al., 2003, p. 474). It is also recognised that perceptions of fairness are stimulated only when an individual compares their individual result with a comparative other’s result. Nguyen connects perceptions of fairness to attribution theory in one of his studies (Nguyen et al., 2011), which suggests that it is possible for people to look for underlying clarifications for an incident, if anything is unanticipated and/or undesirable (Folkes, 1988). Similarly, perceptions of unfairness are also affected by the principles of equity theory (Adams, 1963), which suggests that people in a social exchange relationship associate and match the proportion of their efforts versus rewards with equivalent other; any difference identified is what stimulates the perception of unfairness.

Recently, consumer's perceptions of fairness has been gaining popularity and attention among firms (Samaha et al., 2011), practitioners (Groves and LaRocca, 2011) and researchers (Bolton et al., 2010). Doubtful marketing strategies used to appeal or keep existing consumers, such as customer tracking, poor information handling, favouring profitable segments, frequent price changes, hidden fees and surcharges, are what may alarm consumers in relation to the fairness (Frow et al., 2011; Nguyen, 2012). Most recently, a study explored perceptions of unfairness in relation to e-CRM which discovered that elements of poor service quality, price, communication efforts and differential treatment are some internal factors what may prompt consumer perception of unfairness (Yu et al., 2015).

As mentioned earlier, treatment that is based on individuals' needs and desires is the core of CRM; therefore, the offering of customised products, services, prices and even methods of promotion are quite common (Bull and Adam, 2011). When implementing customised offers, brands also need to realise that 'word of mouth' is prevalent and equally powerful in relationship marketing. As a result of effective word of mouth, customers will come to know if someone else is getting better deals and that knowledge is what makes them feel unfairly treated. Therefore, the failure to consider such dimensions of differential treatment, and the inappropriate use and misuse of CRM, increase the likelihood of firms' overall relationship marketing efforts and investments failing (Nguyen, 2012).

Studies have shown that higher service customisation leads to higher perceived quality; however, studies show that service customisation is one of the major reasons behind unfairness perceptions (Frow et al., 2011) which has also been identified as one of the dark side behaviours and will be discussed in detail in a later section. Furthermore, service quality is regarded as one of the major elements in customer relationship management; therefore, understanding service users' perceptions of service quality is imperative. Yu et al. (2015) identified that a lack of service quality and communication efforts from service providers play a role in consumers' perceptions of unfairness. Customers' judgements of whether the service quality delivered is reasonable or not are what determines their perceptions of service quality. The next section will provide more detail about the instrument and the scopes of service quality.

2.10 Perceptions of Service Quality

This topic is briefly discussed here as the researcher in this study is aiming to understand the perceptions of service users. Perception refers to the difference between expectation versus actual performance, therefore it is safe to say the perception on service quality is built through overall journey of service delivery. Although Grönroos postulated that service quality can be both technical and functional, however, it has been described by marketing experts as being something that is difficult to understand and evaluate (Parasuraman et al., 1985).

This study views service quality as being a major element of customer relationship management. It is a powerful tool by which consumers can spread positive word of mouth about the firm and its service quality through interactional channels that consumers today find trustworthy (Nijssen and Herk, 2009). Previous studies have shown that better service quality prevents customers from switching; this leads to profitability through customer retention (Gounaris et al., 2010) and also intensifies consumption and creates opportunities for new offerings (Payne et al., 2008). Firms have therefore started realising the importance of considering customers' perceptions of service quality (Saravanan and Rao, 2007).

2.10.1 Service Quality Model

SERVQUAL's basic idea is the difference between a customer's expectations versus perceptions of the service received (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Originated and popularly known as the Gap Model, the model of service quality was developed during a five-year long research project dating from 1983 to 1988 by a group of American scholars (Parasuraman et al., 1988), and it defines service quality as a function of service users' perceptions and expectations. This model serves as a scale by which to measure service quality, and, in parallel, indicates the likely reasons behind service quality problems. When first established, there were 10 components, which were later reduced to five due to the fact that some of the components were identified to be overlapping and interrelated. The original 10 components, which are competence, courtesy, credibility, security, access, communication, knowing the customer, tangibles, reliability and responsiveness, were later compressed down to five, which are reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness. As explained by

Parasuraman et al., unlike the nature of products, which can be objectively measured using numbers and scores, service quality is an abstract concept that has the unique features of being intangible, heterogenous and inseparable from production and consumption. Therefore, Parasuraman and his fellow researchers proposed that consumers' perceptions of quality could be measured as a means of measuring service quality. The new 5 dimensions are briefly discussed below.

Reliability

This dimension reflects service provider's ability to deliver the service exactly as promised. Reflecting the accuracy and service user's dependability towards the service providers, this dimension measures the extent to which service users/customers can rely on the promises made by service providers. For example, when purchasing a mobile deal over the phone, the customer makes a purchase decision fully relying on the information provided over the phone. There are cases of customers being sold the contract with limited and false information. Studies have identified dark behaviours based on lack of reliable information supplied by the sellers.

Assurance

This dimension reflects employees' knowledge about their duties and their ability to build confidence in service users towards their service. Often employees are not trained enough, thus resulting in a lack of knowledge that can have an adverse impact on service quality. Similarly, such a lack of knowledge results in service inconsistency. As postulated in equity theory, such differences in service level in one encounter versus another are also one of the crucial factors that have an impact on fairness perceptions.

Tangibles

This dimension explains the physical evidences and facilities involved in service encounters, including the appearance of physical capacities, equipment, employees and communication materials. In this study, when a customer visits a store to enquire about or to purchase a mobile phone deal, the customer may expect to be asked to be seated, rather than to stand in a queue, in cases when the waiting time is long. A comfortable seat, air conditioning, the number of sales assistants in the store, the availability of demonstration devices that the customer can try out (i.e., the model that

the customer is interested in), the way the staff are dressed (i.e., uniform), and so on, can be factors that customers take into account when forming an opinion about the service on offer. This reflects the fact that customers' service perception development begins long before the actual subscription or the purchase of a product or service. Similarly,

Empathy

Empathy is a core feature when it comes to services, especially when it comes to service users/consumers forming perceptions about their service provider. Empathy refers to the human side of the brand. It reflects how much service providers care about their service users, including whether employees care about the service users and whether they try to provide customised solutions based on the individual's needs, and so on. This makes the customer feel that the service provider is a part of them and not just a brand. For example, when a service user encounters a problem, how well the staff try to understand the issue, if they listen to the customer and if they care enough to put themselves in the customer's shoes while addressing the problems, and so on, are key issues.

Responsiveness

This dimension reflects whether employees are inclined to help customers. It includes both the knowledge and promptness that are deployed in responding to any queries; for example, how well staff reply to queries on social media platforms and how quickly they respond to social media posts, tweets and private messages, and so on. There are times when brands use software that generates automatic replies in order to trick customers into believing that the firm is being responsive. Similarly, there are times when customers are promised that a customer service agent will phone them in a certain amount of time and they never hear from them. All these activities, which are carried out by staff while dealing with customer queries, fall under the responsiveness dimension.

Despite the fact that the intangible and subjective nature of services makes it tough to estimate service quality, SERVQUAL is still viewed as being a dominant measurement scale in the area of service quality. The recent studies have however proposed the need of development of new service quality model (Riadh, 2009; Chanana et al., 2016)

considering the rapid change in the nature of service industry. For example, the development and popularity of social media and online brand communities has increased the need for communication efforts to be made by service providers more than ever. The failure to address service users both sensitively and in a timely fashion can result in service failure.

The primary objective of implementing a SERVQUAL model is to understand the gap in service delivery and when identified; to capitalise and close the gap. Failure to understand and adhere to these dimensions of SERVQUAL leads service users to have perceptions of unfairness, which are also viewed as being dark behaviours. Such dark practices, in relation to service delivery, lead service users to engage in negative word of mouth or to end their relationship with the service provider. This issue will be addressed in the discussion chapter in greater detail.

Some of the established dark sides in relation to service quality and delivery failure include lack of responsiveness, lack of communication, negligence from the staffs handling customer touchpoints, and so on. Based on the observation data and analysis, the main problem is that MNOs are not implementing strategies aimed at addressing service delivery failure. They seem to be ignoring the learning relationship aspect of CRM, which is the root of the CRM concept. This is where need of addressing service failure, which is also known as service recovery, comes into play.

2.10.2 Service Recovery Strategy

Service recovery is probably the most studied area in service management literature (Kunz and Hogueve, 2011) and many academics have advised practitioners on how to effectively implement and manage service recovery. However, past studies have shown that organisations are significantly lacking in service recovery management strategies (Michel et al., 2009), which suggests that academic research needs to be more visible in organisational service recovery policies and practices.

The idea of service recovery underlines the strategy and activities towards restoring consumer trust, satisfaction and loyalty after a service failure incident. Such strategies confirm that organisation learns and improves from their failure and empowers their

employees in doing so (Michel et al., 2009). Service recovery incorporates the most prevalent issues, such as service recovery, complaint handling, organisational learning and employee empowerment. Upon analysing the observed data gathered in this study, the researcher witnessed how poor UK MNOs are in terms of complaint handling and realised that such failures are costing them their relationships with their service users. In simple terms, the efforts that organisations make in relation to making things right is what service recovery is. Service recovery counts more than ever today, because of the power of online communities and social media. They are increasingly used by consumers to post complaints and share their experiences, both to the service providers and fellow consumers. Unlike the traditional channels, the complaint and a firm's recovery efforts are evident to other passive spectators. The next section discusses the online brand communities and evolution of CRM to social CRM. The researcher briefly introduces concepts around online brand communities (OBCs) while also deriving how OBCs and effective social media handling are crucial in CRM success; and how the activities around OBCs and social platforms can result into dark sides if misused inappropriately.

2.11 Conceptualizing Online Brand Communities and Social CRM

Despite their popularity in practice, the available literature on online communities shows a lack of uniformity in the definition of online communities, which also reflects the lack of an extensive typology of online communities. There is a broad range of online communities based on their objectives, which is likely the reason why there is a lack of a detailed definition. Online communities can vary according to many factors, such as the purpose of the online community, the structure of the interactions between community members and the administration of the community (Gallagher and Savage, 2013).

On social networking sites, brand communities, fans and consumers create interactions with other consumers and the brand itself by 'liking' and commenting on posts made on the page or by sharing user-generated content (Loureiro, Maximiano and Panchapakesan, 2018). Prior studies have stated that brand communities are important marketing instruments and understanding who joins a community for what reason may have potentially powerful managerial implications (Ouwensloot and Odekerken-Schröder, 2008). Most studies on OBCs are primarily focused on word of

mouth (WOM) and its impact on purchase intention and purchase decisions. In addition to looking into the positives and value co-creation offered by OBCs, there are also negative impacts posed by OBCs that should be considered; however, these are rather unexplored by scholars. The relationships between consumers and firms and their engagement with each other do not always result in positive outcomes and value co-creation. A study conducted by Li et al. (2013) brought to light the concept of value co-destruction, which is defined as a context in which the nature of the relationship, the engagement involved and implementation of resources between consumers and an organisation result in detrimental relationships.

OBCs are either member initiated or organisation initiated. The current researcher used organisations initiated and mediated by OBCs to collect the data. The credibility of organisations' own OBCs is often questioned in terms of trustworthiness, as there have been occasions on which brands have been found to be misusing and mishandling communications within these communities in their favour. This includes creating controversial posts to get community members or non-members engaging with such posts, deleting any negative or unfavourable reviews and comments made on their posts, engaging fake commenters and reviewers, using social bots to secure a higher reach and higher engagement, and so on. The hospitality industry, and particularly hotels and restaurants, have been seen to be publishing fake reviews with the motive of increasing visibility on platforms such as Tripadvisor, Expedia and even on their own websites (Lappas et al., 2016), as even half a star's difference in reviews can make a huge difference to customers' purchase decisions. The practices mentioned above are all related to manipulative and deceptive tactics, which have been identified as one of the dark sides of CRM by Nguyen et al. (2017).

Businesses trying to manipulate OBCs through intervention is not unheard of. There are many examples of firms who have been found to be deleting genuine comments that are negative or adding fake positive reviews and comments that rate their products or services more highly. A study by Zhuang et al. (2018) defined this as manufactured opinion. Few clues are available about the fact that manipulation is taking place in the case of businesses deleting information, as consumers do not readily suspect manipulative intent; thus, this manipulation results in higher purchase intention and adverse selection. However, consumers with substantial expertise in

online shopping are less vulnerable to the influence of manipulation due to their heightened levels of suspicion.

Given the tremendous impact of online product reviews on consumer purchases, firms may manipulate online reviews to increase sales by anonymously posting favourable reviews and/or deleting negative reviews (Hu et. al, 2011). Despite the actions of platform operators, who police and sift through online content for forged reviews, and the efforts of policymakers to eradicate fake review practices, the manipulation of online reviews has persisted in several forms. Businesses involved in such manipulative practices do so to increase their ratings, which are often measured in terms of stars, as purchase decisions based on the reputation of firms or brands are substantial in the current online shopping environment. Having said this, there is little to no empirical evidence on the benefits of such manipulation for firms or the economic effect of such misinformation. In addition, no studies have been conducted in relation to the motives and processes involved in practicing such unethical behaviours.

Furthermore, there is also the emerging concept of vine reviews and reviews provided through influencer marketing – both of which are extremely popular. As suggested by the term ‘influencer’ itself, influencer marketing is a social media marketing strategy where brands collaborate with people of influence; that is, those with a mass following and reach, to launch their products and services, mainly on their private social media platforms. These social media influencers are usually paid to review and endorse products through social networks, including but not limited to Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Snapchat, YouTube and Twitter, and are presented as being completely personal endorsements. However popular they are, the reviews shared through influencer marketing are also equally controversial in terms of the trust and credibility of those reviews, given the money associated with influencer marketing strategies. Despite the questions about the ethical status of such reviews and the trust element associated with the use of influencers, the sales generated by influencer marketing strategies in today’s world are significant. This form of marketing could be one of the leading marketing strategies in today’s social media era; however, there is a lack of empirical research and literature – hence, future research needs to focus on this area of relationship marketing.

Some of the past research has indicated that despite consumers' awareness of firms engaging in such manipulative practices, they still let the reviews, posts and comments visible in these communities impact their purchase decisions. However, these studies do not clarify the level of consumers' awareness and whether they are aware of such consequences. Hence, future research needs to be undertaken in this unexplored area.

2.12 Additional theories to support the research findings

Questions about fairness do not always originate with comparisons as to what someone else is getting. As postulated by equity theory, different consumer perceptions result from the comparison of an individual outcome with that of a comparative other. The comparison may not be limited to another person only, rather it may include certain segment of people, a group or the person him/herself compared to his/her previous experiences. As stated in equity theory, the feeling of inequity arises when an individual's perceived efforts and/or results of an exchange relationship are psychologically different with that of the comparable other (Adam, 1965). In the past, equity theory has been previously implemented in study within wider disciplines, including work motivation (Adam, 1965), fairness perceptions (Nguyen et al., 2014), customer revival (Homburg, Hoyer and Stock, 2007), CRM (Nguyen et al., 2009), organisational justice (Yean and Yusof, 2016) and online buying behaviour (Lim, 2019).

In this study, answering the research objectives involves understanding theories such as equity theory, justice theory and the theory of opportunism (as practiced by the firm). Further, the theory of reasoned action (TRA) will be discussed in brief in order to shed light on what makes service users behave in a certain way after realising that they have been taken advantage of by their service providers through the practice of dark behaviours that can destroy long-standing loyalty and the buyer–seller relationship as a whole.

2.12.1 Equity theory

The popularity of examining consumers' perceptions of equity is ever increasing amongst marketing and consumer researchers (Adapa and Cooksey, 2013),

particularly in the field of service marketing. Originally envisioned by Adams (1963), the idea behind equity theory is that people measure the efforts and investment that they sustain while being in a relationship exchange against the rewards that they gain in return (i.e., input versus output). This cognitive process also involves comparison of the results against other parallel experiences.

Equity theory is an insightful theoretical basis for this study as a whole as it provides an understanding of the equity of exchange between service providers and service users and a basis for comparing the behavioural practices of service providers against the responsive behavioural intentions of service users. Service fairness, or justice, is concept built on equity theory.

Some past studies have already explored the use of equity theory in learning consumer behaviour and their perceptions, including how the consumer responds to firm's service failures and recovery efforts (Andreassen, 2000; Hess et al., 2003), consumers' perceptions of price inequality and how they react to such conditions (Homburg et al., 2005; Xia et al., 2004), consumer ethics (Culiberg and Bajde, 2014) and consumer decision making (Craft, 2012).

2.12.2 Justice theory

Fairness issues and the reactions of service users towards unfairness can also be studied by using the theoretical underpinnings of some of the established justice theories; and by distributive theory and interactional justice in particular. Distributive justice refers to allocating goods or services to people in a fair proportion based on their inputs and needs; consumers seek for an equal share compared to what others are receiving. Fairness is questioned when a consumer realises that they are not receiving what they have paid for. From the CRM perspective, and particularly in this research, distributive justice links to service user's perception of unfairness on what the service users are receiving in return to what they agreed to receive from their service providers. It includes dark sides related to issues like favouritism to new vs existing customers, loyal customers having to pay more in long run often regarded as loyalty penalty, prioritising and treating a profitable segment of customer better and so on.

Furthermore, this study is also linked to interactional justice, which denotes how a firm/service provider treats service users after the consumer transaction when they are complaining or seeking solutions. This includes the attitudes of members of staff, sales advisors or customer support and whether service users are addressed with sincerity, respect, empathy and sensitivity. Overall, the adequacy of information and quality of the relationship/attitude during the conversation is what signifies interactional justice. These elements are the most observed and talked-about issues in the MNO industry at the moment. The Big Four MNOs' social media platforms are full of comments made by users who feel that they have had a poor experience, insufficient consumer service, been treated rudely by staff, received machine-like replies and been treated with a lack of empathy. All of these issues will be discussed in the findings chapter.

2.12.3 Theory of reasoned action and planned behaviour

Having been originally developed and suggested as a means of evaluating human behaviour (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010), this theory is probably one of the most popular and diversely implemented theories that has been applied to fields including, but not limited to, marketing, health, organisational behaviour, sociology, psychology, and so on. The theory was further extended to theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010) that added one more construct 'control behaviour'. TRA emphasises that the main factor behind an individual's behaviour is behavioural intention and which is determined by their attitude about doing the behaviour and their individual norm related with the behaviour. Theory of Planned behaviour later added 'perceived control' over the behaviour. Let's briefly look into these determinants.

- a. The behavioural intention of an individual begins with their belief about the outcome of a behaviour. In context to this study, a mobile service user may feel that, 'If I am vocal about how I feel about the service provider's particular behaviour then it will be heard, and the firm will stop practicing it'. Favourability of outcome and intentions are directly proportional. It shows that one's belief contributes on a person's ability to judge or assess the outcome of a particular behaviour.

- b. Normative beliefs refer to an individual's perceptions about the beliefs of important people around them, including their friends, family, acquaintances, colleagues and society as a whole. Such beliefs add to the perceptions of peers and the collective pressure that contributes to their drive to conform. In this study, friends' or family's recommendations, or reviews about a particular network operator, are found to have an impact on purchasing decisions. If a friend or family member has a negative experience with a particular MNO and recommends that an individual should not use that MNO, then the individual's intention of subscribing to a service with that particular MNO will decline. This suggests that intention gets stronger as a result of social pressure.
- c. Perceived behavioural control: An individual develops a belief about the factors that either assist or obstruct them from engaging in a particular behaviour. It can be an internal control, which is often regarded as self-efficacy; that is, an individual's belief in their own competence, or an external control, such as time, resources and social support. Perceived behavioural control is positively related to intention.
- d. Intention: Intention suggests an individual's plan of action characterising their motivation to perform a behaviour. Intention can be seen as a cause of behaviour.
- e. Behaviour: An individual acting a certain way is indicated by intention, which is also the function of beliefs and attitude including internal and external control variables.

In this study, a service provider's practice of unfair behaviours is the strongest external control variable that causes service users to behave in dark behaviours. Studies have shown that the consumer's ethical decision-making behaviours and decision-making models have been hugely associated and developed under the foundation of the theory of reasoned action (Cronan and Al-Rafee, 2008; Yoon, 2011).

2.12.4 Theory of Opportunism

Opportunism is one of the variables that are related to how and why a service provider ends up acting in a deceitful manner and practicing dark behaviours with their service users. In a study of moral hazards and supplier selection, Schauwecker (2012)

identified different types of opportunistic behaviours practiced by suppliers, which include failed delivery, quality shortfalls, poor service, price overcharging, failing on problem solving assurance and the manipulation of markets through corruption, this behaviours are closely related to this study too. However, most of the past studies on opportunism in buyer–supplier relationships are found to be predominantly focused on transaction cost; neglecting the behavioural aspects of relational exchange (Steinle, Schiele and Bohenkamp, 2019) which this study aims to discover to certain degree.

Opportunism is also guided by concepts such as the deceptive tactics and manipulative tactics that favour firms' profitability while putting service users in an unfair position. Deceptive tactics are the strategies that are intentionally implemented by marketers that are directed towards altering consumers' decision-making processes and rewarding firms with increased profitability. These tactics are morally wrong as a result of the fact that they violate psychological contracts with consumers/service users. An awareness of such violations can lead to consumers terminating the relationship exchange as a whole. Firms have been found to practice deceptive tactics in CRM, as well as through misinformation, exploiting data, mishandling privacy concerns, and so on.

Opportunism is also related to the concept of Manipulation, which is an ethical principle but deliberate in nature, that undermines consumer's normal/rational decision-making process. Rudinow (1978) outlined manipulation as being a marketing effort that intends to impact consumers' behaviour by altering goals through deception or by taking advantage of an individual's weakness. Sherr (2011, p.97) further described that marketing strategies are regarded as being manipulative if they are "intended to motivate by undermining what the marketer believes is his/her audience's normal decision-making process either by deception or by playing on a vulnerability that the marketer believes exists in his/her audience's normal decision-making process". Such practices, however, are ethically questionable.

2.13 Conclusion

Service providers are found taking reverse gear shifting their focus on transactional profit more than the relational one. They have been found practising malicious behaviours that ranges from violating psychological contract with their service users to financial exploitations (Frow et. al, 2008). Such behaviours in relation to customer relationship management are termed as dark sides of CRM.

The principal idea of relationship marketing and CRM is that the relationships are built on knowledge, based on customer information, and when customers share information about themselves or give their opinion about products or services, it is sole responsibility of the firm to capitalize perks of that relationship. One of the results being customised offerings. Customised offers to one customer however can be perceived by another customer as an unfair behavior, hence controversies around whether to keep customization as a goof marketing effort.

Perceptions of fairness is found studied in a range of backgrounds, but a very small amount of attention has actually been paid to marketing. In marketing, perceptions of fairness has been explored in relation to the pricing context to direct managers to start an operational pricing strategy (Bolton et al., 2003; Xia et al., 2004). Some years later, Lo et al. (2007) stretched the fairness perceptions research into directed promotional activities, that included exploitations through unfair promotional offers and imbalanced product bundling. As aforementioned, literature is limited in terms of its ability to provide insights into which of the CRM offerings implemented by the firms are fair and offers perceived value. Most recently, Nguyen (2015) undertook a study of fairness perceptions by observing how differently customers perceive when they know they are in a disadvantaged position. He explained how firms' CRM offerings end up inducing feelings of advantaged inequality or disadvantaged inequality. On realizing the need to measure the level of fairness or unfairness from consumers' perspectives, Nguyen (2012) proposed that some measures of fairness should be developed however not much has been gained since then.

In response to fill the gap in literature, the researcher has decided to undertake this research.

Chapter 3: Research Gap and Contextual Analysis

Introduction

Based on the findings of the literature review in the previous chapter, we can now appreciate the fact that there are some gaps in the CRM literature. Future research must identify and address the dark side behaviours being practiced in the service industry, as these go against the ideology of CRM and its objective of dual value co-creation through relationships. It is clear from the pre-established studies that the service industry, which also includes mobile network operators, is prone to practicing dark behaviours despite its competitiveness and it being highly regulated by regulatory bodies. This chapter is divided into three sections that include discussion of the research aim, questions and knowledge gap explored in this study. In addition, a contextual analysis of the MNO industry and conceptual framework of the study are provided.

This chapter begins by highlighting the research aim, objectives and the research questions that are posed in order to achieve the objectives. The main aim of this study is to understand whether service users are aware of the hidden practices used by their MNOs. If they are, how do they react and respond to such behaviour? And how can service providers be encouraged towards eliminating such behaviours in future?

To achieve the aim and objectives of this study, following research questions have been formulated:

- a) Are service users aware of their service provider's dark customer relationship management practices?
- b) What kinds of service provider behaviours are termed as dark behaviours by service users?
- c) What behaviours do service users practice after realising their disadvantaged position?
- d) What recommendations can be made to service providers with regard to achieving a win-win situation through transparent customer relationship management?

The objectives of this study are broken down as follows:

- a) To critically review existing literature in order to identify the research gap in the area of research;
- b) To highlight the awareness of service users and their perceptions with regard to the dark CRM behaviours practiced by mobile service providers;
- c) To identify the perceived dark behaviours practiced by mobile service providers;
- d) To identify the behavioural actions taken by service users in response to their awareness of their disadvantaged position; and
- e) To recommend a strategy framework for practitioners by which they can work towards eliminating such dark practices and encourage fairer relationship behaviours.

This study will proceed by thoroughly reviewing the context of the UK mobile network operator industry. This includes analysis of the current condition of the industry, economic impact of the industry, evolution of MNOs, market dynamics and the identification of the dark practices currently used within the industry. Study of MNOs' current practices will allow the researcher to establish the research gap. Thereafter, a summary of the industry and its current situation, along with an overview of the existing dark sides activities used by UK MNOs, is provided.

3.1 Contextual Industry Analysis

According to the statistics published by PWC (2018), the United Kingdom is the 6th leading national economy in the world in terms of nominal gross domestic product (GDP), 9th in terms of purchasing power parity (PPP) and 19th in terms of GDP per capita - that is 3.9% of the world's GDP. In 2019, with a GDP of approximately 2.11 trillion British pounds, the United Kingdom moved to being 5th largest economy in the world, even though the United Kingdom's economy grew by approximately 1.4 percent only which is the slowest growth since the great recession of the late 2010s, where the economy shrank by 4.2 percent (Clark, 2020). Within Europe, Britain's economy is second to Germany's, which is followed by. It is the second-largest economy in the European Union by both metrics and stands in 21st position in terms of population, with 65.5 million inhabitants as of 2016. The UK includes England, Scotland, Northern Ireland and Wales, and the power of UK economy differs from country to country. England has the highest GDP amongst the UK's constituent countries whilst Wales has the lowest.

The service sector dictates the UK economy and contributes to approximately 80% of GDP (Booth, 2018). The financial services industry is predominantly key, while London is the world's largest financial centre (GFCI, 2018). A report states that out of the 500 largest companies in the world, 26 are headquartered in the UK (Fortune, 2018). Since its formation in 1973, the UK has been the most prominent affiliate state of the European Union (EU); however, a referendum in 2016 resulted in 51.9% of UK voters backing leaving EU, and the country's exit took place on 31st January. In 2016, the total value produced by the European mobile ecosystem was nearly €161 billion (or 1% of GDP), with MNOs producing the major chunk (Sivakumaran and Rogers, 2017). Industry revenue dropped down to 33.8 billion British pounds in 2018. Globally, mobile technologies and services contributed 4.5% of GDP in 2017, adding \$3.6 trillion of economic value, which is expected to reach \$4.6 trillion, or 5% of GDP by 2022 (Sivakumaran and Pablo, 2018).

After the UK's decision to leave the EU, the inflation rate rose by 3% and the unemployment rate went down by 4.4%—to 4.8% (Clegg, 2018). While commenting on the impact of Brexit on the UK economy, scholars and researchers have stated that Brexit will make the UK inferior, as letting go of existing trade agreements will create new barriers to trade and migration between the UK and the other nations of the EU (Sampson, 2017). Forecasting agents and investors have even predicted that a mild recession will hit the UK after it leaves the EU and exits the single market.

3.1.1 Overview of Mobile Network Operators in the UK

As per statistical reports, the four leading mobile network operators (MNO) in the UK are Everything Everywhere (EE), O2, Vodafone and Three (3) (European Commission, 2016). According to a report by Statista (Figure 3.1), EE holds the biggest chunk of the market share, with 28%; followed by O2, with 26%, Vodafone with 21 % and Three 12% (O'Dea, 2019). Additionally, there are other small operators who are classified as mobile virtual network operators (MVNO). These are the smaller firms who only acquire rights from the MNOs to use their wireless network arrangements. Such operators use established infrastructures to provide their services to customers. EE was founded by Deutsche Telekom and Orange S.A., but was later bought by the BT Group. Under EE, the number of MVNOs are also increasing. At the

moment, EE owns around 553 retail stores and serves over 31 million connections across its mobile, fixed and wholesale networks (EE, 2017) while covering over 75% of the UK's landmass. The popular networks Orange™ and T-Mobile are also holdings of EE.

O2 (UK), formerly known as BT Cellnet, was obtained by the Spanish giant Telefónica in 2005. O2 owns 430 retail stores, including half of Tesco Mobile, and currently serves more than 25 million customers across the UK (O2, 2020). Along with 2G, 3G and 4G networks, O2 offers broadband services. According to Ofcom reports, O2 has the most satisfied consumers in the UK (Ofcom, 2016; O2, 2020). If prices are taken into account, O2 is expensive when compared to other competitors in the market; however, the excellence of its coverage means that users of other networks are tempted to switch to O2. O2 has been winning USwitch's Best Network Coverage Award for 3 years in a row since 2018 (O2, 2020).

Globally, Vodafone is one top mobile communications providers and is operational in 26 countries and in conglomerate with vonetworks in over 55 more (Vodafone, 2018). Vodafone serves more than 444 million customers globally, out of which 19.5 million are the UK customers. Vodafone employees more than 13000 people in the UK only (Vodafone, 2020).

After being launched on 3rd of March 2003 (03-03-03), Three UK's parent company Hutchison Whampoa planned to purchase the UK operations of O2 for £10.25 billion, which was rejected in 2016 by the EU Commission as a result of the effects the takeover would have on competition in the UK market (European Commission, 2016; BBC, 2016). The Commission stated that this acquisition would lead to lower choice for consumers and that it would also lead to a hike in prices. In terms of service users' satisfaction, Three's customers report lower than average satisfaction with their mobile phone reception (Ofcom, 2017).

Overall, the statistics show that mobile customers are more satisfied than broadband and landline customers and that 86% of customers are satisfied with their reception.

Figure 3. 1 UK MNOs' Market Share (adapted from Statista, 2020)

3.1.2 Evolution of Mobile Network Operators in the UK

As per a report released by Ofcom in 2010, the radiotelephone system run by British Telecom (BT) was the only two-way mobile communications service for public use in the UK before 1985 (Ofcom, 2010). In 1985, the Government approved two national operators; namely, Cellnet (Telecom Securicor Cellular Radio) and Racal-Vodafone, as cellular radio service providers in the band 890–905/935–950 MHz. Later, the band was extended to 872–888 /917–933 MHz to increase capacity in Central London. Later, on 18th February 1988, the first sample of digital mobile telephone system that had a capacity to function anywhere within the Europe was exhibited, the same year when the government released plans on cordless phones. The interest in this technology was quite significant for the time: Racal Vodafone alone received 250,000 subscribers within the span of three years (DTI, 1988), while the combined number of subscribers (end of year), when combined with Cellnet, reached 500,000—with coverage surpassing 90% of inhabited areas in the UK.

In 1989, DTI and the then Secretary of State for Trade and Industry, Lord Young, made an announcement regarding the need for more operators to provide 'phone on

the move' (cellular mobile services) and placed an open invitation for more companies to join personal communication networks' (PCNs) operator service (DTI, 1989). Gradually, efforts were made to improve signal and call reliability, and there was an upsurge in the number of operators.

In April 1994, Hutchison's Orange launched digital PCN services (Ofcom, 2010) and later in the year Cellnet and Vodafone also launched digital (GSM) services. In 1996, DTI and the Radiocommunications Agency together initiated a forum for mobile operators and manufacturers to build consensus towards vision for third generation systems called the UK Third Generation Mobile Group (UK3GMG), which was then followed by the UK Third Generation Advisory Group (UKTAG). Both forums presented a regulatory framework and an analysis on the spectrum available for UK Third Generation of mobile communication, which was later termed as Universal Mobile Telecommunication Services (UTMS) (DTI, 1997).

In 2000, the Radiocommunications Agency released 3G Licences to One 2 One Ltd (which became T-Mobile (UK) Ltd; now Everything Everywhere Ltd) and TIW Ltd (now Hutchison 3G UK Ltd), followed by BT3G Ltd (now Telefonica O2 UK Ltd). A few months later, Vodafone Ltd. and Orange received their 3G licenses. The signal spectrum moved to 4G in 2012 and EE became the UK's first main fourth generation (4G) mobile service provider. Ever since its launch was announced at the Mobile World Congress 2018, network providers around the world have been working on releasing 5G networks to their customers. 5G, which is the talk of the town, is the most awaited generation of wireless technology, and it is expected to support data speeds of up to 1Gbps. In May 2019, 5G officially launched in the UK, initially 5G plans were offered by EE and Vodafone only. Figure 3.2 reflects the evolution and generations of mobile technology.

Figure 3. 2 Generations of mobile technology, adapted from (Ofcom, 2018c, p.9)

The mobile network operator industry itself is subject to aggressive demands as a result of ever advancing technology, its amassed users' anticipations and the obligation to invest in new digital infrastructures. According to a press release by the House of Commons (Parliament, 2017), the industry is responding to these pressures by consolidating its presence across Europe with the aim of empowering operators to expand capacity, expand margins and invest more—of course. Currently, the two prevalent forms of mergers are 'mobile operator with mobile operator' or 'mobile operator with fixed-line broadband operator' mergers. A handful of mobile-to-mobile mergers were been approved by the European Commission and are now up and running (for example, Orange/Hutchison 3G in Austria and Telefonica Ireland/Hutchison 3G in Ireland), but some other merger requests were blocked. The Three and O2 merger in the UK was not approved on the presumption that the merger would lead to decrease the alternatives to consumers, which may also result in increased price. The section below is dedicated to explaining further the current situation of the MNOs in the UK and market dynamics.

3.2 Current Situation of MNOs and Market Dynamics

Customers can purchase mobile devices and network connections in two popular forms in the UK: prepaid and post-pay. As suggested by the name, the former involves buying credit to use phone and internet data in advance, while the latter involves entering into a contract with the network provider to use their network along with a selected handset in which a monthly contract fees covering the preceding month's usage is set in place. Prepaid is referred to as Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) and post-pay is better known to consumers as a monthly 'contract'.

As per a report by IBIS, the industry is dominated by four mobile network operators (MNOs), Three, Vodafone, EE and O2, which were anticipated to generate 90.4% of industry revenue in 2017–18 (IBIS, 2017). They are also known as the Big Four. Along with them, there are several other mobile virtual network operators who do not own their own networks but who work in collaboration with the Big Four's networks.

As per Ofcom (2020), mobile telephony services made £3.4bn in revenues on second quarter of 2019, which shows decline by £32m (0.9%) in comparison to the last year where the average revenue per subscriber was £13.52. It reflected that the pay as you go subscribers generated less revenue than the monthly pre-paying subscribers.

On a survey conducted by Ofcom (2017) to understand the service quality and service users satisfaction from their service providers they identified the customer reach out to their respective service providers. They identified number of reasons for customer complaints, mainly, the lack of service performance, billing issues and the dissatisfaction with customer service. It shows that the customers interact to their service providers in a search of solution. It also shows that service users follow up on customer service more than one-time s if they are unsatisfied or if their provlem is not solved on their first attempt.

Figure 3. 3 Reasons to complain about a service provider (Ofcom 2017, p.66)

3.2.1 Rise of MVNOs

Ofcom welcomed the support that mobile virtual network operators (MVNOs) could offer to consumers. MVNOs are service providers who provide retail mobile services without possessing any or all of the mobile set-up and ground infrastructures themselves; thus, they provide enhanced retail competition, although they do not have the similar capability to differentiate services that comes with control of a network. Ofcom grants licenses under the Wireless Telegraphy Act 2006 to the MNOs who control the networks and run the radio spectrum. It is mandatory for all the networks and service providers to conform to general authorisation policies. At the moment, there are 31 MVNOs, who have their own SIM cards and network codes belonging to them, and numerous light MVNOs (uSwitch, 2019); some have stronger commercial relationships with the host MNO while some are only limited to accessing host's network.

3.3 Overview of the UK MNOs

In the UK, buying a handset on a monthly contract or a pay-monthly service is very common, as it allows consumers to pay for an expensive handset in instalments. Service users are charged for handsets and a monthly air plan that includes voice call minutes, texts and internet data. Most network providers continue to charge their customers the initially contracted monthly fee even when the minimum contract period expires, which refers to the time by which the price of the handset has been paid off.

As reported by Ofcom (2017), approximately 1.5 million people are in such a vulnerable position; namely, one in which they keep paying an excessive amount by continuing to pay a monthly fee that also includes the cost of a mobile handset, regardless of the fact that the initial minimum contract period has already ended. In addition, Ofcom has reported that customers who purchase their handset along with the network's service can end up paying 34% more than what they are actually supposed to pay. Therefore, Ofcom has urged people to be aware of their mobile contract status and of the upgrade options that are available to them when their contract ends. The number clearly states the prevalence of hidden behaviours, which could be the result of MNOs hiding relevant information from customers while selling mobile plans. Failing to highlight or clearly discuss the terms regarding what happens at the end of the contracted period can make service users feel cheated or unfairly treated later on. This can result in severe consequences, such as their withdrawal from the network for good.

The world's inhabitants are inclined to be dependent on internet and mobile data. The majority (62%) of time spent on the internet was on mobile devices, and it was seen that only mobile advertising covered 45% of online advertising in 2017 (Ofcom, 2018a). Given the increasing use of data, combined with consumers' ever-increasing power in the relational exchange and their knowledge about marketing practices, this study provides even more significant managerial implications. Although the idea of dark side practices and consumers' perceptions of fairness were first questioned more than 15 years ago, the factors that customers use to decide whether or not a firm is acting fairly are still to be researched and understood (Boulding et al., 2005).

3.4 Overview of Online Communities and Social Media

Online communities, as a general term, refers to a group on any of the mainstream social media platforms that is created by a consumer or a brand itself with an objective of bringing like-minded customers or users together on the same platform in order to share their views, interests and feedback about the product or services offered by the brand. Brand communities were originally outlined by Muniz and O'Guinn (2001, p. 412) as being a "specialised, non-geographically bound community, based on a structured set of social relationships among admirers of a brand". More recently, they have been implemented as one of the major communication platforms, and they are

often integrated into a firm's marketing strategy or business model as a means of influencing their consumers' behaviour (Edvardsson, Tronvoll and Gruber, 2011). The use of social media platforms by brands is almost mandatory today, given the fact that the emergence and popularity of digital media has brought with it the possibility of constant communication. Due to the fact that such strategies are aimed at retaining the customer relationship, they are interrelated with the concept of social CRM. Social CRM entails hearing what customers have to say, analysing such conversations and formulating efficient marketing activities based on the notion of dual value creation.

According to a report published by Statista, there are 45 million active social media users in the UK in 2020, which is 66% of the total population of the UK (Johnson, 2020). Now that social media is so popular for personal use, businesses are integrating it as business tool and academics and researchers are embedding it as a research instrument. Research conducted over the internet ranges from seeking a qualitative understanding of experiences on a small scale to understanding the pattern of behaviours and their emergence on a large scale (Hina, 2017). This study is carried out by using online brand communities and social media platforms to explore the experiences of customers and identify particular phenomena.

In this study, the researcher collects data by observing service users on their respective MNOs' social media platform. The researcher has chosen Netnography, the observation of service user's comments, posts and general engagement in these online platforms as Netnography collects the rawest form of consumer experiences and perception about their service provider's activities that the service users perceive to be dark.

The researcher has outlined two objectives to fulfil through the quantitative study.

1. Understanding the service user's level of awareness about the dark side behaviours from their service providers.
2. Identifying what kind of activities do the service users perceive to be hidden and unfairly practiced by their service providers

3.5 Conceptual and Theoretical Framework of this Study

To address the research problems, the researcher implements a quantitative online survey in order to answer two research questions. The online survey is implemented primarily to understand service users' level of awareness of the dark side behaviours being practiced by their service providers. A lack of awareness and visibility of such dark and hidden activities is often the main factor that encourages practitioners to keep performing them. On the one hand, service providers may intentionally take advantage of service users' lack of awareness and try to abuse it as an opportunity to maximise profit. On the other hand, service users may not even realise that what firms are practicing are dark side behaviours that can destroy their service users' loyalty and damage the relationship as a whole. Thus, identifying service users' level of awareness is crucial.

In order to identify users' level of awareness, a questionnaire has been formulated in such a way that service users can provide answers regarding the activities that they perceive to be dark. The use of open-ended questions is aimed at obtaining more details on dark side behaviours, which will be validated through the findings of qualitative data collected through Netnography.

Figure 3. 4 Conceptual framework of the study based on perceptual process

The above figure shows the conceptual framework of this study based on the concept of perceptual process. The next section briefly explains the key used in the framework.

CRM activities: CRM activities refer to any actions carried out by a firm, i.e MNO in this study, that are associated with acquiring, developing, and maintaining a relationship with their customers, with an objective to enhance long term profitability. CRM activities can range from simply collecting customer data from customer touch points, deriving customer insights and tracking customer behaviours to social media interactions and engagements that may include pre-sale service encounters and/or after sales customer service. The combination of practices, strategies and technologies that MNOs use to analyze and manage customers are what the researcher is referring to as CRM activities in this study.

Consumer perception: Generally speaking, perception is the process of assigning meaning to what a person senses through their sensory receptors. Consumer perception is a process by which a consumer forms an attitude about a product, service, brand and a company's activities based on their individual bias, needs, knowledge and experience. Consumer / service users derive meaning from the company's values, advertisements, products, services, and so on, and incorporate this derived meaning into their purchase and post-purchase decision making. Additionally, external points of view and fellow consumers' word of mouth also play an important role in perceptions of a product or service these days. The current study focuses on service users' perceptions of MNOs' CRM activities and how these are manipulative, deceptive, unfair and/or how they go beyond the actual objective of CRM activities, i.e., to create value co-creation and achieve a win-win situation.

Dark side: The term 'dark side', as used in this research, does not include all the problems associated with service or product failures that lead to the destruction of the customer relationship. It rather refers to the intentional, manipulative, and exploitative behaviours of UK MNOs that are often undertaken in the name of CRM (Frow et al., 2015) with the aim of taking advantage of customers in an unfair way. The term also includes some activities that emerge as a result of negligence and a poor understanding of the holistic approach of CRM as a strategy.

Dark side behaviours/activities of CRM: Dark side behaviours can be described thus: “Instead of acting as partners engaged in mutually rewarding co-destiny relationships, too many marketers and consumers continue to be locked into mistrustful, adversarial relationships in which there is a constant tug-of-war to determine which side can benefit disproportionately and unfairly” (Sheth and Sisodia, 2006, p. 3). Service providers often find it profitable to confuse and mislead customers into making poor purchase decisions through the use of complicated and vague terms of sale. Likewise, they sometimes make sales using false advertising or misinformation with a malicious intent to lure and bind customers into contracts. Common practices include confusing usage rates on mobile phones, high penalties when customers exceed credit limits, overdrafts and payment deadlines or fall short of minimum balances in bank accounts (Frow et al., 2011, 2013). These examples are some of the dark side behaviours that are practiced intentionally. However, there are other activities, such as failing to train and educate customer service staff, the lack of strategic and departmental integration, failing to incorporate customer knowledge, a focus on data rather than customer insights and knowledge, and so on, which are examples of dark side activities that are the result of a poor understanding of the strategic focus of CRM and may lead to the inappropriate exploitation of customers, especially when service providers use intrusive technology (Frow et al., 2017). This study aims to explore the dark side of service providers’ behaviour in terms of the abuse of relationships created through poor customer management, both intentional and unintentional, although the study will not examine the classification of these activities.

Relationship instruments: Researchers have used the term ‘instrument’ to describe the elements that support the maintaining and reinforcing of firm–customer relationships. They are also the dynamics that firms implement to influence their existing and prospective customers. The same notion is described using the term relationship ‘tactics’ by most researchers, and it is also referred to using the term ‘CRM offerings’ by Nguyen (2009) in his research. Several elements have been acknowledged in the relationship marketing literature as helping to form and build a relationship, and they are often presented as key variables of relationship success; they include trust, commitment, satisfaction, uncertainty, dependence, fairness and symmetry (e.g., Smith et al., 1999; Britton and Rose, 2004). Similarly, several frameworks have been developed to identify the factors that influence relationships

and relationship marketing. One of them being the Relationship Marketing Tactics (RMT) framework by Peng and Wang (2006), the elements of which are crucial when it comes to understanding and analysing the gap in the current study.

Service users' behavioural actions: Customers are expected to be transparent with companies and are required to disclose personal information to their service providers (Liu et. al, 2015). In return, customers expect a proportional return from the relationship and some benefits in return for sharing their personal information. However, despite numerous opportunities to enhance transparency and information asymmetry, companies are often reluctant to disclose information and opt to control their online reputation (N'Goala, 2015; Parris et. al., 2016). When customers realise that they are being treated unfairly and are receiving the shorter end of the stick in the buyer–seller relationship, based on equity theory, customers with a grudge may end up ending their relationships with the business and/or seek retribution through negative word of mouth or revenge (e.g., Campbell, 1999; Ren and Quan, 2012). Some studies have highlighted that buyers who receive inadequate service seek revenge for their suffering and for getting a smaller slice of the pie in the buyer–seller relationship (e.g., Daunt and Harris, 2012). Furthermore, service users today are aware of their reach, as facilitated by the internet and digital platforms, so they often abuse the power they have when it comes to spreading negative word of mouth. This study aims at understanding and identifying the kind of activities or behaviours that service users practice against service providers when they realise that they are being treated unfairly by their MNO.

The detail framework of this study and the theoretical framework will be introduced in the section below.

Figure 3. 5 Detail framework of the study

Firstly, the researcher aims to understand the level of awareness amongst service users about the hidden and dark practices prevalent amongst MNOs. As per the contextual analysis of the industry, it is clear that MNOs in the UK are practicing some forms of dark behaviours to maximise their profits ignoring the relational aspect. After the dark sides are identified, this research will recommend a framework that enables practitioners to both address and eliminate these dark side practices.

While undertaking the literature review and evaluating established theories to identify the research problem of this study, the researcher identified a suitable framework that can be used to address service providers' use of the dark sides of CRM. The framework was developed by Payne and Frow (2005, 2013). The framework is based on the notion that there is a need to focus on key strategic processes in managing customer relationship's cross-functional conceptualisation of CRM. It identifies the components involved in each individual business process that can be address individual CRM activities. This process-based framework was developed specifically to address the dark side behaviours identified by the same group of researchers (Frow et. Al., 2011). Additionally, the limitation of the suggested framework is that it was formulated based on the findings of extant literature reviews and the perceptions of business practitioners; thus, it does not incorporate the perceptions of service users

at all. Therefore, researcher is implementing the work of Frow et. al. (2013), as a theoretical framework for this study.

Figure 3. 6 Theoretical framework of the study

3.6 Conclusion

Based on the literature review, it can be clearly seen that an extremely limited focus has been put on increasing the visibility of the dark side practices of CRM. Lack of awareness about dark practitioners not only encourages the practitioner to continue such behaviours but also flaws the perception towards CRM overall. It is important for future researchers to focus on this ignored aspect of CRM. This research, therefore, is a move towards increasing the visibility of one of the most important—and yet ignored—aspects of relationship marketing.

This research aims to add to the literature of dark sides, including causes and the consequences of dark CRM practices, more specifically focusing the latter. This study will identify the additional dark sides of CRM that are being practiced by MNOs in the UK. As reflected by the theoretical framework, the researcher will be identifying and expanding on the types of practices that Frow et. al. (2011)'s work has already identified. Frow and his fellow researchers identified dark behaviours purely based on available literature but the researcher identifying them based on the perceptions of service users and their experience.

The next chapter discusses the research methodology implemented in this study and justifies the research philosophy, research approach and instruments implemented to collect data. This research deploys a mixed method study in order to gain a detailed understanding both of what people say online but also to explore what these online activities mean within the context of people's everyday lives (Hampton et al., 2012).

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

Introduction

The manner in which a research study is undertaken is based on the research philosophy it follows, the research strategy used and the corresponding research instruments that are applied to achieve research objective(s), and to answer the research question. The aforementioned techniques as a whole are referred to as the research methodology; a term that is often used interchangeably with the term 'research method'. The research methodology reflects overall fundamentals of the study, based on which the researcher plans and executes a complete research study.

This chapter includes three broad sections: (1) the philosophical underpinnings of the research; (2) the research methods, which includes the research settings, research instrument and data collection methods, and; (3) data analysis, which comprises a discussion of the descriptive statistics and the analysis techniques implemented.

4.1 Philosophical Underpinnings of the Research

Philosophies, in research, refer to a researcher's assumptions in terms of what is significant to the study, what can be known, what research tools and designs are suitable for gaining the knowledge sought and what criterion should be considered to justify the quality of the research. Broadly speaking, it is a belief that guides how data on a particular (intended) phenomenon should be amassed, scrutinised and used. Research philosophies differ based on the purposes of the research and the methods implemented in order to achieve these objectives. For example, some researchers aim to test existing theories, while others try to define a complex situation and originate a new theory. Based on such purposes, the approach might be inductive or deductive; thus, the instrument used to collect data varies from study to study.

There is increasing complexity when undertaking research today and it is due to an incoherent categorisation of research philosophies, which include epistemology, ontology, axiology and doxology, and it includes—but is not limited to—debates on the quantitative and qualitative dichotomy, which is ultimately rooted to the respective philosophical stances. Researchers (Saunders et al., 2009; Ritchie and Lewis, 2003;

Guba, 1990) have used diverse explanations, categorisations, classifications paradigms and philosophies in relation to research methodology; however, they all have intersecting emphases and connotations.

The philosophical paradigms and the distinctions between them have been long disputed. For example, a study that takes a quantitative approach infers beliefs associated with the positivist paradigm, whilst a qualitative approach suggests the beliefs related to the constructivist paradigm. These relationships are, however, by no means permanent (Bryman, 2004).

The use of the term 'philosophy' is also slightly disputed. It is often interchangeably used with the terms 'philosophical paradigm' or 'paradigm' on its own, which Neuman defined as referring to a whole system of thinking (Neuman, 2011). The term was originally coined by Kaun in 1961. He defined it as "A set of values and techniques which is shared by members of a scientific community, which act as a guide or map, dictating the kinds of problems scientists should address and the types of explanations that are acceptable to them" (Kuhn, 1970, p. 175). Morgan (2007) also defined Kuhn's (1996) concept of paradigms as "shared beliefs within a community of researchers who share a consensus about which questions are most meaningful and which methods are most appropriate for answering those questions" (2007, p. 53).

In a simple delineation, paradigms are human constructions. This was outlined by Denzin, who said that they "define the shifting worldview of the research-as-bricoleur" (Denzin, 2010, p. 421). If we closely examine the debates and arguments about paradigms that have taken place in the past few decades (Denzin, 2010; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2003b), three major paradigm wars can be identified: a) the post-positivist war against positivism (1970–1990); the wars between competing post-positivist, constructivist and critical theory paradigms (1990–2005); and the most recent war between evidence-based methodologists and the mixed methods, interpretive and critical theory schools (since 2005). Each of these have raised questions about paradigm-based assumptions without realising that all of them have only reconfigured the relationship between the paradigm, methodology, epistemology and ethics.

It is already evident that the philosophical underpinnings of a research study can reveal a researcher's view on what constitutes knowledge; it also discloses the reasons behind the choice of a specific methodological approach. Therefore, it is a vital consideration for any study, as it explains and guides the researcher about overall progression of the research. It also explains what other methods are available in the market and why has the researcher has chosen specific method, strategy or the approach.

Philosophical paradigms are founded upon three perspectives, which are epistemology, ontology and methodology (Denzin and Lincoln, 2003; Punch, 2013).

- a. The epistemological perspective is concerned with the way knowledge is acquired or the approach towards the development of knowledge (Kuhn, 1996; Crotty, 1998). It is completely dependent upon the relationship between the researcher and the way that the researcher perceives a particular reality (Creswell, 2007; Gratton and Jones, 2004)
- b. Ontology is concerned with the nature of reality. Reality is perceived as being subjective and it depends upon how both researcher and the participants perceive it (Creswell, 2007; Punch, 1998). Saunders defined ontology as the interpretations on how knowledge is judged as being acceptable (Saunders et al., 2003)
- c. Methodology is related to the overall process and techniques through which the researcher acquires, understands and contributes to knowledge about the world (Creswell, 2003, 2007; Punch, 2013).

Based on the researcher's notions and thoughts about the development of knowledge, combined with the fact that the researcher found some of the pragmatist approaches to research to be very reasonable, pragmatism is a fundamental philosophy in this research study.

In order to explain the philosophical underpinnings of this research, the next section will discuss a number of concepts and assumptions that are made about this research that eventually led to the choice of certain methodological approaches. Ideas about the philosophy of knowledge must be combined with research strategies and implemented alongside research procedures and methods.

Despite the fact that they have such a fundamental influence, paradigms are almost 'hidden' in any research work; however, they must be stated as a result of the influence they have on the practice and execution of research (Creswell, 2009). The roots of the qualitative and quantitative approaches spread into several philosophical paradigms and particularly into positivism and post-positivism (Neuman, 2006; Cohen et al., 2007; Flick, 2007; Wisker, 2008; Collis and Hussey, 2009; Creswell, 2009; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Lincoln et al., 2011). More specifically, post-positivism is characterised by two sub-paradigms; interpretivism and critical theory, and realism; often regarded as bridge between positivism and post-positivism (Blumberg et al., 2011; Bellamy, 2012). Later, a different paradigm—known as pragmatism—originated.

4.1.1 Justification of pragmatism

Originally conceptualised, Positivism and Interpretivism are two most popular and distinct paradigms (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007; Morgan, 2007). The positivist view of a singular reality—implying that there is only one truth out there waiting to be discovered by objective means— underlines quantitative research methods. While interpretivists oppose the idea arguing that there is no such thing as a single objective reality and that subjective analysis is the only reasonable thing; rooting for qualitative research methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Despite today's significant advances in the fields of feminism, postmodernism, critical research and many more, these two paradigms still dominate methodological debates in the realm of research, and particularly in social sciences (Hughes and Sharrock, 2007; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009).

Pragmatism acts as a new paradigm that can replace an older way of thinking about the differences between approaches to research. Pragmatism provides researchers with a sweeping exit from age-old philosophical disagreements regarding the nature of reality and the possibility for truth. As stated by Hall, pragmatism provides “an alternative epistemological paradigm” (2013, p. 19). In Morgan's recent work on pragmatism, he mentioned pragmatism as not just another substitute that disputes on the nature of reality(Morgan, 2014).

Pragmatism has often been regarded as the philosophical stance that is best suited to the mixed methods approach; however, there have been claims and evidence of the fact that mixed method studies are being conducted without explicitly or formally acknowledging that the practice relates to the mixed methods approach or its practical and philosophical premises (Bryman, 2006; Gorard and Taylor, 2004). Pragmatism was originated post-purist paradigm war, when researchers realised that each preferred philosophical paradigm were asserted around ontology, epistemology, methodology, and ethics, the inventor Khun essentially expressed a preference for a version of research paradigms that was much rooted in research practice and research communities (Morgan, 2007).

Morgan's argument states that pragmatism emphasises the creation of "shared meanings and joint action" (2007, p. 67) and has presented pragmatism as being a complementary approach. He highlights the fact that qualitative and quantitative approaches can be collective and that they complement the advantages and disadvantages present within each. Accepting the 'complementarity' of pragmatism paradigm, Arnon and Reichel (2009) undertook a study regarding the perceptions of a good teacher across different genders and ethnicities among Israeli citizens. A concurrent parallel design was implemented; namely, an open-ended telephone interview that was followed by a quantitative survey. These separate sets of data were then individually analysed and integrated via two methods: triangulation and 'quantising' the qualitative codes for statistical analysis (p. 182). Although they experienced dissonance in the data integration phase, their study emphasised the importance of the pragmatic perspective and the shared meanings that were created as a result of the integration of two methods. Likewise, such studies also nullify the long discussed dichotomy between "complete objectivity" and "complete subjectivity" (Morgan, 2007, p. 71).

4.2 The Mixed Methods Approach

While the philosophical stance is important in understanding the choice of a research approach, other factors may also play a role in the selection of methods that are used in a particular research study. Scholars have long advocated that the adoption of a methodological approach—such as a qualitative, quantitative or mixed method—

depends on the purpose of the study, the research questions, the way in which questions are asked (Punch, 2013) and an understanding of the paradigm and nature of the knowledge that are embedded in the study (Baxter et al., 2002).

When there were two dominating research orientations, mixed methods research was conceptualised as a challenge to validate or “legitimate” the use of multiple approaches (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p. 14) in answering research questions over the restrictions or bound on researchers’ choices created by qualitative or quantitative purists. It is both inclusive, expansive and complementary, and it allows researchers to take a freer approach to method selection, thinking about and conducting research; the mixed methods research design has been defined as an approach with philosophical assumptions as well as a method of inquiry (Plano Clark, 2011).

Mixed methods research (MMR) is often referred to as “the third methodological movement” and has become increasingly popular amongst practitioners and academics over the past 10 years. Described as a “quiet” revolution (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003), the mixed methodological approach “as a method...focuses on collecting, analysing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study or series of studies. Its central premise is that the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches, in combination, provides a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone” (Johnson et al., 2007, p. 123). Historically, the need of combining qualitative and quantitative methods suggested a few decades ago. Jick suggested that “qualitative and quantitative methods should be viewed as complementary rather than as rival camps” (Jick, 1983, p. 135).

The predominant method in this particular research study is the qualitative method, as the researcher aims to understand the perceptions of service users of service providers’ behaviours/activities which is served better by a qualitative method than a quantitative one. A quantitative method of data collection, an online survey, is subsequently applied to enhance the quality of the findings.

Qualitative or quantitative researchers need to understand that the purpose of mixed methods research is not to supersede either approach; rather, it aims to extract the

strengths of these approaches and to reduce potential weaknesses (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Saunders and his fellow researchers also contributed to the dialogue about why it is high time for mixed methods to be accepted as a new approach. This is where pragmatism, as a philosophy, plays a role. In relation to the paradigm war, pragmatism offers numerous ways by which to channel the dichotomies that exist in mixed methods. Pragmatism breaks down the barriers between the positivist and constructivist ways of thinking in order to look at what is meaningful from both perspectives (Biesta, 2010). There are some research that have been undertaken to highlight the concept of pragmatism in relation to mixed methods research (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Maxcy, 2003; Morgan, 2007; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2009; Hall, 2013; Greene and Hall, 2010); however, a justification of its relevance is still very limited.

The nature of reality in mixed methods research can be singular or multiple, as the researcher can pool both deductive and inductive thinking to embody compound perspectives of reality (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). If viewed epistemologically, the major significance of pragmatism is its practicality and space for rationality, as the researcher combines the best alternatives with regard to approaches and methods. Similarly, when it comes to addressing the research problem, the researcher's data collection process is entirely based on what works, unlike in post-positivism, where the concept of neutrality and objectivism is deemed as being crucial to data collection (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007).

Axiology, another element of research that creates a divide between researchers, refers to the role of values in shaping research. Pragmatists operate from both objective and subjective points of views, letting research questions dictate the methods, data sources and data type (McInerney, D., Walker, R. and Liem, G. (2011). Accepting values is a crucial part of this research process, however, with reflexively well considered because of their influence on the overall conduct and outcome of research. In pragmatism, researchers allow both biased and unbiased perspectives and they acknowledge how objective and subjective knowledge together can add value to the research (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Methodologically speaking, data from two different strands (QUAL and QUAN) are collected and mixed (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010); this technique enriches the

research findings. Finally, in terms of the language used and the presentation of the research findings, pragmatism allows for both formal and informal rhetoric to be used (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). Rhetoric is important as it reflects how the researcher shares and communicates their knowledge, the researcher in this study uses the best explanation that makes sense within researcher's own value system.

Mixed methods research methodologists have argued that there is a need to acknowledge the ideologies and conceptualisations of two types of studies: 1) studies that implement two forms of data without thoughtful integration, and 2) studies that mix unlike forms of data efficiently; understanding the difference between these is crucial (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2009). Research that implements the former type is simply a compilation of methods. Strong mixed methods research not only uses more than one method to solve a problem; it also clarifies on data integration including the time invested and priority given to one stream of data (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

Literature on MMR is still very limited on business research, predominantly because of the historic practice of preferring quantitative research in business (Hunt, 1994), and the lack of effort from scholars in learning two approaches collectively. Woodside brought up another reason, as trend for academics and researchers have tendency to implement the tools based on convenience, although at times the use of those chosen method is "highly inappropriate" (Woodside, 2010, p. 66). It is imperative for the researcher justify the suitability of their methodological preferences, the mix of designs they are implementing and, in parallel, anticipate the challenges that might arise that are associated with each choice.

4.2.1 Mixed Methods: Terminology

The terminologies used in mixed methods design and their implementation been quite chaotic. Originally developed by Morse (1991), and refined in 2003, the MMR notation system is still used in mixed methods research. The Morse notation system identifies that the following aspects are part of mixed methods research:

- a. Research orientation: whether the research is qualitatively (QUAL) or quantitatively (QUAN) oriented;

- b. Dominance: whether the QUAL and QUAN aspect has a stronger role or dominance; and
- c. Timing: if the studies are undertaken simultaneously or sequentially.

Morse identified two types of mixed methods designs; namely, simultaneous design and sequential design. Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009), however, recommended that researchers should use the term 'parallel mixed designs' instead of 'simultaneous designs', as they argued that it is more inclusive and explicit. A parallel mixed methods design permits researcher to collect data (QUAL and QUAN) at the same time or at marginally different times, as the collection of two types of data at exactly the same time not be practically possible for one person. This type of design was further expanded by Cresswell and Clarke (2011) with the introduction of embedded design. Types of mixed method designs will be elaborated in later section.

4.2.2 Mixed Methods Design

Methodologists have identified and used several types of mixed methods design. Harrison's study on major mixed methods design types (Harrison, 2013) examined the use of mixed methods research designs, and it was published in the *Journal of Business Research*. In his analysis of 2,072 articles published between 1990 and 2010 in the *Journal of Business Research*, he found that 17 mixed method studies implemented data collection procedures sequentially (68%), six implemented them concurrently (24%) and two combined both sequential and concurrent procedures (8%). In the same study, he identified the fact that business scholars were recognising the benefits of using mixing qualitative and quantitative research simultaneously but equally lacking the knowledge on demonstration of the mixed method literature or procedures; therefore, directed future researchers to seriously consider the need.

Amid an absence of an acknowledged taxonomy or distinct typology of mixed methods sampling, Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) discussed some strategies for mixed methods sampling designs by implementing the viewpoints of both probability and purposive sampling. Their outlined typology includes (a) basic, (b) sequential, (c) parallel, (d) multilevel, and (e) multiple mixed methods sampling strategies.

Later, Harrison identified some types of mixed methods design, as can be seen in the table below.

Design type	Variants	Timing	Weighting	Mixing	Notation
Convergent	• Parallel database	Concurrent: quantitative and qualitative at the same time	Usually equal	Merging the data during the interpretation or analysis	QUAN + QUAL
Embedded	• Embedded experimental • Embedded correlation ◆ <i>Embedded methodology</i>	Concurrent or sequential	Unequal	Embed one type of data within a larger design using the other type of data	QUAN (qual) or QUAL (quan)
Explanatory	• Follow-up explanations	Sequential: quantitative followed by a qualitative	Usually quantitative	Connect the data between the two phases	QUAN → qual
Exploratory	• Instrument development • Theory development	Sequential: qualitative followed by a quantitative	Usually qualitative	Connect the data between the two phases	QUAL → quan

Table 4. 1 Types of mixed methods design (adapted from Harrison, 2013, p. 2156)

In this particular study, the data are analysed, and findings are generated from each strand individually before being mixed in the discussion stage. If we refer to the table above, we can see that the research design implemented in this research is referred to as convergent design; here, the researcher collects both qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously, studies both data strings individually and then mixes the databases by merging the data (Creswell and Clark, 2011). The timing of the data collection, however, is concurrent. This allows the researcher to triangulate the results from the separate QUAN and QUAL components of their research, thereby allowing them to “confirm, cross-validate, or corroborate findings within a single study” (Creswell et al., 2003, p. 229).

As mentioned earlier, a researcher will use mixed methods research depending on the nature of the research question under study. In this research, the researcher implements a quantitative online survey in order to identify service user’s level awareness about the hidden behaviour being practiced by their service providers. Questions will be directed towards finding out whether service users have ever identified any kinds of behaviours that they think are being undertaken in a hidden or concealed way by service providers.

Based on how the typology has been defined, there is slight confusion regarding whether this research implements a concurrent convergent design or embedded design. Firstly, the samples/respondents for the online survey (QUAL) data are selected based on the observations made through Netnography, which is one of the major qualitative tools. On the other hand, data are analysed separately as individual

strands. The data come together only when the results are interpreted, with each type adding to the validity of the other results. However, based on Harrison's analysis (2013), embedded designs are employed when researchers have different questions that require different types of data while concurrent designs are used when the researcher feels that there is equal value for collecting and analysing both quantitative and qualitative data to understand the problem. He has also related choice of design with researcher's skills and resources involved on collecting data. Creswell and Clark (2011) identified some conditions in which embedded designs could be successful, such as when utilised under the following conditions: when researchers have little prior experience of the supplemental method or when researchers do not have adequate resources to place an equal emphasis on both types of data).

There are some examples where researchers have used an embedded method by implementing Netnography as a major methodological tool. Chan and Li (2010) and Fong and Burton (2008) both used an embedded design in their respective studies; the former study had a qualitative data dominance while the latter incorporated equal weights of qualitative and quantitative data. These studies reflect the fact that researchers are positively inclined towards using Netnography, and particularly in consumer research.

Over the time, several methodologists have also criticised the use of mixed methods designs. Freshwater (2007) criticises the mixed methods research approach as a whole because of its desire for certainty, overemphasis on completeness and, mostly, as a result of the fact that the MRR literature is dependent on the research literature of quantitative and qualitative methods. This therefore demands the need for MMR to be theorised the way quantitative and qualitative research are individually theorised. As suggested by Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004, p. 23) qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods are "superior under different circumstances"—the only thing to be considered by researchers is establishing knowledge with regard to how to use different approaches based on their research problems.

4.3 Constructing a Mixed Methods Design

In relation to the question of how research designs are actually defined, there are three factors that have been highlighted in a recent study of the construction of mixed

methods research design (Schoonboon and Johnson, 2017). This section highlights that theoretical drive, timing and point of integration are dimensions of mixed methods design; however, theoretical drive has been criticised as much as it has been praised.

a. Theoretical Drive

Theoretical drive refers to whether a study is qualitatively driven or quantitatively driven, which is utterly defined by whether the research aims to explore and describe a phenomenon or whether the researcher is trying to test a hypothesis. A qualitatively-driven study, by nature, embeds an inductive approach, while a quantitatively-driven study suggests a deductive approach. In their study of mixed method, Morse and Niehaus (2009) divided components of mixed data. The decisive components are called core component while the supporting component or set of data is called supplement component. They also invented a notation system wherein the core component is written in capitals whilst the supporting component is written in lower case. For example, if the weight of qualitative data in the study is higher it will be written as QUAL → quan design.

Morse and Niehaus's theory was criticised for not explicitly mentioning the of the core component and supplemental component. Moreover, they were ignorant with regard to the possibility of equal status mixed methods research, in which both the qualitative and quantitative components are of equal value and weight; this same criticism applies to Morgan's (2014) set of designs. Greene (2015) through his recent study stated that by successfully conducting an equal-status study, the researcher authenticates the mix of philosophy.

b. Timing

The second dimension of mixed methods design is its timing or sequence, which refers to the manner or order in which two data strands have been structured and used, whether qualitative inquiries are made first and followed by quantitative inquiries, or vice versa; timing, however, depends on the design type selected (Harrison, 2013). If one type of data is collected first and followed by another type, then it is called sequential design. However, some researchers collect both types of data simultaneously, which is called concurrent design.

According to Harrison's study (Harrison, 2013), convergent designs employ concurrent data collection procedures, explanatory and exploratory designs employ sequential data collection and embedded designs employ either sequential or concurrent data collection procedures.

c. Point of Integration

Aside from theoretical drive and the sequence of data collection, the point of integration also plays an equal role in designing or implementing an effective mixed method research.

In this research project, the mix occurs in one or all methodological stages. The researcher's Netnographic observations will be a major basis by which to select sample participants for the quantitative surveys. The point of inference, as defined by Morse and Niehaus (2009), can occur at any stage including, but not limited to, the point of methodological design, data collection, analysis and interpretation (Cresswell and Clark, 2011; Teddie and Tashakkori, 2009).

After considering all the elements discussed above, the researcher has constructed a framework that reflects the overall progression of the research in a nutshell. Beginning with an observation of each of the four MNOs' dedicated Facebook pages, the researcher will identify purposeful samples for both the qualitative and quantitative samples. In terms of the qualitative strand, most researchers use purposeful sampling strategies in order to gain rich data. The researcher will collect data from interactions that take place via posts, reviews and comments made on the online platforms of the MNOs. Likewise, regarding QUAN strand, the researcher will also post the online survey on MNOs Facebook page. The two sets of data are then analysed and mixed in the interpretation stage. This reflects the fact that the mix can occur at any stage of the research.

Figure 4. 1 Research design of the study, Created by the author

Once the design is defined or constructed, the researcher builds an appropriate sampling strategy that is then followed by the identification of appropriate data collection methods.

4.3.1 Sampling in Mixed Methods Design

Sampling is the process of choosing “a portion, piece, or segment that is representative of a whole” (sample, n.d). In any form of research, whether quantitative or qualitative, a researcher agrees on the number of participants to include, which is technically referred to as the sample size, and, accordingly, the process of selecting the samples is also clearly defined. Every procedure followed while undertaking research is aligned with and defined by the research question and the overall aim of the research.

Mixed methods sampling can be considered as both opportunity and challenge, as it requires an understanding and knowledge of the sampling strategies that are used in both QUAN and QUAL research. This is a challenge as two form of data collection demands a lot of effort and it is time-consuming.

Despite the recent popularity of mixed methods research in the research community, very little attention has been paid to sampling in mixed methods research. As illustrated in the work of Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2014), the position of sampling in mixed methods research remains underdeveloped, with very limited publications to date (these include Collins, 2010; Collins and Onwuegbuzie, 2013; Collins et al., 2006a, 2007; Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007, 2014; Teddlie and Yu, 2007).

In the sampling literature, random sampling is often presented as belonging to the quantitative paradigm, while non-random sampling methods are presented as belonging to the qualitative paradigm. This is a false representation: random and non-random sampling can be applied in both quantitative and qualitative studies (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005). Similarly, there is another misleading area in the literature in terms of sample size, where it is argued that small samples are correlated with qualitative research and larger samples are correlated with quantitative studies. Onwuegbuzie and Collins claim that such a representation is too simplistic and thereby misrepresenting (2007).

Some methodology experts have created guidelines regarding the selection of samples in qualitative studies that are based on the selected research design (e.g., case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory), sampling design (i.e., subgroup sampling design, nested sampling design) or data collection procedure (i.e., interview, focus group).

While defining samples for QUAN data, researchers tend to obtain samples that represent the whole population, unlike in QUAL data, where the researcher looks for samples that provide information or a 'thick description', as it is termed by Geertz (1973). Therefore, a sample for a mixed methods design happens to be representative of the population as well as being rich in information.

The sampling tactics used for quantitative methods in a mixed methods design are well-established and based on probability theory, unlike those used for qualitative methods, which are less obvious and significantly less clear. The samples for qualitative studies are generally assumed to be selected purposefully to rich information (Patton, 2015), however criticisms have been made for lacking guidelines. This study follows purposeful sampling to ensure that the researcher identifies and selects the information-rich cases as directed by Patton (2015). The first rule of thumb for purposeful sampling is the researchers' confidence in potential participants' knowledge of the subject matter. On top of their knowledge about a particular phenomenon, in order for a qualitative inquiry or interview to be effective, the participant must "have the necessary experiences or information, be willing to participate and have available time and be articulate, expressive and reflective"

(Morse, 2016, p. 64). However, the lack of literature in regard to guidelines of purposeful sampling confused the researcher, on what forms of purposeful sampling are suitable for their studies (Palinkas et al., 2015).

For this study, the researcher followed Cherif and Miled's (2013) community selection process that follows two stages, firstly determining the research questions and secondly, finding the most suitable forums or communities to answer them. When choosing the online platforms for Netnography, namely, the researcher ensure the criteria referred by Kozinets (2010, p. 89) to make sure they are relevant, active, interactive, substantial, heterogeneous, and data-rich.

4.4 Data Collection in Mixed Methods Research

Data collection strategies include, but are not limited to, observation, unobtrusive methods—including the study of documents, artefacts, photographs, and so on—focus groups, interviews, questionnaires and any other tests (Johnson and Turner, 2003).

The data collection in this study was started after the researcher received approval from the ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland. An ethics committee can take varying amounts of time to approve an ethics request depending upon the subject, nature of the research and the types of target participants. For example, if a study involves vulnerable segments of the population, then the ethics committee may request extra documentation in addition to what has been already submitted and that may take extra time to acquire, submit and gain approval.

Credible data from two different strands will define the overall quality of the data in a mixed methods study. Yet again, there is a very limited discussion on what represents or defines the quality of data in mixed methods research. Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) illustrated that QUAN researchers “evaluate (or often fail to evaluate) their data quality in terms of data/measurement validity (whether the data represent the constructs they were assumed to capture) and data/measurement reliability (whether the data consistently and accurately represent the constructs under examination)” (p. 209). On the other hand, QUAL researchers demonstrate the validity of their data through its trustworthiness and credibility.

In order to ensure the trustworthiness of the study, it is necessary for a researcher to use a reflective journal. This is the process of developing a separate diary where the researcher records information about themselves and their use of 'self' as an instrument (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). In a consumer research, reflectivity and introspection, both the researcher and the informants' inner voices, is said to play imperative role within the whole research process (Takhar-Lail and Chitakunye, 2015). Reflexivity also contributes to the reduction and elimination of personal biases. In this study, the researcher completed a diary in which they could note any significant or unexpected happenings the occurred during the online observation.

4.4.1 Instruments of Data Collection

After the designs and strategies to be used in a research study have been considered, data collection tools/instruments must be decided upon. For this study, given the fact that it is a mixed methods study in which various tools are combined to enrich the study, the researcher included one or more QUAN and QUAL instruments. In this study, the researcher has chosen Netnography as an instrument for qualitative data collection; this is a process in which the researcher observes the experiences, feedback and complaints shared by service users in the online community of their respective service providers. Simultaneously, the researcher also implemented an online survey as a quantitative tool. These will be brought together to triangulate and enhance the results. The table below shows the details on combination of online platforms used to collect data.

MNO	QUALITATIVE DATA	QUANTITATIVE DATA
EE	Twitter and Facebook page	Facebook page
O2	Twitter and Community Forum	Community Forum
Vodafone	Twitter and Facebook page	Facebook page
Three	Twitter and Facebook page	Facebook page

Table 4. 2 Details of online platforms used for data collection

4.4.2 Justification of the use of Netnography

Observation is one of the most popular QUAL data collection tools in social science. Ethnography is a process in which participants are observed in natural settings and unadulterated data are gathered and recorded; nowadays, ethnographic approaches are even more powerful as a result of the fact that they have been galvanised by online tools and environment (Cooke, 2008). Considered in relation to feasibility and efficiency, the internet is now a crucial setting for research. Its ease of use, popularity and effectiveness means that individuals are relatively easier to access online than they are in real life.

Netnography is an ethnographic study that takes place online or in a digital location. Kozinets coined and defined Netnography as being a form of ethnographic research that embraces participant-observational tactics and considers virtual platforms and online interactions as part of its fieldwork (2015). Kozinets described it as a “new qualitative research methodology that adapts ethnographic research techniques to the study of cultures and communities emerging through electronic networks.” (2002, p. 62), and labelled the researcher or the observer as “a specialized lurker”. In a study in which methodological terminology was reviewed, Netnography was defined as ‘virtual ethnography’ (Watson et. al, 2008). It was further rephrased as ‘ethnography for the internet’ (Hine, 2015), ‘connective ethnography’ (Dirksen, Huizing and Smit, 2010) and ‘Netnography’ (Kozinets, 1998, 2010, 2018). More explanatory collective terms have also been used, such as ‘computer-assisted webnography’ (Horster and Gottschalk, 2012) and ‘Netnographic grounded theory’ (Healy and McDonagh, 2013).

As was seen in the discussion of the research design framework, Netnography plays a crucial role in both the quantitative and qualitative strands of this research, as Netnography helps the researcher to gather insights into service users’ needs and desires, their preferences, symbolic meanings and much more, as Reid suggested customers are more expressive online than in real life(1996). Online settings include, but are not limited to, blogs, communities, social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, fan accounts, online forums, apps, dedicated consumer feedback forums, and so on. While there are studies that have been undertaken by analysing multiple online communities in parallel, this particular research is limited to

the combination of two platforms belonging to each MNO; namely, their official Facebook page and their Twitter page. This is because time was a major constraint in this research. The researcher could not use the same combination of platforms for all the MNOs because not all the operators implement social platforms in a same way. For example, O2 does not let its followers create original posts on its Facebook page, while their online community forum is very active. The researcher selected the most interactive and responsive platform to ensure the data collected are both purposive and rich.

Qualitative research methodologies in the online environment have been described as “sitting within a broader methodological context of online or virtual ethnography which comprise approaches for conducting ethnographic studies of online communities and groups” (Wiles, Bengry-Howell, Crow and Nind, 2013, p. 20). Gilchrist and Ravenscroft (2011) studied consumer behaviour using netnography, which was viewed as being a new research method at the time. Although it has been noticeably practiced in various disciplines and research settings, Netography’s use in management and business research is still very undeveloped in terms of practice. Over the time, the ability to combine Netnography with other research methodologies has also been established.

The researcher has chosen Netnography as a major research tool in this study; it is not just a data collection method but can also serve as a crucial instrument for identifying samples. For example, if the researcher was to combine observation data with interview, the researcher would identify the most informative possible participant through observation and approach them accordingly. The objective of this research is to understand the perceptions of service users analysing their experiences, and the digital social storylines are understood to be the best ones as consumers are said to be honest when it comes to sharing their opinions on brand communities. Word of mouth, complaints and honest feedback on online communities are therefore assets that adds on value co-creation for business.

According to Cherif and Miled (2013, p. 14), businesses are transferring their attention towards a “participative model based on interaction between brands and customers”. Consumers or service users are no longer patrons only and their experience counts as a real value. To capitalise on the benefits of value co-creation, companies now

invest in online platforms and social networking pages dedicated to their brands. Turning again to talk about this study, MNOs have official social media pages with numerous followers. They also have Twitter and community forums particularly created for customer support purposes. These not only contain frequently asked questions but also provide opportunities for interaction amongst consumers who share similar problems.

As a research method, Netnography mines data from compound sources, including participant observations, conversation threads and dialogues with relevant participants (Füller et al., 2007). Similarly, Brodie et al. (2013) define netnography as including both the observation of communication in an online community and qualitative in-depth interviews with community members—as do Cherif and Miled (2013) and De Valck et al. (2009). Chua and Banerjee (2013) combined qualitative case studies and netnographic methods to analyse how social media was used among customers of Starbucks coffee shops, whereas Borghini et al. (2010, p. 115) characterised their study of street art as a being comprised of “multisite ethnography and netnography.” Fisher and Smith (2011) combined ethnographic, videographic and netnographic research methods with participant interviews to “capture important aspects of consumer and community co-creation” (p. 335).

Researchers often use interviews when it comes to understanding customers' perception. Interviews are believed to widen the understanding of investigated phenomena, as it is considered to be more realistic and less structured data collection technique (Alshenqeeti, 2014). However, researchers have argued that observation can guarantee an unfiltered and richer perspective beyond that which an interview can provide. This is because interviews have a possibility of the interviewee modifying their response when they are put in spot, such lack of honesty can affect the overall findings of the study.

4.4.3 Justification of the use of an online survey

Emergence and progression on how the internet is being used today, it is a fantastic place for the researchers to collect data. The pace of virtual communities' development enables hundreds of thousands of people to frequently participate in discussions about

almost every conceivable issue. Online survey methodologies are mainly advantageous for the convenience and time and cost-effectiveness that they offer (Denissen et al., 2010).

Online surveys involve collecting answers to a structured set of questions, which are often presented on a web-based platform. There are typically two forms of online survey based on how they are distributed to the participants. Firstly, an e-mail-based surveys in which the researcher shares survey questionnaire to the defined samples of participants through participant's email. Secondly, an Web-based survey in which the questionnaire is created on the host's platform and the participant's responses gets collected on host's server (Hoonakker & Carayon, 2009). In this study, the researcher implemented second method to distribute survey, using 'Survey Monkey' a platform to conduct an online survey.

Invitations to take part in the survey may be posted to a known population; for example, via a mailing list, or they may be publicised more widely; for example, via social networking sites, to an undetermined population of potential participants. The researcher posted the survey in MNOs Facebook pages and on an online forum, only for O2, as it didn't allow posting on it's Facebook at the time when the researcher was collecting data.

Surveys allow for a structured approach to be taken to exploring participants' experiences and understanding however before employing a survey, the researcher needs to confirm the questions like, how does my population of interest experience and understand my topic of interest?, What socio-demographic factors account for differences?

Although online survey has been one of the most popular means of collecting data, there are significant challenges an online survey holds. Firstly, generalisability can be problematic for online surveys in cases where the underlying population is unknown: it can be unclear who saw the survey invitation, and response biases are thus hard to determine. Secondly, the response rate is one of the major challenges on employing an online survey (Denissen et al., 2010). Third weakness is that some of the online survey hosts can be expensive based on the analytical features they offer.

The anonymity of online surveys however adds confidence to participants while researchers can also avoid biasness which adds on credibility of research. Online research allows participants to feel increased comfort and independence and decreased hesitance in participating, knowing that their contributions will remain confidential and that they have the ability to complete the survey privately (McDermott & Roen, 2012; Willis, 2011).

4.5 Data Analysis

Mixed methods data analysis entails knowledge of both QUAL and QUAN data analysis strategies. QUAL data analysis is iterative in nature and can start shortly after data collection begins. On the contrary, QUAN data analysis can start only when the set of data has been collected in full.

With regard to QUAL data analysis, there are several software programs available in the market that assist QUAL data analysis and with both time and innovation the quality and proficiency of such software is steadily improving; thus making the management and organisation of data even more efficient (Bringer, Johnston and Brackenridge, 2006). Methodologists have advised researchers to thoroughly analyse the advantages and disadvantages of each form of software and to pick the one that permits rigorous QUAL data analysis (Auld et al., 2007; Banner and Albarran, 2009). On the other hand, statistical techniques can be used to analyse QUAN data and there are also several QUAN analysis software packages available.

For the data analysis, the researcher uses NVivo for QUAL data analysis, while the QUAN data will be analysed using SPSS. IBM SPSS is one of the most intelligent and trusted analysis tools used in research. While many researchers still prefer to use Microsoft Excel to analyse QUAN data, SPSS stands miles ahead in terms of its benefits—such as its ability to conduct RFM analysis, easily identify groups, find unusual data, prepare and transform data, and so on. The researcher uses SPSS to examine the descriptive data in this study.

When it comes to identifying the dark side behaviours being practiced by MNOs, thematic analysis is the optimum analytical method; this is because the research aims

to develop patterns based on the experiences shared by service users. Thematic analysis is one of the most prominent and widely-used methods in qualitative research, as it underlines the importance of categorising, evaluating and constructing meanings around the qualitative data collected through methods like interviews, observations, focus groups, and so on. This study includes data collected via observation over the internet. Deriving a meaningful pattern involves classifying and categorising the data; a process that is often known as coding. Coding in thematic analysis is the most important phase.

Even though researchers like Braun and Clarke (2006) have outlined the six-phase method of thematic analysis, in practice, it is a repetitive and reflective process. Thematic analysis builds and comes in shape over time that involves a continuous move back and forth between the data set. When conducting this research, the processes of data collection, analysis and interpretation were largely interrelated and were often carried out simultaneously (Creswell, 2007).

The next section provides justification on the dependability and reliability of the research methods used in this research.

4.5.1 Thematic Analysis, Credibility and Trustworthiness

The principle behind qualitative research is to comprehend and draw patterns through the analysis of words used by a participant or a responder, by connecting the dots and creating a representative figure without compromising its richness and dimensionality. Similar to quantitative study, the purpose of qualitative research is to answer research questions through the development of a theory or by expanding or disproving an existing theory.

The human emotions, perspectives and subjectivity involved, in terms of both researchers and participants, is what often causes the trustworthiness and reliability of qualitative research to be questioned; however, qualitative researchers find the same elements to be crucial in relation to the findings of the research. Qualitative researchers are encouraged to involve with the data and analysis with their honest

perspectives, pre-existing thoughts and beliefs while developing theories (Starks and Trinidad, 2007). When the researcher engages with the qualitative data, any theoretical and reflective thoughts that come up ought to be recorded, including ethical issues and their understandings associated with the research area (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Such documentation helps to enrich the trustworthiness of the findings of the study.

When conducting qualitative data analysis using a thematic analysis method, the researcher is a major tool for analysis, as they make judgments about categorising, coding and theming the data (Starks and Trinidad, 2007). Due to the nature of qualitative research and its flexibility, each researcher may use their own techniques for running, recording and assessing their data analysis processes, but it is also the individual researcher's responsibility to ensure the thoroughness and trustworthiness of this process. This involves the transparent explanation of the overall process involved in data collection and analysis.

A thorough thematic analysis produces reliable and intuitive findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006); however, there have been arguments around how a researcher can apply this method to ensure reliability. Often, criticisms of thematic analysis as a method revolve around the researcher's failure to establish the details of how data have been analysed. Disclosing such details about what the data analysis process involves is important in order to ensure the credibility of the research (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2007).

Further, with regard to trustworthiness in qualitative research, the illustration prepared by Nowell et al. (2017, p. 4), which is based on the original criteria set up by Lincoln and Guba (1985), sums up the whole picture as to how each phase involved within the thematic analysis adds to the trustworthiness of a research project both in relation to the methodology itself and the findings of the study.

Phase 1: Familiarising oneself with the data

The observation data was initially collected in Excel, where each spread was dedicated to each MNO. The columns included the date the comments were made, a link to the comments and the comments themselves. To avoid research bias, the

researcher avoided recording the gender of participants. The researcher used Excel spreadsheets to record all the raw observation data and organise the progress of the data collection. The Excel documents were later converted into a format (PDF) that could be imported into NVivo. While documenting and recording the data, the researcher also kept notes of any related information in the form of field notes. These not only included notes on possible themes or subthemes, theories or problems, but also the researcher's insights with regard to the methodology.

Phase 2: Generating initial codes

As explained by Braun and Clarke (2006), by the end of the first phase, the researcher will be aware of what the data involves and what they are achieving through the analysis of the raw data. The next step involves speculation, through which the researcher creates initial codes from the set of data. In this study, the researcher revisited the raw data set several times to ensure that the codes are in track in defining the phenomenon giving an equal attention to each observation data on the file.

Phase 3: Searching for themes

This is the phase where the researcher makes an effort to build connections between the identified themes. The researcher is expected to make notes about how they uncover the connections between the identified groups of themes and how they have arranged them into a hierarchy. Researchers used tables and mind maps (Braun and Clarke, 2006) to record and organise the known theme ideas. There is no specified method by which to determine a code, so the researcher in this study determined the codes based on the research questions and theoretical framework to initiate coding, unlike using predefined codes to help control the analysis (King, 2014). Often there were times when the researcher identified codes that were important but that would not fit in with the main themes; by implementing Braun and Clarke's (2006) advice, the researcher provisionally created a 'miscellaneous' theme and later distributed them correctly.

Phase 4: Reviewing themes

This is the phase where the researcher returns to the raw data more than ever. By this point in the study, the researcher has adequate knowledge of what he/she is looking for. Hence, if the researcher recognises any relevant material in the raw data text that

has not already been enclosed within an existing code, a new code needs to be introduced. Similarly, there are times when a theme is introduced initially which may not seem to add much value in the later phase or that overlaps with other codes; thus, it can be erased (King, 2014). The researcher had experience of this and deleted more than 10 codes that were initially thought to be relevant. An equal number of other codes were found to be overlapping and were thus merged with similar codes. The addition of new codes is often viewed as being challenging for inexperienced researchers; however, as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006) that the researcher will have an ongoing reflexive dialogue with self; about whether the coding is enough and that covers all the dataset. The researcher frequently reviewed and examined the coded excerpts for each theme and subtheme in order to define whether a clear pattern had been identified.

Phase 5: Defining and naming themes

This was an important phase in this particular study, as the main themes identified would serve to create a structure; namely, with regard to the dark sides of the CRM behaviours being practiced by MNOs. It was imperative for the researcher to ensure that the themes were named accurately enough so that the reader would immediately make sense of what the theme was all about. One of the most common feelings shared by qualitative researchers in thematic analysis is the difficulty to decide when to stop refining the defined themes. In this study, the themes were considered to be final after the researcher had thoroughly read the whole data set and studied the developed themes and subthemes more than twice, as suggested by King (2014). The insights acquired during the development of the themes were constantly recorded as they contribute to the trustworthiness of the research method and findings as a whole.

Phase 6: Producing a report

It is crucial for researchers to effectively communicate the logical flow and processes involved in the development of the findings so that any statements made regarding the data and findings are viewed as being reliable and convincing. Once the themes and subthemes are finalised, it is followed up by an analysis and fully written report (Braun and Clarke, 2006), which is often included in the discussion chapter. Academics such as King (2014) and Braun and Clarke (2006) have suggested that the inclusion of quotes from participants is a crucial element in reporting. Short quotes

from the observation data set have been included while discussing each sub-theme in the hope that this will help readers to understand and interpret the importance of the established themes. The researcher also referred to the reflexive diary now and then when writing the report in order to ensure that the findings were on track and that the reviewed literature supported the findings (Polit and Beck, 2008). Furthermore, the researcher also went back to confirm the research findings (Tuckett, 2005), especially as the findings of this research contribute to the literature on the dark sides of CRM behaviours.

Overall, these six phases (**Table 4.3**) provide a clear overview of how this research project and its findings ensure trustworthiness and credibility. The six phases explained above served as a guide by which to conduct a rigorous and trustworthy thematic analysis, including the interpretation and presentation of the findings.

Phases of Thematic Analysis	Means of Establishing Trustworthiness
Phase 1: Familiarizing yourself with your data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prolong engagement with data Triangulate different data collection modes Document theoretical and reflective thoughts Document thoughts about potential codes/themes Store raw data in well-organized archives Keep records of all data field notes, transcripts, and reflexive journals
Phase 2: Generating initial codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer debriefing Researcher triangulation Reflexive journaling Use of a coding framework Audit trail of code generation Documentation of all team meeting and peer debriefings
Phase 3: Searching for themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researcher triangulation Diagramming to make sense of theme connections Keep detailed notes about development and hierarchies of concepts and themes
Phase 4: Reviewing themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researcher triangulation Themes and subthemes vetted by team members Test for referential adequacy by returning to raw data
Phase 5: Defining and naming themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researcher triangulation Peer debriefing Team consensus on themes Documentation of team meetings regarding themes Documentation of theme naming
Phase 6: Producing the report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member checking Peer debriefing Describing process of coding and analysis in sufficient details Thick descriptions of context Description of the audit trail Report on reasons for theoretical, methodological, and analytical choices throughout the entire study

Table 4. 3 Establishing Trustworthiness During Each Phase of Thematic Analysis, adapted from (Nowell et al., 2017, p. 4)

4.6 Potential Ethical Issues in the Study

The rise of the internet and the expansion of digital technologies has empowered firms to create a virtual space or communities in which they and their customers can interact and share issues related to mutual interests, concerns and other ideas (James and Busher, 2009) while removing mainstream barriers such as physical distance, time zones and even languages. Use of internet on research not only contributes on ease and reach of data collection but also on richness of data. As much opportunity as the use of internet in research promises, it also presents some areas of challenge. Ethics in the online setting have been the subject of controversy in both academic research and practice.

The section below highlights the ethical considerations involved in this research.

1. Ethics in qualitative studies

In a qualitative paradigm of research, the researcher should pay attention to both reflexivity and applicable ethical issues. Ethics are not only limited to prescriptive guidelines in qualitative research; in a broader sense, they incorporate an individual's personal experiences and whether or not sharing such experiences to public study can be ethically questionable.

With regard to ethical dilemmas, Netnography has been challenged by researchers in relation to its research area, the need for participation agreements and the privacy concerns that researchers need to take account of (Roy et al., 2015). Kozinets' (2018) ethical guidelines are possibly one of the most argued about concerns in Netnography. When responding to his parameter of 'needing to disclose [the] researcher's intention', Langer and Beckman (2005) argued that doing so would only make sense if the researcher was studying the private online communications of a private group and stated that it is far too demanding when researching a public forum. They also argued that if an individual participates and give an input in an online communication or a communal platform without any restrictions, then it implies the concept of traditional mass media communication content analysis (Langer and Beckman, 2005); that the researcher requires no consent to analyse those publicly availed data.

In addition to whether a Netnography researcher—particularly when carrying out the observation of online communities—needs to seek ethical approval, plenty of previous researchers have argued that it is not necessary due to the fact that online content is publicly accessible. These researchers argued that since users have complete control over where they are engaging with others and what they are posting in openly-accessible platforms, there is no need to ask for permission to use their content in research (Rageh, Melewar and Woodside, 2013; Wu and Pearce, 2014). Wu and Pearce (2014) also argued that seeking consent on such online platforms can spoil the natural content; and also stated the process to be “too rigorous and [that it can] endanger the unobtrusiveness of online communication studies” (p. 465). Rageh et al. (2013) further claimed that the popularity and use of electronic communication and the regulation of public forums themselves has negated the need for consent; understanding of the universal opportunity for interpretation, access and use of online data.

However, if observation is being conducted on a private community, the researcher believes that there is a need to obtain ethical consent to use any of the content available in a private group. This is because the purpose of making a page or a group private is to protect the community’s content and to guard the privacy of both the content and the members involved in the community.

2. Ethics in quantitative studies

When posting the survey on the big four MNOs’ Facebook pages, the researcher posted an introductory statement to disclose who the research was being carried out by and why the research was being carried out, which was followed by a link to the survey. The survey started with an information sheet, which contained details about the researcher, the aim of the research, the university’s details and how the data collected would be implemented. At the end of the survey, the researcher also included their contact details (email address) in case any respondents wanted to follow up with some information or if they would like to query anything else. Disclosing such information is crucial to ensuring credibility.

O2’s Facebook page was restricted to make posts by the followers, hence the researcher used their dedicated community forum for both qualitative and quantitative

data collection. In order to gain access to the forum, the researcher first became a member of the community. This had to be approved by the moderator of the group. Afterwards, they posted the survey following the same pattern as above.

4.7 Privacy, Anonymity and Confidentiality

Ensuring the anonymity, privacy and confidentiality of the collected data is imperative in any form of research. Although the researcher did not collect participant's IP addresses, use tracking links or any other identifying information aside from the content of the survey itself, there was still the possibility of breaches of anonymity and privacy occurring when carrying out online research, and this was outside the researcher's control. Mahon (2013) argued that is unreasonable for researchers to state that their online surveys are anonymous and rather suggested that researchers should include a cautionary declaration alongside the participant information sheet. This, however, has not been much explored by recent researchers.

In this research, the participants in the online survey were provided with information in the participation information sheet, which included detailed information about the researcher, the research itself and how the data and its findings would be used. This research is purely academic, which means that the findings are used to seek answers to the research questions and to build a solution framework towards addressing the research problem.

The storage of data is one act that can violate the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. The data collected for this research was stored on the researcher's personal computer that could not be accessed by anyone else. The researcher ensures that information collected for the research purpose will not be misused in any way. Additionally, the researcher's notebook and reflexive notes are also stored privately to ensure confidentiality of the data.

4.8 Chapter Summary and Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the research approach, design and the methodology implemented by the researcher. After starting by discussing the philosophical underpinnings of the research, this chapter justifies the use of mixed methods research in this study. The mixed methods research approach used in this study follows the pragmatic approach.

Methodologically speaking, data from two different strands (QUAL and QUAN) are collected and mixed in this study (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003), as this is a technique that enriches the research findings. Finally, in terms of language and the presentation of research findings, pragmatism allows for both formal and informal rhetoric to be used (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). With regard to the qualitative aspect of the interpretation of the data, rhetoric is important for its reflection of how the researcher shares and communicates the knowledge. The researcher in this study uses the best explanation that makes sense within their own value system.

The predominant method used in this particular research is the qualitative method; this is because the researcher is on a journey to understand the perceptions of service users of service providers' behaviours/activities. An online survey, which is a quantitative method of data collection, is subsequently applied to enhance the quality of the findings further. Although online surveys are extremely popular today as a result of the popularity of the internet, the researcher experienced that the response rates are declining. This may be because people are spammed with surveys in one form or the other in their social media feeds, which causes them to tend to automatically ignore any kind of survey.

Qualitative data are collected through observation in an online setting using netnography—which is often referred to as virtual ethnography. This concept is only about two decades old, and it is gaining popularity amongst academics and market researchers as a result of advancements in digital technology and the increased use of the internet.

As aforementioned, the data collection is carried out in parallel, as the two sets of data are not dependent on each other in any way. The only common object amongst two methods of data collection is the platform used. Data collected in the two separate strands are analysed individually and the findings are generated from each strand individually before being mixed at the discussion stage. The research design implemented in this research is referred to as convergent design, which is where the researcher collects both qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously, studies both data strings individually and then mixes the databases by merging the data (Creswell and Clark, 2011).

This chapter also explained the phases involved in the thematic analysis and justified the trustworthiness of both the process and findings of the analysis. Although thematic analysis is not a method that can follow a step-by-step process, as the researcher needs to go back and forth to the data set to refine each phase, the six phases enhance the trustworthiness and overall quality of the findings.

Thereafter, the ethical issues and considerations associated with both research methods were highlighted and discussed. The researcher, however, identified the limitation in ethical considerations in Netnography. Controversial claims have been made in relation to whether a researcher requires consent to use data that is publicly accessible in online communities, which can make such research complex for inexperienced researchers. Therefore, the researcher feels that there is a need for more exploration of this area of netnography.

The next chapter details the findings and interprets them in relation to the research questions.

Chapter 5: Findings, Data Analysis and Discussion

Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from the data collection and it is segmented into two parts. The first part will detail and explain the findings from the quantitative study and the second part will discuss the findings from the qualitative study. Overall, this chapter will present the complete research findings from both the quantitative and qualitative data collection. Based on what is identified through the analysis and discussion, a recommended framework of solutions will be presented in the next chapter.

The main aim of this study is understanding the perceptions of service users of their service provider's dark side behaviours. Perception, as defined in psychology, is a process by which a person processes and interprets certain stimuli or a particular situation that involves them giving it a meaning of its own. Due to their intangible nature, service sectors are prone to subjective evaluation and perception. As discussed in the previous chapter, service fairness refers to service quality, which is defined by several factors, such as price equality, trust, commitment, service delivery, after sales services, communication, and so on. As a result of the emergence of social media and the increasing transparency offered by such online platforms, it has become even easier for consumers and service users to compare and judge how they have been treated by their service providers. Any signs of opportunism and inequality are taken account of or reacted to immediately. Many will resort to pouring out their frustrations on social media platforms, calling out brands, spreading negative word of mouth and engaging in informed withdrawal; these some of the reactions observed in this study. Very few service users were also found to engage in the abuse of frontline staff, which is an unacceptable behaviour regardless of the cause or motive. The details of how service users respond to situations after realising their disadvantaged position are discussed later in this chapter.

Equity theory states that consumers tend to compare what they invest into a relationship exchange with what they receive from being in that relationship—and the difference is what raises the question of fairness or unfairness. During the observation,

service users were seen to be expressing their anger and frustration at having got the shorter end of stick from their network providers. Fairness, particularly in the service industry, is crucial as a result of its intangibility; consumers stay loyal to the brand based on their judgement of trust, whereas in the product industry which would simply be measured by ability of product in meeting and satisfying the customer's need. Furthermore, some of the behaviours practiced by service providers are not just unfair; rather deceptive and misleading to make consumers make a purchase decision.

The overall purpose of this study is to understand whether service users are aware of fairness/unfairness behaviours and the dark practices engaged in by their service providers. This will be achieved through the use of both the qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection. If they are aware, this study asks what activities they categorise as being dark practices. With regard to the qualitative data, it is observed to a certain degree that the consumers are aware of their unfair situation and disadvantaged position and they react to it through several behavioural intentions, which will be highlighted and discussed below.

Likewise, some of the questions in the survey questionnaire helped the researcher derive answers with regard to consumers' awareness of service fairness. Service fairness is purely consumers' perceptions of the level of fairness in their service provider's conduct. Fairness, as defined in the existing literature, incorporates the involved/related parties being treated on equal terms. It was therefore important to understand whether customers realised whether they were being fairly treated or not and what kinds of activities, as practiced by their mobile network/service providers, were perceived as being fair or unfair. These include unfair treatment and unfairness in terms of price or service quality. When talking about service quality, customer service and communication plays a crucial role.

Studies have proven that the way that employees interact with their customers hugely impacts customer loyalty (Yieh et al., 2007), and it ultimately results in a better relationship. In today's digital era, employee–customer interaction is not limited to face-to-face communication; rather, it includes telephone conversations, social media post/replies, email responses, live chats, and so on. Based on the data collected via social media comments and posts in this study, it is found that several customers

decided to terminate their contract and long-standing relationship with their provider based on the tone taken by the customer advisor over the phone or the attitude of personnel in store, and so on.

Personal association with a brand is one of the factors that makes a customer stay loyal to a brand; therefore, when a brand diverts away from a particular belief, service users tend to move away. Trust and commitment are the foundations that relationship marketing is built upon (Palmatier, et. al. 2006). Often related to customer satisfaction, the model of relationship marketing is based upon commitment and trust (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Palmatier et al., 2013), and mutual loyalty helps both parties fulfil their needs.

Governors like Ofcom review their fairness channels every year to protect mobile customers and this includes the measures taken towards ensuring greater transparency, fairer contract terms and price protection approaches by the MNOs (Ofcom, 2020). The operators seem to have ways of ignoring such policies. For example, Ofcom has clearly stated that “[m]obile customers must be told the cost of buying handsets and airtime separately”; however, some of the MNOs are still practising otherwise. Such unfair practices can lead consumers to feel that their trust and commitment have been broken. As a result, some service users exit their long-standing relationship with their service provider, while others go out on online communities, publicise how they have been treated and state that they do not want any of their friends and family to join the network. Such repercussions not only be financially costly to the service providers but also negatively impacts brands reputation.

While the assessment of fairness is subjective and highly relative, social media and open discussions on such platforms have a huge impact on assessments of fairness as they provide a basis for comparison. This further highlights the need for service providers and practitioners to be transparent. Even if service providers are trying to deliberately hide some information, it is not that easy and safe for them to do so anymore. Once one service user is aware of such malpractice, it will be out there in online spaces in no time. That is the power of the online world and social media. Online presence also includes the concept of e-commerce and online retailing.

In the past when retailing was limited to an offline space, people would not be able to easily compare substitute products and services as much as the online shopping has empowered today. Buyers would not go around every store only to compare prices. Furthermore, they would have to rely on brand's information and advertisements about their products and services, unlike today, when online reviews, comments on social media and referrals are way more powerful in influencing purchasing decisions. Although there are many positives associated with an online presence and maintaining online communities for brands, if not analysed and implemented properly the same platforms will result in negative impacts.

The next section will analyse and discuss the findings and interpret the data.

5.1 Findings from the Quantitative Data

The survey was created using one of the most popular survey platforms amongst beginner researchers in the UK, Survey Monkey. It was chosen after considering two factors: firstly, the easy of creating a survey questionnaire and secondly, the end user experience of the respondents. The pilot study reflected that the survey created on this platform has higher response rate and also the platform's user experience is good.

In terms of the four objectives of this study, the quantitative survey method was primarily implemented in order to understand service users' level of awareness of hidden practices, which have been recognised as dark sides by some of the previous studies. The survey also includes some questions to build foundation on understanding how the service users react to the unfairness situation, which is another objective of this study.

The participants for this study are UK mobile network users. With an objective to obtain the informative participants, the link to the survey was posted on the Facebook pages of (EE, Vodafone and Three) and community forum (O2). The survey contained 20 questions that were completely inter-related and which aimed to answer two of the sub-questions. First of all, the researcher intended to understand the level of awareness of service users with regard to dark practices, as often the lack of awareness is what encourages service providers to continue engaging in such

practices. Secondly, the researcher aimed to understand how responsible service users themselves are; this includes negligence, failure to express, lack of communication, and so on. For example, the survey findings showed that out of the total number of participants (n=188), 28.19% are 'not aware at all' of how their data are being used, while 21.81% had 'never' read the terms and conditions and privacy policies when signing a mobile contract with their service providers. Such negligence can be one of the factors that encourage service providers to continue their malicious practices and this can even encourage them to incorporate ambiguous conditions in their fine print. This ensures they are legally in the clear, while the service users are legally bound into a contract.

5.1.1 Discussion of the quantitative study

As per Ofcom (2020), mobile telephony services made £3.4bn in revenues on second quarter of 2019, which shows decline by £32m (0.9%) in comparison to the last year where the average revenue per subscriber was £13.52. It reflected that the pay as you go subscribers generated less revenue than the monthly pre-paying subscribers.

Demographic analysis of the quantitative data

Approximately 95% of households in the UK own mobile devices; more specifically, a smartphone is owned by 79% of UK adults (Ofcom, 2019). According to a report published by O'Deah (2019), smartphone usage reached 78% during the first half of 2018, which is almost 50% higher than what it was in 2011.

Irrespective of users' age, smartphones are the most sought after and adopted smart devices in the UK and specifically among those aged between 18 and 34 years old. Among those aged between 45 and 54 years old, smartphone adoption rates have jumped from 60% to 90%, and that has doubled to 80% among 55 to 75-year-olds. It has also been noticed that users over the age of 55 tend not to use smartphones.

In this research, approximately 40% of the total respondents are aged between 18 and 24, while the second most dominant age range is the 25–34 age range. These are the most popular age ranges in terms of smartphone adoption, with smartphone adoption rates of 93% and 94% respectively. Only 4 respondents out of 188 were below the

age of 18 years, which is also the number of respondents in the 55–64 age range. 3.72% of the respondents were over 65. Based on national telecommunication and mobile users' statistics, the UK market's youngest mobile phone users are aged 6 and upwards, and they use their phones with parental guidance. In today's tech savvy age, and especially in the western world, mobile phone users range from 5 years old to over 65. In 2019, a study carried out by Ofcom amongst UK parents found that kids as young as 5 own their own smartphone (Kleinman, 2019).

UK mobile industry is dominated by female service users. According to the statistics reported in 2015, 4% more females used smartphones in comparison to male users, which was other way around in 2012.

In this study, 56.91% of the respondents are female and 42.55 % are male. Only one of the respondents is reported to be other than male or female.

Out of 188 respondents, 47.34% are students and 43.09% were employed. Less than 3% of the respondents were retired, unemployed or self-employed.

Choice of service providers, satisfaction and loyalty

MNO and loyalty

Although the respondents were targeted to be using the Big Four MNOS, some of the respondents used UK MVNOs including giffgaff, TalkTalk, Tesco, Lebara and Lyca Mobile. This could be the result of the fact that these MVNOs share the network infrastructures of the Big Four MNOs and because most subscribers to MVNOs tend to visit the social media platforms of the parent MNO.

In this study, a quarter of the respondents are observed to be using the Three network, whereas 21% are using O2. EE was used by 17% of the total respondents, while only 14% of the respondents were found to be using Vodafone. As per the statistics, EE—which has 28 million customers in the UK—is the leading operator in terms of its total number of customers, and it is followed by O2, which has 26 million customers. Vodafone and Three are in third and fourth place, with 21 million and 12 million

customers respectively. EE has had the leading market share since BT took over the company in 2015.

The degree to which consumers react to any fair or unfair situation is often dependent on the length of their relationship with the brand. It is a virtue of human nature that we expect to be treated better as a result of the time that we have invested in building a relationship. In other terms, good treatment can be viewed as being a return for sticking with the brand. In this research, out of n=188, 12 respondents had been with their service providers for more than 10 years, while 97 of them had been with their providers for 1 to 5 years. The number of respondents who had been with their provider for less than a year and between 5 and 10 years was almost equal; the former being 40 and the latter 39.

Based on the cross-tabulation analysis, it was found that the most satisfied respondents had spent 1 to 5 years with their service provider. Out of a total of 6 dissatisfied respondents, 4 of them had spent 1 to 5 years with their service providers. A total of 41 respondents were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

Satisfaction

Perceived satisfaction is defined by a number of factors, including customer service, service delivery, brand association, attachment to the brand, and so on, and it has been found to be directly proportional to customer loyalty. In this study, the majority of the respondents are satisfied with their service providers. The question 'How satisfied are you with your current service provider?' was based on a Likert scale and 43.09% of the respondents answered that they are satisfied, while 21% are highly satisfied. On the contrary, 3.19% are highly dissatisfied and 4.79% are dissatisfied with their service providers. 21.81% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

Subscription Type

In this study, it has been observed that 82.98% out of the total respondents are on Pay Monthly plan, while 17.02% use Pay As You Go. This aligns with the results published by Ofcom, which stated that Pay Monthly was the most common type of mobile subscription in 2018 (Ofcom, 2019). The proportion of monthly users continued to be higher in 2019, as shown by Deloitte's UK mobile consumer survey—which

illustrates that 41% of consumers use a Pay Monthly phone contract (including SIM and handset), 23% use Pay As You Go, 34% use a SIM only plan and 2% fall into the unknown category.

Impact of online reviews

The popularity and usage of social media platforms have encouraged people to be more vocal. They are also a popular source of research, for both products and the service industry. People tend to believe more about what a fellow user has to say when compared to what brands say about themselves. When asked if online reviews have an impact on their purchasing decision, 62.23% of the respondents said that the online reviews shared by fellow service users had an impact on their purchase decision. However, only 22.87% of the respondents are found to be sharing their experiences online. Studies have shown that people refrain from leaving an online review as a result of several factors, starting with how user friendly the review platform is.

Service users are found to be leaving negative comments if they identify that their service provider is engaging in any hidden or unfair activity. When asked 'If you come across any unfair treatment, how do you react?', 11.70% of the respondents answered that they would leave a negative comment. This reflects the fact that they would not hold back from sharing their negative experiences online if they experienced any unfair treatment at the hands of their service providers.

What factors impact the service user's purchase decision and the choice of MNOs?

Purchase decision, especially in a service industry like mobile communication, is defined by several factors including, but not limited to, the price of the handset, the brand of the handset, recommendations from friends and family, online reviews about both the product and service provider, the network quality of the particular MNO, and so on. Respondents were asked 'What information do you look for while buying a mobile plan'? It was a multiple response question with an option where respondents could add further information if their answer was not listed within the choices given. One of the service users pointed out ease of signing up was one of the factors that

played role on customer's purchase decision. This also correlates with what has been observed in the qualitative data collection with regard to procedure complexity.

Price plays a huge part in purchase decisions, and especially when there are alternatives available and they are extremely competitive. This study highlights that the price and service package (i.e., how many minutes, data and texts are included) are two of the major factors in making a purchasing decision. Only 28.72% of the respondents looked at the brand and specifications of the handset. Similarly, only 31.3% of the total respondents took account of the quality of the service that the MNO had to offer. 37.23% of the respondents made their purchasing decision based on the length of contract on offer. Some other factors were highlighted by 4.26% of the respondents. These are highlighted below:

- a. Signal coverage
- b. Extras, i.e., free access to Spotify for a certain period of time
- c. Tethering
- d. Ease of signing up
- e. Recommendation
- f. Reliability
- g. Signal
- h. Price quality and brand

Referrals and recommendations

A significant amount of sales conversion is delivered by referrals and word of mouth in the service industry. People tend to make purchase decisions based on what has worked for their friends, family and acquaintances and whether they are satisfied with their relationship exchange with the brand (Adjei et al., 2010). Recommendations have been found to be one of the factors that have an impact on purchase decision, as are online reviews. In this study, 83% of the existing service users answered that they would recommend their current service provider to their friends and family; however, 16.49% said that they would not recommend them. This was an open-ended question, where those who answered 'no' could elaborate on why they would not recommend their service provider. 60% of the service users seemed disappointed with the quality of the network signal and the internet, which is an essential part of the service. 5 out of 12 respondents pointed out that they had received poor customer service. One

respondent highlighted the fact that the service was expensive, while another respondent provided a statement of their frustration: *“Horrendous company; hassling me for money I don’t owe. Termination fee for a contract—I never signed a contract. Manipulative. A danger to vulnerable people because they’d con them out of money”*. One of the respondents also pointed out that they had received *“below promised network or internet”*. Many comments similar to these statements were made in the second part of the data collection of this study; this reflects the fact that service users are clearly aware of the brands overpromising and under delivering, which they define as being misleading and unfair. False advertising and the practice of concealing important information have also been underlined as being hidden activities by some of the past studies. The findings of the qualitative data collection will be discussed later on in this chapter.

- *not currently pleased with speed of company service*
- *Not the best service*
- *below promised network and internet*
- *Offshore Customer service speak poor English & Rude i.e talk over you & overbearing*
- *It is too expensive*
- *I never get a quality network or internet.*
- *I've been having issues with network and internet access for quite a while*
- *Poor network speed*
- *Not good service*
- *Customer service is non existent*
- *Horrendous company, hassling me for money I don’t owe. Termination fee for a contract, I never signed a contract. Manipulative. A danger to vulnerable people because they’d con them out of money.*
- *Network coverage not as good as previous provider*

Customers’ behavioural intention

A question was initially asked to identify users’ level of awareness with regard to whether they have identified any hidden or unfair behaviours being practised by their service providers. This was then followed up by another question whose objective was

to understand how they would react upon finding that they themselves were being unfairly treated and or taken advantage of. This was a multiple-variant question.

Service users' accountability

The last four questions of the survey were focused on understanding what efforts would service users would make as a responsible buyer. It is very necessary to be well informed when purchasing a product or service. Similarly, it is crucial to be informed about how a service provider uses one's data, read the full terms and conditions and be attentive with regard to bills. Sometimes customers put the blame on service providers for consequences that are the result of their own negligence. For instance, some service users do not update their marketing preferences and call out the service providers for sending them offers and promotional messages.

Customers or service users have a set of responsibilities when purchasing goods or services. These begin with gaining as much information as possible, including product information, information about pricing and payment options, general terms and conditions, data and information use and other related policies. With particular reference to this study, mobile service users are expected to gain information, such the price they are paying, billing conditions, network signal strength, after sales services, general customer services, and so on. Many customers tend to cut corners and sign a contract hastily without even acquainting themselves with the basics. It goes without saying that it is the responsibility of sales advisors to inform customers as much as possible while selling a product or service, but it is equally the customers' duty to do their bit.

This study found that 21.81% of service users never read the terms and condition or the privacy policies when purchasing their mobile plan. 29.26% answered that they do this 'rarely' and 19.15% answered that they do this 'sometimes'. This result somehow reflects why the service providers are encouraged to hide important clauses within the fine print.

Similarly, 32.45% of the respondents are found to never check their bills before making a payment, and 18.62% answered that they 'rarely' do so. The use of payment options such as Direct Debit often lead people to overlook checking their bills, but it is

necessary for customers to do so to keep track. Only 28.19% of the respondents always check their bills, while 20.74% said that they check their bills 'sometimes'. According to Ofcom's report, 1.4 million customers are overpaying, on average (Ofcom, 2019).

Furthermore, with regard to users' awareness of how their data was used by service providers, the respondents were asked if they were aware about the use of their personal data by their mobile network providers. 28.19% said they were 'not aware at all' and 22.87% said that they were 'not so aware'.

These findings are incredibly poor in comparison to how qualified the buyers are versus the extent of their lack of knowledge about important issues like data and privacy. Similarly, customers are also found to be negligent in terms of keeping an eye on their bills and reading the terms and conditions. These all fall under service users' responsibilities and, unfortunately, such negligence on the part of service users provides the service providers with increased confidence when it comes to exploiting loopholes.

5.1.2 Summary on the service users' awareness of dark side practices

The main aim of undertaking an online survey was to identify whether or not the service users are aware of dark side CRM practices being practiced by their service users. Out of the total respondents, 19.15 percentage said yes to having experienced some kind of unfair behaviour / activity from their service providers. Additionally, 21.81 percentage of them responded that they came across some activities that were not informed to them by their service providers prior to purchasing the plan. In addition to answering 'Yes' or 'No', some of the respondents also shared what activities did they found to be hidden or unfair in the comment section provided within the survey. Those qualitative information are outlined below and discussed with the use of thematic analysis.

		Have you experienced any unfair behaviour/activity from your mobile network provider?		Total
		No	Yes	
Have you ever come across any activity of your network provider that you would term as hidden, something that you weren't informed about while purchasing the plan?	No	133	14	147
	Yes	19	22	41
Total		152	36	188

As aforementioned, the researcher designed some questions in such a way that the researcher could gain deeper insights, and this was achieved by not limiting the respondent to only pick a given option. Two questions were formulated to identify the existing dark side behaviours engaged in by service providers. This question aimed to also understand what kinds of behaviours service users would perceive to be dark or hidden.

The two questions are:

- a. Have you experienced any unfair behaviour/activity from your mobile network provider?

b. Have you ever come across any activity engaged in by your network provider that you would term as being hidden; that is, something that you were not informed about while purchasing the plan?

The answer choices for both the questions were ‘yes’ and ‘no’. Furthermore, the respondents who said ‘yes’ were given the option to input their comments so that they could elaborate or to share the details of activities that they felt were unfair and the ones that they felt could be identified as being hidden. The table below illustrates the activities provided in response to the open-ended questions:

<p>Have you experienced any unfair behaviour/activity from your mobile network provider?</p>	<p>Have you ever come across any activity engaged in by your network provider that you would term as hidden—something that you weren’t informed about while purchasing the plan?</p>
<p>In the past with different networks.</p> <p>Phone broke after 9 months, had to pay for a new one...</p> <p>Shop worker told me the wrong information which meant I lost all my credit and wasn’t refunded</p> <p>Trying to sell me products when I called customer service</p> <p>Charging over the normal agreed bill—I had to be refunded.</p> <p>A lot of calls</p>	<p>They sent surprise gifts, such as £3 Costa vouchers</p> <p>They charged me £100 when my free minutes ended and never mentioned it</p> <p>Orange passed on my details to third parties which resulted in spam</p> <p>Lack of mobile data caps and lack of distinctive information regarding pricing</p> <p>Additional costs were placed on my contract without my knowledge</p>

Added costs	Increase in monthly payment
Throttled network while abroad	SecureNet free antivirus offered for first three months, after that it was an extra £1 per month unless cancelled before the free trial was over
As above; their adverts are misleading	
Slow data speed compared to others despite stating high speed	Charged for running over mobile data limit
International calling doesn't work sometimes and yet they charged many times	Added costs that come into force after the contract has started
Charge too much	"Security fee" of £1
Message keeps popping up on the screen after every call or text and there is always automatic voice recording at the beginning of any call—that is damn annoying	Price increases every March
Price rise without prior information	They advertise being the best in terms of their network and 4G, but their service is nowhere near.
No notification of contract end [date]	Frustrating
Different price for everyone	How to set the damn payment system up in the first place. The instructions are crap—trendy crap—but no good for an average person and I am IT literate!
Won't replace a faulty phone without me paying £120 excess	
Manipulation. Refusing to let me speak to a manager. In order for me to prove I didn't sign a contract they had me fill out a form and wait 7 days, put my case through the	They changed the price after a few months

<p>fraud department (no idea why) wanted me to go to a shop; I've never set foot in a shop. After cancelling everything finally in May, no termination fee, I have it all in writing, they sent me a threatening letter in July saying I owe them £24?? Over two hours on the phone to different people they've somehow added to the £24 and say I have to pay termination fees or they'll get debt collectors involved. I've got no choice but to go to the ombudsman.</p> <p>Removal of 'Tugo' which allowed calls and texts when abroad over WiFi</p>	<p>Price rise without prior information</p> <p>They never notify me when my contract ends and [they] increase the price often</p> <p>Extra bill</p> <p>Termination fee for rolling monthly plan = £40</p> <p>Auto enrolment on some kind of security service that is a free trial and once that's over you have to pay for a subscription for a service that is pointless</p> <p>Annual increase</p>
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This table includes all the activities identified by the service users as being unfair or hidden. This reflects that the service users have an awareness of the dark behaviours that are being practiced by their service providers. From the list of activities, a theme has been identified that is also identified in the observation data. A list of dark activities have been identified that will be discussed altogether in the later section when discussing the themes developed through thematic analysis. These activities are:

- Extra charges
- Incorrect billing
- Contract auto-rolling
- Lack of information
- Mid-contract price increases
- Misleading adverts

5.2 Discussion of Qualitative Analysis

As established in the previous chapter, the researcher implemented Netnography to collect the qualitative data. Netnography is developed from the concept of ethnography, and it is the process of observing and recording the events happening in natural settings over the internet. The researcher selected the social media platforms of the Big Four MNOs; these include their official Facebook page, Twitter and official community forums, with the objective of answering the third question of this research, which is '*What behaviours of service providers do the service users perceive as dark behaviour?*'. With regard to the pre-identified dark side activities, it has been observed that the UK mobile network operator industry is certainly not immune to such behaviours. Most importantly, service users seem to be highly aware of them. It seems that some of the activities are being deliberately practiced by the MNOs, which falls under the concept of opportunism, while some seem to be the result of ignorance on the part of employees or due to procedural negligence from the top level. Either way, it is necessary for the MNOs to acknowledge, and implement necessary measures to end, the use of such practices.

The researcher selected these three platforms with the aim to achieve informative data. These social media platforms play a distinctive set of roles for both new and existing customers. It has been observed that new customers browse companies' official Facebook pages to gain an insight into service information, pricing, customer support comparison and the overall attitude of the brand towards their customers, while existing customers use Facebook to share their experiences, for technical support or to simply engage with the posts made by the service provider or fellow service users. Furthermore, existing customers were also seen to be comparing prices and the service that is offered to new customers. Twitter seems to be a space for providing technical support for all four network providers; even the posts made by the brands themselves were full of comments containing support questions. On the other hand, the community forums were more of a space where people could share their experiences in detail.

The researcher observed and recorded 100 statements for each service provider from the combination of social platforms. The observations were made over a period of one

and a half years; from July 2018 to December 2019. The data were extracted from one of the following means; a post made by a service user, a reply to an original thread created by other service users, a response to posts made by the service provider, a tweet mentioning their respective MNOs, a reply to someone else's tweet in which the MNO is mentioned, posts made on the community forum and replies on any posts made on the community forum. Some comments were one liner, but most of them were detailed. In order to gain detailed information, the researcher tried to ignore one-line comments as much as possible. People were also observed to be making posts and comments on multiple threads and multiple platforms; however, comments from the same person were discarded as much as possible in order to avoid the duplication of data.

In their recent studies, Heinonen and Medberg (2018) implemented Netnography as a tool for understanding customers in the service context. The data acquired through Netnography are the most raw and naturalistic in nature and this guarantees that the researcher can understand the consumers/service users better; this is why this research implements Netnography as a major research technique. Data observed through Netnography is not just limited to words; rather, they also reflected attitude and emotions and emotions of the service users. It was observed that most of the comments and statements included in the study were not one-off comments: they seem to be a follow up on an earlier enquiry or complaints.

This study uses thematic analysis, which includes the coding and development of themes. Coding is all about shifting intuition into logic while keeping the research question in mind. In qualitative research such as this study, the description of events and experiences is important; however, it is crucial to always keep track of how these experiences are related to the research question, otherwise it is very easy for the researcher to divert from the core objective of the study.

Using the thematic analysis, the researcher has developed the following themes, and each theme includes a sub theme. These themes and sub themes refer to the dark CRM practices that are being practiced by the service providers according to service users' perceptions. The categorisation of such activities as dark sides is based on past studies (Payne and Frow, 2015). Some of the identified behaviours have already been

established as being dark sides of CRM; however, the researcher has identified some new dark side behaviours. By doing so, the researcher makes a fresh contribution to the theory of dark sides of CRM.

Themes	Sub Themes
Behavioural Discrepancy	Favouritism
	Loyalty Penalty
	Exploitation of Vulnerability
Data Exploitation	Data Misuse and Mishandling
	Privacy Invasion
Deceptive Tactics	False Advertising
	Information Asymmetry
	Lack of Transparency
	Misleading Practices
	Procedure Complexity
	Fine Print Misuse
Employee Incompetency	Misinformation and Forced Selling
	Lack of Product Information
	Employee Negligence and Irresponsibility
	Dishonesty and Violation of Psychological Contract
Financial Exploitation	Billing Shock
	Mid-contract Price Rise
	Price Discrepancy
Service Quality Failure	Poor Customer Service
	Inadequate Service Value
Consumer Dark Side Behaviour Intentions	Anger and Use of Foul Language
	Negative Word of Mouth
	Withdrawal from the Relationship

Table 5. 1 Dark sides behaviours identified by the study

1. Behavioural Discrepancy

Although the fundamental objective of CRM implementation is to customise offers on an individual basis, Ngyuen found that such differential treatment is a pitfall within CRM as the differential treatment of customers is perceived negatively by customers (Nguyen and Simkin, 2009). The literature on fairness has brought this issue to light by suggesting that consumers attribute negative inferences to a firm that treats certain customers differently; for example, by presenting persuasive offers to new customers over existing ones. Issues like favouritism and loyalty penalties are perceived as being unfair by consumers, which seems to hinder buyer-seller relationship; therefore, it is identified as a dark side of CRM in this study.

“I was disgusted and appalled to see two men being treated with utter disrespect and hate by the manager of the Hounslow branch...”

“Visited this EE outlet last week and was traumatised by the whole experience: all the reps were interested in was getting customers to sign up to the new fibre broadband, [giving each other] high fives and fist punches, [and] running in and out of the staff area to check who has made the most sales.”

This is an era in which consumers are smarter and more knowledgeable than ever. Ignorance of any form on the part of staff comes down to the issue of poor organisational ethics and the lack of employee training.

a. Favouritism towards new customers

Past research shows that favouritism to either new or existing customers and any kind of differential treatment stimulates perceptions of unfairness in the disadvantaged customers (Nguyen and Simkin, 2009). Boulding et al. (2005) suggest that CRM activities create the potential for issues to arise that are related to the differential treatment of customers.

“So, my fiancé and I have had two [phones] on the same bill for over ten years now—we’re in the process of renewing. First, we were offered a tariff that cost

MORE than the advertised tariff for new customers, then, when he called to speak to them, he was offered a more fair deal on his line—and the advertised price on my line. No 10% off, and no extra data.”

This statement reflects the fact that a loyal service user feels unfairly treated when a new customer gets better deal. On the other hand, and very rarely, the opposite perception was observed; namely, that a new customer felt unfairly treated based on the comparison of the price that they were paying with what an existing customer was paying. This area has not been researched at all and research is required that sheds further light on how a new customer feels about an existing customer being offered a better price for the same deal.

b. Exploitation of vulnerability

In their recent publication that provided guidance for firms on the fair treatment of vulnerable customers (FCA, 2019, p.6), the FCA defined a vulnerable consumer as being “someone who, due to their personal circumstances, is especially susceptible to detriment, particularly when a firm is not acting with appropriate levels of care”. Vulnerability is driven by four key factors that include health (physical or cognitive disability), life events, resilience and capabilities. While considering the issue of the loyalty penalty, the UK’s Citizens Advice also specified that consumers in vulnerable situations who are older, living on lower incomes and less educated are more likely to face the loyalty penalty.

One of the service providers shared their experience by writing that:

“...so now I’m going to be left with no phone and my credit rating is now going to be affected because I’ll have to go and take out a brand new contract and it’s going to leave a search on my credit file. Thanks a bunch, Vodafone! And what makes it even worse [is the fact that] I suffer from autism and would be classed as a vulnerable customer!”

Likewise, another service user stated:

“EE is a disgrace! It continues to charge the cost of the handset after the contract has expired and the handset has been paid for. The majority of people who are being caught [out] by this are pensioners. How disgusting is that?... trying to make more money from those who can least afford it!”

This clearly indicates that vulnerable segments of the population are being ignored despite governing bodies constantly reminding firms of the need to address this issue as a matter of prime importance.

c. Loyalty penalty

Loyalty is one of the major strategies in consumer retention and relationship marketing as a whole. As a paying service user, we presume that a being a loyal customer—by virtue of its nature—guarantees better treatment from the service provider, both psychologically and financially. The cost that an existing loyal consumer has to pay for sticking with a particular service provider is defined as the ‘loyalty penalty’ in consumer marketing. Citizens Advice defines loyalty penalty as “the cost of being a long-standing customer compared to a new customer receiving the same product or service”, which is sadly yet another extremely popular practice in the service industry. The chief executive of Citizens Advice also stated that some of the biggest mobile phone providers are routinely overcharging their loyal customers (Citizen Advice, 2017).

Vast numbers of consumers across service sectors, including energy, insurance, banking and telecoms, are forced to be on uncompetitive agreements after they have spent a certain amount of time with their existing service provider. They end up paying a significantly higher price for a service than new customers would, especially after their initial agreement comes to an end.

In September 2018, Citizens Advice, which is a social welfare organisation, filed a super-complaint about the £4.1 billion loyalty penalty to the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA).

One of the service users included in this study wrote:

“...I’ve been with Vodafone for 10 years now and this is the worst I’ve seen it. Like I told one your managers this morning: if it wasn’t for my circumstances at the time, I wouldn’t have gone with Vodafone because the deal you offered me was disgusting. Especially when new customers were getting better deals. I understand you want to get new customers in, but you also need to look after existing ones.”

This statement clearly shows that this service user feels violation of their trust for having to pay more than new customers, and regarding that as incurring cost of being in a relationship with service provider for 10 years.

Another service user writes: *“...I’ve been a loyal customer for 6 years. 6 years and they treat you like crap.”*

Another service user feels that their trust has been broken. They wrote:

“I’ve been a Three customer now [for] long enough that I trusted you and you didn’t need a contract to keep me loyal. Now you tell me if I don’t sign up for another 12 months, you’ll raise my bill by over 25%. I wasn’t considering switching supplier until you pulled that stunt.”

With reference to social comparison theory, some loyal service users feel that they deserve incentives for having stayed loyal to their service provider. One writes: *“As it stands, there is no incentive to stay with you, as 10 years of my ‘loyalty’ ain’t worth much for you guys.”*

As highlighted in the literature review, loyalty—along with trust and commitment—is a major instrument of CRM. Service users expect some advantages in return for being loyal to the service provider. One of the service users wrote: *“Yep, just wanted a slightly better deal for being with you for over 10 years. Not asking for the world, just a slightly better thank you for being so loyal for 10 years kind of deal!”*. This reflects that the service users seek better advantage as a price of being loyal.

2. Data Exploitation

CRM revolves around coordinating and integrating data from different channels, enabling a firm to gain an insight about individual customers and thus enhancing firm profitability through individually customised products/services. Data, therefore, is a key component of a firm's CRM strategy that enables them to transform customer data into useful insights for value co-creation. Of course, handling a large amount of data can be difficult for firms with millions of service users, such as the Big Four MNOS in this study, as it is extremely important to consider the personal safety of consumers in relation to their private data. Data handling incorporates the notion of trust and information reciprocity, which suggests that consumers share their data and information in return for receiving customised offerings. Unfortunately, sometimes firms move away from the notion of reciprocity and use the available data to extract more value for the firm while providing less value for the customer. Realising that a violation of the principle of reciprocity has taken place induces feelings of unfairness and mistrust that may even end in relationship breakdown (Boulding et al., 2005). Sharing data with third parties without service users' explicit consent, using data for transactional marketing purposes that include upselling and cross selling, web behaviour tracking through the use of cookies and web beacons, the mishandling of data and overall data safety are only some of the identified forms of dark side behaviours in CRM in relation to data exploitation. It may be that there are several others that are going unnoticed; hence, it is crucial for researchers to explore this grey area of customer and relationship management.

Laws enforced by the European Union and the UK Data Protection Act 2018 control how individuals' personal information is used by organisations, businesses or the government itself and how these data are being processed. Under the Data Protection Act 2018 (Gov.uk, 2018), as a consumer, one has the right to know what information the government and other organisations store about you. This includes:

According to Data Protection Act 2018, one has right to:

Be informed about how your data is being used

Access personal data

Have incorrect data updated

Have data erased

Stop or restrict the processing of your data

Data portability (i.e., allowing you to get and reuse your data for different services)

Object to how your data is processed in certain circumstances

Despite the substantial penalties levied against violations of data protection rules, MNOs are nowhere near implementing them. Such failure, to ensure data safety, respect customer privacy and prevent the misuse of information, contradicts the idea of CRM implementation which results in unfairness perception in customers resulting to destroy relationship as a whole. Some of the dark practices identified in relation to data exploitation are discussed below.

a. Data misuse and mishandling

As mentioned above, customers share their personal data and information while trusting that their data will be handled properly and will not be misused for any ulterior motives. However, previous studies have found that firms are selling their customers' data to third-party brokers without the knowledge of customers. Similar experiences have also been observed in the present study.

The mishandling of customers' supplied data is another extremely important concern that the providers are disregarding. One of the service users states:

"...The issue is that someone from within your organisation has ordered themselves a SIM card on my account. Whilst they have done this, they have also taken it upon themselves to change some of the details on my account, which means I am unable to pass security to be able to discuss this problem

further. I'm really concerned as I am unsure as to whether or not this SIM card is still in use and as I'm unable to visit the store until next week. I currently have no way of speaking directly to Vodafone to resolve this issue. To my knowledge, it has been reported to the fraud team; however, I was due a call back from them today which hasn't taken place. So far, the staff from Vodafone have made me feel powerless and I am starting to feel like they have no interest in helping me solve this problem."

Similarly, MNOs are also found to be using their past service users' data, which is against the rules of erasing data. This may result in a company being hit with a penalty of thousands of pounds as a fine, according to the new GDPR policy. One of Vodafone's ex-service users writes:

"...I left Vodafone October 2017 after constant mistakes with my bill. I am still getting a monthly text and email with an amount on my bill that you cannot actually take. In my opinion, it is against data protection for you to hold this information. I have contacted you by phone and been into shops so many times since then, but this still continues."

Furthermore, another service user writes:

"I have been victim of a scam thanks to EE [after] they did not check the identity of the person at the store. EE opened an investigation and confirmed that it was fraud and [that] someone upgraded my account under my name..."

This either reflects that employees are not appropriately updating their databases or that there is a flaw in the process itself.

One service user writes:

"Just wondering if it is company policy to ask for my mate's number when discussing an upgrade? Supposedly to confirm what he had on his contract could be matched for me. Obviously didn't give his number, but surely that's not right?"

Furthermore, with regard to data protection regulations, companies are not supposed to make forceful and excessive numbers of offers through the use of telephone, fax, e-mail or any other media suitable for distance selling. It is also a form of trust violation that is viewed as being a dark side behaviour in relationship management as a whole.

b. Privacy invasion

Although there are a great deal of legal norms and policies in place when it comes to the use of consumers' data and privacy protection in business, and specifically in CRM system implementation, there have been cases of loopholes being exploited and users' privacy being invaded. In today's digital world, there has been an explosion in the use of spyware by firms to track customer behaviour and it has led to general distrust in online shopping and a desire for greater levels of consumer privacy than ever. To address such important public concerns, there are governing bodies like Information Commission Officer (ICO) in place who advocate the issues regarding information rights in the public interest and their personal data privacy. To control excessive the information sharing and behavioural tracking over the internet, ICO has placed specified rules on direct marketing, and this includes telephone and electronic marketing. Despite their efforts, in an investigation conducted by ICO in 2018, it was found that EE was sending direct marketing messages via SMS without service users' consent; this ended with the UK telecom giant being fined a sum of £100,000 (ICO, 2019).

As identified by Nguyen (2015), data exploitation is a current dark side of CRM and it is one that the present study also aims to address by identifying to what extent MNOs are practising it. Service users are seen to be raising concerns with regard to privacy invasion.

A service user writes:

“Can someone please action this? I've now received a bill from an account that you have allowed to be fraudulently created using my information. Do you not deploy fraud/identity checks?”

This is an extremely important issue that has been overlooked. A number of users made complaints related to similar issues:

“You keep sending marketing texts. When I complain, you claim it’s a data error that’s turned all my marketing preferences back on.”

“They have pestered me five times within the past 24 hours for no reason, continuously calling about a bill that was fully paid.”

“Can your marketing team stop calling me?! Multiple times a day. EVERYDAY. I am not interested and it’s literally harassment. Sick of it.”

“I would like to report that #threemobile violated my privacy and sent my SIM card to strangers [the strangers’ address is stated by the user...wanting me pay £226.34, which I did not use—but the stranger did!”

“I have tried refusing the call; I have tried blocking the number, but [I’m] still getting a call from them almost once a day... Normally while I am in work as well!”

On top of this, companies are also seen to be lacking control over their third parties misusing users’ data. MNOs work in collaboration with several clientele, ranging from internet suppliers to other third-party application companies, and they share their consumers’ data with these companies. It is extremely hard for service users to keep track of the third parties as they multiply in number.

“...I am highly disappointed by EE’s customer safety: there have been many complaints about this, and it hasn’t raised any concerns [on the part of] your company. I am definitely going to dig a little more about the relationship between EE and Bounce Game.”

Out of approximately 400 statements observed on this issue, users wrote that:

“I’m getting charges from a third party, only to get [the] blame for what’s going on. I didn’t subscribe to anything and the lady on the phone was so rude.”

“Some 3rd party company has been charging my account without my consent or knowledge until I checked my account.”

“I am currently on my third call—and on hold again—over the last three days [while] raising a dispute over scam text messages I have been charged for.”

Despite the penalties and fines that the MNO may have to pay, negligence over sensitive issues as such these will not only sink the existing customer relationship; it will also deter potential customers from joining the MNO.

3. Deceptive tactics

The practice of deception is not a new notion within the marketing arena. Deception was originally introduced by Gardner in 1975, when he described that any marketing tactics would be termed as being deceptive if marketers underlined the non-functional benefits of products or services. The vagueness of this definition risks putting every marketing tactics as deceptive, therefore Sher (2011, p. 104) redefined deception in marketing tactics as “if it intends to bring about consumer misconception by providing what the marketer believes is false evidence, omitting key evidence, or misrepresenting what the evidence means”. Based on this definition, this study clearly illustrates that the UK’s MNO are practising deceptive tactics through behaviours like false advertisements, over promising, providing misleading information, concealing information within small print, and so on.

Service users seem to be very aware of how service providers practice ambiguous tactics and of the fact that they use technicalities to conceal the facts. One of the service users states that:

“I’m not looking for technicalities; I’m looking for decency. I’d argue the policy is deliberately ambiguous [so] as to extract money from those who are unaware [that] they are being charged. I was at no point given any warning that I was

being charged for calls or even for missed calls; of course it is not in EE's interest to do so. £500 is a lot of money in return for very little. The policy also means if I was to travel to any other part of Europe and call the German number from there it wouldn't cost money, but if I was in the UK then it would. I can't see how this makes sense, other than it exploits a legislative loophole. My only option is to now ensure that EE doesn't profit from what is (technically legal or not) essentially stealing. I am not going to give in until I receive a satisfactory answer."

Similarly, service users have also called out service providers for deliberately making procedures complex. This includes switching barriers, termination complexity, complicated processes involved in refunds, and so on. These are all related to the concept of customer lock-in, as outlined by Payne and Frow (2013).

One user writes:

"The problem is [that] although it is OK to buy a device with a Pay Monthly 2-year contract, at the end of the 2-year term it is not straightforward to terminate the contract online. You [are] ask[ed] to contact [them] yourself in order to terminate a contract that has completed its 2-year term anyway. Unfair. Complicated."

Another service user also pointed out that service providers are using complex terminology that is hard to understand, specifically for vulnerable segments of the population. This is simply against the law, as outlined by the European Union, which states that contract terms must be drafted in plain and understandable language. Should any lack of clarity be identified, it will be concluded to be in the consumer's favour.

a. False advertising

False advertising includes the use of untrue, misleading or unverified evidence to promote products. This may include products' or services' capabilities being exaggerated, false claims, the use of false testimony, misleading health claims, and so on. This is done in order to persuade prospects to turn into customers: the purchase

decision made by a customer is primarily motivated by the information provided by a product/service advertisement.

Over the years, many big brands have been called out and fined for the practice of false advertising. For example, Kellogg's for claiming that their products benefit children's health; Nutella for claiming that their products are a healthy breakfast option; and Heinz for using false claims in their advertisements about using all-natural ingredients. Similarly, brands should avoid the practice of making exaggerated claims, which is a technique often known as 'puffery'. This includes making statements like 'UK's number one', 'the best in the world', 'most loved network', and so on, which lack adequate substantiation. Such subjective claims can mislead buyers into making a particular purchase decision; this has therefore been observed as being a dark behaviour within CRM practice. Despite the recognition of such practices and their severity, academics have not researched this area enough. False advertising has been perceived as one of the dark aspects of CRM, as its negative impacts destroy customer trust and lead them to withdraw from the relationship as a whole.

In this study, MNOs' exaggeration of their networks' capabilities was one of the most observed practices. A significant number of the service users pinpointed the fact that the quality of the network had been falsely advertised. One service user writes: *"it's taken me 10 mins to send this tweet on your network. Despite full signal and 4G. Can I get an email address to send my complaint? I want to leave with no fee's as you can't deliver the service you advertise."* Most recently 'Three' was called out by for false advertisement about their 5G network, which they were found to be "misleadingly" by using the words to mislead customers. They advertised their 5G service with a tagline "If it's not Three, it's not real 5G." ASA warned them not to use wordings that can mislead or misguide their customers (Jackson, 2020). Service users are observed to be quite aware of being misled by service providers.

Another service user writes: *"VodafoneUK's blatantly misleading advert after everyone's seen it is pointless. It's time to introduce a naughty step whereby regular offenders have to get TV ads approved before air until they can be trusted."*

b. Information asymmetry

Information asymmetry refers to a situation where there is an imbalance and inconsistency in the information that has been provided to customers; this may have an impact on their purchase decision, as well as on their post purchase decisions. This study observed noteworthy information asymmetry practices by MNOs and the service users are seen raising concerns over it. One service user writes:

“Which is correct? And if the newer and cheaper prices are the correct ones, please make your call centre aware of this. I’m presently unable to change my plan to 200GB per month for £60, because the call centre insists it’s £100.”

This can lead to service users withdrawing from a particular purchase decision.

c. Lack of transparency

A decade ago, customers would make purchase decisions merely based on how brands advertised their products or services; however, today’s market is a place that is full of smarter consumers (i.e., those who are more knowledgeable in addition to having an equal understanding of sellers’ marketing tactics). Likewise, the creation of value for consumers and its diffusion has shifted from a surface understanding of consumers’ perceptions of value (i.e., what influences perceived value) to a more complex construct—namely, perceived equity. This is also another key reason why businesses need to appreciate the importance of being transparent more than ever as Internet has made it very easy to compare what deals people are being offered. Based on the observation data, the MNOs’ failure to be transparent is clear. Lack of transparency is often intertwined with misleading customers through the practice of concealing information. For example, a service user writes:

“Just had a chat with EE’s support over hidden charges on my bill. Turns out every time I type ‘:)’ in a text I am being charged 50p “because emojis”. Their solution? a) Don’t type ‘:)’, b) Use WhatsApp instead, c) pay extra each month for a package [that] allows me to type ‘:)’.”

This is an issue related to companies providing customers with basic usage information, and it falls under consumers' right to be informed when signing a contract. This is more of a transparency issue than one related to a lack of information.

d. Misleading practices

Misleading, as a layman's term, must be one of the most used expressions observed during the data collection. In addition to using the term 'misleading', service users repeatedly used terms like 'deceptive', 'false' and 'confusing' in their comments. Researchers have defined all these terms to be different in terms of their meanings and the intention behind the practice; however, they are often used interchangeably by service users. In truth, the use of any strategy that can give an incorrect idea to service users and that makes them purchase a particular service is categorised as being the use of misleading tactics.

Firms are often seen to be using statements like 'limited time offer', which leads service users to panic buy.

e. Procedure complexity

Inconvenience is one of the major dark side behaviours observed in the present study. One of the studies conducted of Canadian mobile networks and the internet industry finds that service convenience is one of the major determinants of customer satisfaction (Cowell et. al., 2008); inefficient service convenience leads to deter customer relationship overall (Berry et. al., 2002). This is also one of the most observed behaviours in this research: there were several practices that seem to have been made deliberately complex merely in order to keep customers locked into their contracts. Customers wrote:

“Apologies for the novel [written] above, but I am ever hopeful that my marriage certificate, passport, confirmation email and hopefully a note on my order details online explaining the issue will be enough to get me my shiny new phone tomorrow....”

“Time to make it easier to cancel an existing contract. [S]pent 2 hours trying: our contract has not been used for some time and [we] never set up an online account. Sort it out!”

f. Fine print misuse

The fine print often implemented as part of the terms and conditions refers to an appended part of the terms and conditions that comprises details that are not incorporated within the main document. They may be placed as a footnote or in a separate file. Although the fine print includes important details, there is convincing evidence to indicate the fact that the majority of customers do not read the fine print. This was also identified in the quantitative survey in this study. This type of text is often regarded as the small print, and not reading it can be very costly as firms are often found to be sneaking important clauses into the small print of their terms and conditions. For example, network operators advertise their roaming services to be free, but the fine print indicates that minimum payments need to be made; thus, such fine print is likely to be misleading. This is perceived as being wrong and to have been deliberately implemented by the MNOs in order to maximise their profits.

One service user writes:

“Yes, you get people to put daft clauses in small print right at the bottom then try [to] rip people off. Your customer service is shocking and [and you provide] shocking signal.”

Some service users were found to be recommending that their fellow users or potential buyers should read the small print after realising that O2 was sneaking important information into its fine print. One user wrote:

“Read the small print folks. You’ll be stuck in a contract with terrible network coverage and nothing will be done to help you, as it states this in the contract. BEWARE.”

Even though the regulating laws state that the terms and conditions of the contract must be written in plain language that is easy to understand for anyone, firms are

found to be using complex terminology that exploits vulnerable segments of the population.

Another service user was seen to be challenging Vodafone on the fact that it was misleading buyers in relation to roaming charges through their use of fine print. This user replied to another service user's post by writing:

"Yes Tash, I'm still being charged for international calls despite being on GLOBAL roaming.... It is wrong for @VodafoneUK to have misleading small print."

This suggests that the user is being forced to continue paying for the roaming service that he used after he assumed it to be free; however, the fine print suggested something else entirely.

Another service user stated: *"Vodafone UK is selling a 5G plan but restricting download speed to 2 Mbps (small print)."*

Another service user pointed out that they had the right to be informed, by stating that: *"The really important stuff should be made clear right from the start if you were really honest!"*. Even though the service users are aware of the fact that important clauses might be hidden within the fine print, it seems that they do not bother to read it before signing the contract or even within their cooling off period. Such negligence on the part of the service users themselves causes them to be bound into an unwanted contract for a set period of time.

4. Employee Incompetency

The front-line staff in a service industry like MNOs act in the role of representing the firm's products/services, which is why the quality of their service is what defines customers' purchase decisions, customer satisfaction and their relationship with the brand as a whole. In parallel, the quality of employee empowerment in an organisation reflects the service quality that an employee can deliver. An informed employee can help service buyers to make an informed decision; however, if they are not well

informed the consequences can be detrimental. Some of the negative aspects include mis-selling, misinforming and/or forced selling, employee negligence that can affect customers' credit records, making false promises to service users, dishonesty, not providing enough information, and so on.

Employee empowerment helps to understand the role of an individual employee towards firm's mission, which boosts employees' willingness to deliver quality services and further leads to customer satisfaction. Therefore, it is extremely important for employees to be well trained and empowered, which will give them the required authority to carry out their jobs well.

In addition to a lack of employee competence and empowerment, this study identifies that the employees of the Big Four MNOs are also failing in relation to service recovery. Employees are seen to be lacking in empathy and responsiveness and to be acting dishonestly towards service users, despite the fact that past studies have shown that higher employee responsiveness and empathy during service recovery result in users' satisfaction, loyalty and retention—which are the instruments of successful customer relationship management. Some of the dark sides of relationship management, as seen in this study, that are the result of employee competency are discussed below.

a. Misinformation and forced selling

The observation data clearly reveals that even multi-millionaire companies like the Big Four MNOs are lagging behind in relation to empowering their employees in terms of training, product and service knowledge and their overall customer relationship management attitude. This all comes down to a lack of service encounter training. One of the customers writes:

“I actually went in store. I waited for around one hour, bearing in mind I had already paid a fee to upgrade of £240. After waiting one hour AFTER I HAD ALREADY PAID, they stated I was not due the upgrade until tomorrow. I have paid £240 [and] I'm paying extortionate prices per month and left the store with no phone. Ridiculous! I've sent various DMs and emails with no solutions, just

passing me onto other people. Is this an automated response? I have never been as misinformed in my life.”

This statement suggests that there is no centralised communication system in place that aligns the customer touchpoints. First of all, misinformation on eligibility to upgrade, following by taking payment for a product that's not even sold; such poor experience can offend anyone. Additionally, there was also no clear direction with regard to reaching a resolution. Such flaw in procedure can cost a company, both financially and in terms of the customer relationship.

Another service user adds:

“Bad experience and disappointment... To find out I have been mis-sold the product and, funny enough, the person does not work there anymore... I also loved the fact that the store doesn't have a manager at the moment and consultants were trying to pass the bucket.... Is this a joke?”

Similarly, another service user was given inconsistent information that not only caused them inconvenience but also caused them to question brand's trustworthiness. They write:

“So unprofessional. Well after an hour and a half of waiting I got told I can't upgrade until the end of August, but when I went in in June, they just said pop in in August. So that was a waste of time and my day! Fuming.”

b. Employee negligence

The study identified a range of employee negligence that ranges from a staff member simply ignoring a customer who is seeking support to making mistakes that can damage a service user's credit rating. Similarly, there were significant numbers of existing service users who were disappointed by the lack of empathy and sensitivity shown by their service providers/employees. Empathy is one of the major instruments in delivering service quality. Furthermore, if there has been any form of service failure, employees' empathetic behaviour can turn around the whole experience as a whole. One service user writes:

“OMG EE are dreadful—over-charging [and providing] misleading information. What a bunch of robbers—then you spend over 40 mins on the live chat to be told, ‘Oh sorry, you have to call us.’ Unbelievable.”

Such disregard of a service user’s time and effort can be extremely frustrating for them and it can unfortunately damage the relationship.

Furthermore, another service user writes:

“For sure, I will not accept this. If I have to go to court for this I will, because so far I’ve been mis-sold a new contract with misleading information, I’ve had hidden charges placed on my account and it seems they have been charging me a fortune for making calls and [sending] messages inside the UK. I need this sorted.”

Being ignored by frontline staff is one of the most observed behaviours in this study. One service user writes:

“My wife went into EE in Taunton today. All she wanted was a ‘top up’: she waited her turn and the guy came to her and on hearing it was only a top up, he told her someone else would do it and went off to sell expensive phones to customers... He then ignored her and still no one came to [help] her. She left very angry. So, is this the way your staff treat a retired lady?”

This comment not only highlights a lack of customer care; it also points out the issue of vulnerability, which was discussed in an earlier section of this chapter.

Another service user writes: *“Your computer generated ‘replies’ achieve nothing.”* This highlights the problems associated with the omission of a key dimension of service quality model, i.e., empathy.

Furthermore, another service user writes:

“Spent 45 mins on hold to you this morning and still couldn’t speak to anybody, can’t log into my online account and neither [can I] live chat!! This needs to be sorted can someone please respond! What a joke EE are!!! They mess up and yet try to blame the customer!! Maybe if the staff actually listened to the customer and weren’t so quick to get the customers off the phone then there wouldn’t be so many issues!!!”

c. Lack of information

Through their online comments, service users have also brought it to the researcher’s attention that the employees involved in customer service or sales are not given enough training both in terms of knowledge about the product or service itself and what is involved in good customer service. They also seem to lack knowledge about the internal processes of the company.

Firstly, there is a lack of information shared with buyers. One customer states: *“My last invoice in July was charging me £2.50 for the price of the SIM card. They never [mentioned] this charge.”* This reflects that the employees in sales are failing to explain all the necessary details while selling a contract. The lack of information can result in uninformed purchase decisions being made, which can result in consumers’ feeling of that their trust has been violated.

Another service user writes: *“Your overseas team doesn’t have proper knowledge or experience.”* This indicates that the service user was not convinced by the quality or the quantity of information provided by the customer care employee over the telephone. The service user mentions the ‘overseas team’ because customer care operatives in the UK service industry are often outsourced from overseas call centres. Even in such cases, it is extremely important that the employees are well informed so that they can share quality information and knowledge with the service users.

Furthermore, it is extremely necessary for service users to be informed about the end of their contract period and to be given a choice as to whether they want to continue their service with the service provider. The UK Government’s Consumer and Marketing Authority (CMA) has clearly stated that “Auto-renewal must be

explicitly agreed to by the consumer when signing up; not applied on a default basis and consumers should be able to take the contract without auto-renewal” (CMA, 2019, p. 7). Despite such policies being in place, service users are still being taken advantage of through auto renewals and a lack of information. One customer wrote that:

“Customer service should have contacted me to say that my contract was coming to an end and ask me did I want to renew, or did I want to pay SIM only and keep the phone I’ve just paid off...”

d. Dishonesty and violation of psychological contract

Conceptualised by Schein (1978), the notion of a psychological contract is that it is an unwritten agreement between a firm and an individual, an employee or a consumer, that is built upon an expectation of reciprocity and obligation between the two parties who are in a relationship exchange. This agreement is informal, develops during the period of the relationship and is immensely subjective. Consumers have expectations of firms as a result of using their products or services, and they see the time and effort they have expended as being an investment and seek out the same level of reciprocity from the firm. A violation of this agreement results in the customer making an emotional and subjective evaluation and feeling that the firm has failed to meet their expectations. This study has found that issues regarding the violation of the emotional contract are being raised by customers.

A psychological contract is fundamental part of the service industry, particularly as a result of its intangibility, dependence on trust and commitment and its subjective nature. MNOs need to take into consideration that a psychological contract of trust and commitment is the backbone of good relationship marketing.

5. Financial exploitation

Incorrect billing, being overcharged and the continuation of charges despite being at the end of a contract are not unheard of within the UK MNO industry. On several occasions the appropriate governing bodies have charged operators to the tune of

millions of pounds as a penalty for wrongdoing and as a warning to other potential practitioners of such behaviours. However, these behaviours continue.

Some forms of financial exploitation are not merely firms' fault. There are a set of unwritten responsibilities that service users are to be accountable for, which include educating themselves about the price that they are paying, familiarising themselves with the terms and conditions, checking bills, contacting the right department at right time for after sales service, and so on. A lack of understanding with regard to the pricing when purchasing a service or signing a contract, negligence in timely communication if any errors are identified and a failure in being vigilant about bills are some of the activities that are prevalent amongst service users. Failure to adhere to such responsibilities can result in financial exploitation that not only leads them to over pay; it can also end up ruining their credit history. The extent of credit and borrowing in the service industry runs deep and the consequences of failing to make timely payments creates an equal amount of damage. And possibly due to the severity of damage on their credit profile, service users are seen taking their finance related complaints to powerful regulatory bodies like Ofcom and Ombudsman, if their complaints aren't timely addressed by their service providers.

One of the statements made by customers was that:

“[A]fter 10 months of getting my bill wrong, calling me a liar and having the worst customer service ever, now you charge me £8.34 for a late payment fee when my bills have been paid on time!! Never known such money grabbing horrible people.”

This statement highlights that there are multiple aspects of financial dark behaviours. Service failure is not only an issue: service providers are failing to address complaints and to manage RM at all. It is the service provider's ethical responsibility to avoid such practices at all costs or to at least direct customers towards a solution when this is required. Contract auto rolling and auto renewal used to be one of the most practiced dark behaviours however, regulators have now put a policy in place whereby service providers must alert their service users when their initial contract deal ends.

a. Bill shock

Being overcharged is not unheard of in the telecommunications industry and, more specifically, by mobile network operators. The governing authorities have been heavily fining MNOs each year; however, this practice seems to be continuing unaffected. For instance, EE was fined £2.7 million in 2017 for breaking a fundamental billing policy; this was repeated in 2018, and the operator ended up paying £6.3 million in fines (Ofcom, 2017a, Ofcom, 2018). Bear in mind that these are only the penalties for levying excessive charges when customers terminate their contracts early. Virgin Media was also charged £7 million as a penalty for failing to protect their consumers' rights. Despite the fact that businesses are being fined millions of pounds, these practices are ongoing, which is clearly seen in this study.

Bill shock also includes hidden charges being made and other issues related to incorrect billing despite service user's several attempts to inform the MNOs. One of the service users writes: *"Really disappointed in @EE and their hidden charges + sudden increase in prices."* The issue of sudden increases in price will be discussed as an individual dark side in a later section. Another user writes: *"I have never said yes to any subscription with them and I have been charged £2.50 a week for it and so far 85 pounds in total. Outrageous!"*

Furthermore, the MNOs are found to be continuing to bill customers even after a service user has terminated their service contract with the service provider. One service user writes:

"You are still trying to charge us for a contract we ended.... months [ago] in January. Every month since they tell us we owe nothing and then they try to bill us again."

This not only reflects a flaw in an internal process but also the lack of complaint handling.

Despite the service users reaching out and communicating about the error, the continuation of incorrect billing suggests either negligence or flaw in the communication integration process of the company. Furthermore, this also

demonstrates the service provider's failure in adopting knowledge management and organisational learning strategies. Based on the theory of CRM, organisations are expected to convert data, information, feedback and complaints gathered from their service users and to transform them into knowledge for the betterment of the relationship, along with increasing product value.

b. Mid-contract price rise

UK mobile networks have been increasing the cost of their existing mobile phone contracts in line with yearly inflation, based on the national retail price index (RPI) and consumer price index (CPI). Such price increases mean that over a 24-month contract period, a £50 per month contract can cost around £53.50 per month. Even though the governing bodies have put policies in place about adequately informing consumers about any price rises within the existing contract period, practitioners seem to be failing to adhere to this, thus leaving service users in shock when they see their bills are different to what was initially contracted. After Ofcom realised that many consumers were the victim of this issue, it passed a law in order to safeguard consumers against unexpected mid-contract price rises; however, service users are still the victim of these.

One service user writes: *"I won't be staying with O2 as my bill was meant to be £45PM and the vat increases it to £53PM. Absolutely outrageous."* This statement suggests that the service provider failed to provide adequate information about the price of the contract, which can have a great impact on vulnerable segments of the population. Similarly, another service user writes: *"How can it be right that @VodafoneUK can increase your monthly bill by 3.6% when you have signed a fixed contract????? Come on!"* This statement suggests the users' disbelief in the company's practices.

Some service users are also seen to be aware of price rises; however, they want to be treated more fairly and better in return for agreeing to pay in excess of what they signed on to pay. One service user writes: *"I didn't bitch when there was a 33% rise in my monthly costs [but] I have been with you about 5 years and this is how you treat me?"* On the other hand, some other service users were seen to be entirely unaware of mid-contract price rises. For example, one service user writes: *"I called today to enquire why my bill has been increased by over £10."* In addition, another user

indicated that information about mid-plan price rises was included in the small print, which made them feel cheated. They write: *“Stop sneaking plan increases into the small print of contracts! My next, and all future contracts, will be with companies who guarantee not to have mid-plan increases.”*

Another service user questioned the lack of adequate information provided while signing the contract, while also questioning the logic behind the price rise policy itself. They write:

“How is this fair? My wages aren’t increasing by 3.6% so how can you justify such an increase on my 2-year contract? I agreed to a contract with your company based on the price you gave me and that is what I expect to pay for the full term of that contract! #unfair.”

All of these statements clearly suggest that MNOs are failing to provide clear and adequate information regarding the price of their contracts and the issue of mid-contract price rises, which is against Ofcom’s policy. Most importantly, it is damaging the customer relationship as a whole.

c. Price discrepancy

Price discrepancy has been outlined as one of the dark sides in Nguyen’s research (2015). Although the issue of price discrepancy has been well discussed among academics, it remains an extremely prevalent practice in the industry, including in food, retail, telecommunications and MNOs. The inaccuracy of information in terms of pricing leads to breakdowns in customer trust that can result in customer withdrawal. A number of customers complained about this issue online:

“When I upgrade, I’m phoning O2 definitely and not upgrading in the shop because I always get [offered] an over[ly] expensive tariff and price plan.”

“So just saw an ad pop up on my timeline: 18gb for £20 for a SIM only upgrade. I recently upgraded in March to SIM only; 5gb for £20. [I] feel like I’ve been ripped off.... I can’t even upgrade to it. If I want to upgrade my current tariff I have to pay £35 a month for 18gb. Not impressed.”

“£53 a month for an S9 with £39.99 upfront, when I can use a third party and enter into a contract with O2 for the same phone at £40 a month, [with] no upfront cost and a data difference of 26GB. How can third party provider offer these deals but you can’t offer them to pre-existing customers??”

“If I go to a third party’s web site, like mobile.co.uk, I can get a much better deal on a standard O2 contract as a brand-new customer. O2 will then pay mobile.co.uk commission for a brand-new connection, which is between £50 and £200. Why not just offer the best deal directly?”

“I was going to buy a SIM only from the 3 website. [The] offer price was £15 but when I put it in my basket it’s suddenly £16. EXPLANATION?”

“They quoted us over the phone (apparently a recorded conversation) one price, promised to email confirmation, which they didn’t send, and then sent via email a different price [that was] £15 per month dearer.”

6. Service Quality Failure

It has also been found that some of the dark behaviours overlap with the concepts of service failure and recovery failure. This includes poor communication, poor network signal, negligence on the part of staff, employees’ false promises, and so on. Avoiding these issues is vital for keeping the customer relationship intact.

It has been observed that the service providers offer what customers perceive as frustratingly poor service merely as a result of negligence and a lack of care from employees. This involves activities like misinforming service users, not giving full information, prioritising customers who will guarantee them higher revenue or commissions, ignoring less profitable segments, not taking responsibility when required, behaving rudely in store encounters or over the telephone, and so on. Other than the staffs dealing on telephone and in physical stores, service users are seen extremely frustrated with the staffs behind the keyboard who are responsible in dealing with the public social media messages and comments. Some service users have

called out service providers for using automated and robot-like messages highlighting lack of sensitivity on their replies while some pointed that their messages are being ignored and 'not read'. Lack of empathy and lack of adequate service training for staff were some of the issues raised by the service users; these are critical definers of service quality that further lead to satisfaction and, in general, a better customer relationship. The issues identified as dark sides in relation to service quality failure will be discussed in detail below.

a. Poor customer service

Understanding the customers' experience and customer service is key to relationship marketing and CRM. Quality customer service is an added value that not only generates brand loyalty but also creates opportunities to acquire new customers through positive word of mouth. In a digital world like today's, it is increasingly important to offer an excellent quality of customer service; however, this is not what the observation data reflected. MNOs seem to be failing to deliver the expected level of customer service, which has resulted in a lot of negative word of mouth and customers' withdrawal from their relationship with the brand as a whole.

Paying attention to customers, showing a willingness to help customers by demonstrating adequate knowledge of core products or services, providing accurate information, and so on, are key to enhancing customer trust and reassuring them of the quality of the service. In the present study, a lack of interest in customers, a lack of employee knowledge and the absence of empathy were amongst the most mentioned negative experiences identified by the service users; these are major issues when it comes to delivering service quality (Zeithmal, Parsuraman and Berry, 1990). One of the service users writes:

"I would like to focus on your Brent Cross team—the most useless and unprofessional team I have met in my whole life. You can't simply come there with a problem; you will be dismissed and asked to call customer service instead. [It's a s]hame your employees don't understand [that] they all represent customer service."

This statement alone reflects that the elements of service quality are being significantly ignored.

Additionally, people were observed to be frustrated with the telephone customer service on offer. Service users identified that the telephone customer care staff lacked adequate knowledge, acted rudely and were also disinterested in helping on several occasions. One service user writes:

“Utterly disgusted with EE’s customer service: totally rude, arrogant and unhelpful. I did not get my issue sorted out and have been left with a nasty taste in my mouth. I would not recommend anyone I know to use EE. Thanks for a wonderful experience. Not!!”

With regard to social media platforms, one service user posted about service staff ignoring private messages. They wrote:

“You do not bother to read private messages. You never take anything seriously. You treat me with disdain and contempt. You assume me to be stupid. You say this can be ‘fed back’. That translates to me as passed around for a laugh, then swept under the carpet. Your computer generated ‘replies’ achieve nothing.”

When various platforms are in place, regardless of the volume of queries and comments received, it is the responsibility of the service provider to respond to customers’ queries on each and every platform. There is also a need for service providers to integrate them, as there are times when a customer tries to reach out to the service provider through various means of communication and they can get frustrated if they have to repeatedly talk about their problems on different platforms.

Similarly, some service users were also found to be dissatisfied with tangible issues, which is another dimension of service quality. One service user questioned the lack of decency in the uniform that the staff were wearing, in addition to discussing the facilities within the store. They write: *“I never knew it was part of their uniform to wear*

their jeans halfway down their legs with their boxers hanging out: looks horrid and so unprofessional.”

b. False promises/inadequate service value

Past studies have pointed out that effective communication is a key element of customer satisfaction that leads to customer loyalty. The inaccuracy of information therefore reduces service quality, and this seems to be extremely prevalent amongst the MNOs despite the fact that there are laws and policies in place that declare that a trader is liable to compensate the customer if they fail to deliver as promised. In this study, service users were found to be extremely dissatisfied with the false promises received from service employees, and specifically over the telephone and in social media communication.

MNOs are mostly called out for over promising and under delivering. Some of the activities that they engage in include putting customers' calls on hold for more than an hour, promising a call back and not delivering within the given time, promising a solution and failing to provide one, and so on. Some customers were found to be waiting for more than a week after having been promised that they would receive a call back within 24 hours. One service user posts:

“I've been promised a phone call in the next 24 hours 4 times now, [and] each time it has been 2–3 days apart. Then I've asked to speak to a manager and all I get promised is a call back.”

Another wrote: *“They said they would get back to me in 72 hours; now, nearly 2 weeks later—still no call from them.”*

Another service user writes: *“Absolutely disgusting service from @O2. Still people can't get through to me after they said they would move my number across. 4 phone calls and not one person got back to me as promised!”*

Actions as such raises question the reliability and credibility, of the service provider as a whole as they fail to provide the promised service accurately. Furthermore, some

of the service users were also promised a refund that the service providers failed to deliver. One frustrated service user writes:

“I was told again and again that the refund would reach me within 5 days. Again, and again [you said] that you [were] so sorry [and] would help right away. [!] chased every week. 5 weeks later? NO REFUND. Today, I am told again that the refund will reach me by Thursday... What is it? Is this a game? Mess around until your customer is fed up? It's only £25!! Sort it out!”

7. Service users' behavioural intentions

According to the TRA model, an individual's intentions are a function of their attitudes towards the behaviour. Service users react on realising that dark behaviours are being practiced by service providers. When the service users realise that they are in a disadvantaged position, they assume that voicing their frustration, spreading negative word of mouth or retreating from the relationship exchange with the service provider as a whole will be more of an advantage to them than continuing the relationship as it is.

Based on the observation data, the researcher identifies three kinds of dark behavioural intentions that service users seem to be practising in such situations. These will be discussed in detail below. As this study is focused on examining dark sides, and negative behavioural practices in particular, it has also observed service users' behavioural intentions when they are driven by negative emotions; primarily anger and aggression. The quantitative data reveals that that service users' responses range from simply 'letting go' to a 'negative call to action'. This is also validated by the quantitative data gathered in this study. Some service users were seen to be using foul language when talking to social media platform advisors, engaging in personal attacks, making racist remarks and writing emails to the CEO of the company. Some of these activities were identified as the dark sides of CRM that are practiced by customers in a previous study undertaken by Nguyen (2011).

The nature of the digital age has created an opportunity and need for service providers to engage with their service users through online brand communities and social networking sites as a modern marketing strategy, instead of relying entirely on

conventional marketing strategies (Chan et al., 2014). Although there have been numerous claims of there being positive results to be gained from consumer-brand engagement, such engagement may not consistently result in positive value co-creation; rather, value co-destruction may occur at certain times (Li, Juric and Brodie, 2018; Smith, 2013). Value co-destruction, the negative equivalent of value co-creation, is the situation when an original idea behind the relationship process is ignored and that use of resources between two parties result into a rather damaging relationship. The negative engagement can be either intended or accidental. An intentional negative engagement is when a consumer makes an effort to harm the brand and therefore advises fellow consumers, both potential and existing, about the perceived dark sides of the brand. Despite this being a remarkably prevalent concern, extremely limited numbers of studies (Brodie et al., 2013; Hollebeek and Chen, 2014) have recognised the damaging, negative and unfavourable side of consumer engagement. Thus, this study intends to explore and identify the dark sides of CRM.

a. Anger and use of foul language

Past studies have shown that the realisation of violation of moral conduct is what leads to anger. Service users' anger are often instigated by service failure. When a service user realises that their service providers are misusing their data, levying extra charges beyond the contracted prices, failing to address complaints in an appropriate manner, ignoring legitimate enquires, offering better deals to new customers, lacking empathy, hiding important information within small print, and so on, it is highly likely that these service users will feel emotionally cheated on. Based on the TRA model, service users' belief that they are being cheated creates an attitude of revenge; this causes the service users to behave in an aggressive way. They may not always end up withdrawing from the relationship, but their behaviour may extend to deliberately harming the reputation of the service provider.

Consumers' use of foul language and abuse was identified as one of the dark sides of CRM by Nguyen et al. in their study (2015). By virtue of human nature, we tend to express aggression when we realise that we have been receiving less than what we have paid for. Service users' anger is therefore a result of perceived inequality and the violation of a psychological contract. A study of consumer anger recognised three forms of consumer anger; namely, broken promises, unfair treatment and expressed

hostility, which can lead to consumer decisions that extend as far as terminating the relationship with the service provider (Funches, 2011). These three forms of anger have been clearly observed in this study, in which the researcher identified that service users' anger turned into dark behaviours on a number of occasions. The researcher observed service users' anger through their use of phrases like "absolutely fuming", "joke of a company", "irresponsible", "ridiculous", "cheaters", "liars", and so on. Furthermore, they were also observed to be using the relevant emojis to express their fury.

As suggested by Antonetti (2017), consumer anger in marketing takes one of two forms: problem-focused anger and vengeful anger. The repetition of negative experiences is what results in vengeful anger, which causes service users to become focused on taking revenge and hurting the service provider in some way; problem-focused anger results from the need to gain an explanation or solution to the problem that has been experienced. The consequences of this form of anger range from service users seeking a simple apology to demanding costly compensation. The full range of responses was clearly observed during the observation in this study.

For example, one service user writes: *"Spend less on fancy adverts and more on answering your customer service lines. 30 mins on hold to report a lost phone—are you kidding?"* The anger expressed in this statement is legitimate, and the statement clearly shows that the person is seeking resolution.

There were also some examples of users' vengeful anger. One service user writes:

"You do not bother to read private messages. You never take anything seriously. You treat me with disdain and contempt. You assume me to be stupid. You say this can be 'fed back'. That translates to me as—passed around for a laugh, then swept under the carpet. Your computer generated 'replies' achieve nothing."

Some service users were also found to be aiming to harm their service provider's reputation. One person writes: *"Will be reporting you to Ofcom @EE, upselling stuff to*

my Mrs with no clarity and hidden charges. Will be in the local papers too.” Such issues, if not resolved in time, will put the firms’ reputation in jeopardy.

From what has been observed in this study, companies are practising denial strategies rather than acknowledging the issues and moving towards a resolution. Service providers therefore need to identify the type of anger that customers are experiencing and resolve the problem in an appropriate way. They must also accept the fact that not all forms of anger can be dealt with in the same way. Furthermore, service providers need to acknowledge that anger is not always a relational hazard; rather, it can be leveraged as strategy by which to understand problems more deeply and they can act accordingly in a way that results in the constructive re-establishment of a positive relationship.

b. Withdrawal from the service

Failure to meet an expectation or any form of service failure can result in service users retreating from a relational exchange with their service providers. Several decades ago, a study conducted by Kelley, Hoffman and Davis (1994) in the retail industry identified that service failure is the key determinant of consumers’ switching behaviour. Although switching behaviour is one of the key elements in customer retention and relationship management, not many studies have focused solely on consumer service withdrawal and switching behaviour intentions. A study by Srivastava and Sharma (2013) revealed that satisfaction in relation to service quality is a measure by which to prevent consumers’ switching behaviour; this was also revealed in one of the recent studies conducted in the mobile industry in the Malaysian market context (Nikhashemi, Valaei and Tarofder, 2017). It highlighted that product quality is one of the major factors that determine consumers’ switching behaviour.

The present study reveals several factors that lead service users to terminate their relationship with the brand. These include lack of credibility, poor customer service, poor experience with the brand overall, lack of empathy during service encounters, misinformation, billing issues, and so on. Some service users were withdrawing from a relationship exchange with a service provider after being with the MNO for more than 25 years. Most of these withdrawals were the result of one or multiple service failures. One service user writes: *“Can’t believe after nearly two decades’ journeying*

[together]... I'm leaving after the awful experience I had." Another adds: *"People PLEASE, PLEASE find a different service provider! I will as soon as my contract is done!!!"*

A lack of empathy and sensitivity seem to be another reason why service users terminate their relationship with their MNO. As suggested by service quality theory, empathy is one of the major elements that define service quality and enable companies to retain consumer loyalty. This was found to be extremely low in all of the Big Four MNOs.

Understanding consumers' switching behaviour is a crucial component of firms' retention and CRM strategies as a whole. Therefore, negligence in relation to such important aspects reflects that the MNOs are moving backwards, shifting their focus from customer retention towards customer acquisition only.

c. Negative word of mouth

Word of mouth (WOM) is an increasingly important marketing strategy, given the increasing impact of online reviews and online communities. WOM, whether negative or positive, influences purchasing intention. Emergence and increasing use of internet has increased the impact of more than ever; people turn to their social media platforms to share their service experiences, both positive and negative. It is important for service providers to realise that negative WOM impact faster and harsher than positive ones (East, Hammond and Lomax, 2008). One of the service users writes:

"To begin with, I will make sure I never hold a contract with the network again and let everyone I know [learn about] the character of the company. I will continue to use social media to spread the word. I appreciate you want to hand me off to the service team hidden from public view, but I am not going to give in until I receive a satisfactory answer."

This statement embodies a newer concept in WOM; namely, passive aggressive cynicism. A study of e-WOM conducted by Amezcua and Quintanilla (2016) introduced cynicism from a marketing perspective, and stated that it is a coping mechanism where consumers feel a sense of suspicion (Chylinski and Chu, 2010) and act defensively in

response to the perceived concealed behaviours of service providers. Negative WOM extends into cynicism when consumers, who are suspicious of the actual motives of the service providers, attack the brand as a whole; and also appeal others to act against what is being portrayed by the movement (Chylinski and Chu, 2010). Amezcua and Quintanilla (2016) further distinguished between different forms of cynicism based on their degree of severity: posts that embody the slightest element of cynicism are referred to as 'skeptical' and, the more negative and harmful they become as they grow, they turn into 'passive aggressive' and the more extreme 'warrior' form of eWOM.

This study also identifies several forms of word of mouth. People were seen to be spreading negative word of mouth about the MNOs. Some of the statements observed were:

"I am going to blog on LinkedIn and every major consumer forum until you sort this out."

"Off to various social media sites to warn people about Vodafone."

"Definitely avoid these scammers."

"EE does not deserve loyal customers. Do not use."

"Don't go with O2. You will be trapped. Worst company."

One of the service users writes: *"The amount of negativity on this page alone should be enough to stop anyone signing up with this company and any existing customers [from] renewing with them when their contracts end."* This statement clearly shows that the service provider is neglecting customer feedback that comes in the form of complaints, and overall failing to transform the customer information into knowledge, which is against the fundamentals of CRM.

5.4 Conclusion of the Chapter

This chapter presents the research results and overall discussion. The purpose of this chapter is to present the pragmatic findings in order to address the gap identified in current literature with regard to the dark sides of CRM. This is done through the discussion of the research findings, which make contributions in both theoretical and methodological terms. These include managerial implications for CRM, relationship management and customer management.

It is imperative for service providers to implement appropriate measures to prevent such misbehaviours and to enforce effective two-way communication. This is because the reach of the internet and social media is powerful than ever, and the influence of aggressive comments published on social media platforms is equally formidable. Although there have been several studies of the pros, cons and effectiveness of word of mouth in relationship marketing, not enough of them have explored negative WOM and its influence in the modern social media age.

Based on the interpretation of the observation data, it appears that the comments made by service users are being treated as only comments or complaints by the management of MNOs, and they do not take the opportunity to understand them more deeply or to analyse and implement them in reaching long-term solutions. Being vigilant, empathetic and extremely responsive is key in service marketing, and especially given the rise of social media and the aggressiveness of its usage by consumers.

Next, the researcher identified the fragmentation in integration of communication channels and involved internal processes. There are several ways that consumers are getting in touch with service providers in the attempt to find solutions to problems; however, there seems to be a lack of integration, which can have profound consequences. For example, a service user closed, finalised and settled their contract over the telephone. However, a failure of the MNO to communicate with the finance department lead to damage to the service user's credit history. Such a flaw in procedures can result in severe damage, ranging from the termination of the buyer-seller relationship to the destruction of the service provider's reputation as a whole. Even though a successful CRM strategy calls for all customer touchpoints and service encounter points to be integrated, UK MNOs seem to be ignoring this and failing both in relation to their internal communications and information integration.

Earlier research carried out by Malthouse and his fellow researchers sketched how organisations are lacking control over social media message dispersion, big and unstructured data sets, privacy, data security, the reduction in qualified manpower, measuring the ROI of social media marketing initiatives, strategies for managing

employees, integrating customer touch points and content marketing (Malthouse et.al., 2013). These problems still seem to be extremely prevalent.

The emergence of social media and the changing culture has given rise to social comparisons like never before. It has given a huge basis of judgement. What users hear and see on social media and in online communities helps shape their perceptions about network providers. Over the period of their relationship with a firm, the customer builds knowledge about how the firm operates, their practices and priorities. Similarly, the customer also becomes more aware of their specific needs with the brand itself and the pattern of changes. The duration of the relationship enables the service user to form an opinion of the firm's behaviour, objectives and treatment of its customers, which will shape the service user's future behavioural intentions. Along with the self-comparison and social comparison concepts of justice theory, this study has identified several service failures that are rooted in the concept of interactional justice failure. While service firms emphasise the fact that customer communication is key to their business, the lack of the major element of communication, i.e., empathy, is crucial to both relationship and service quality.

It has been noted that a higher level of recommendations lead to positive perceptions while higher levels of negative word of mouth lead to lower purchase intentions. Therefore, it is crucial for service providers to try to minimise negative word of mouth by providing long-term solutions through complaint management. Thus, the researcher identifies that a service recovery process is vital for MNOs.

The findings, which have been interpreted through both quantitative and qualitative data analysis, identify that service users are aware of the dark side behaviours being practiced in the name of CRM that can cost the customer relationship. The aim of this research was to identify whether service users are aware of the dark side behaviours being practiced by service providers. It has been found that although the majority of service users are not aware of the existence of dark practices, 21.81 percent of respondents are aware of these hidden behaviours and 19.15 percent of respondents have feelings of being unfairly treated. This reflects the fact that service providers' knowledge about their service users not being aware of this issue is what encourages them to continue engaging in such unfair practices. Therefore, it is extremely important

for academics and researchers to explore this neglected area and to give it increased visibility.

The service users who are aware of their relationship being taken advantage of by their service providers also indulge in dark behaviours. These include the expression of aggression, cynical word of mouth and their withdrawal from the service relationship.

Service quality has been identified as a major factor of purchase decision, and service providers are failing to deliver the promised service quality. 31.38% of the respondents said that their purchase decision is affected by 'quality of service'. Service providers seem to trap service users into making a purchase decision through false advertisements. The realisation that they are not getting their perceived value and broken trust are what breaks the buyer–seller relationship. Additionally, a lack of complaint handling and management, incompetent employee behaviour and service recovery strategies are also major factors that damage the service provider–user relationship. For instance, one of the service users went to a store to confirm that their initial had been paid off; however, they were still receiving the contracted monthly bill. This user wrote: *"... at the point of cancelling in store, my final bill amount for that month had already been paid. The agent on the phone confirmed this and that my account would expire on the 30th May and that no further payment was due."* An issue like this is the result of either employee negligence or a lack of information and process integration; both could lead to the credit record of an individual being destroyed. This example paints a clear picture of how harsh the consequences of both employee negligence and a lack of information integration can be.

The next chapter will discuss the recommended framework by which to address these dark side behaviours of CRM. Further, the next chapter will also explain the limitations of this study and provide guidance for future research.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

The last chapter discussed the findings of the study in detail. The researcher identified seven categories of dark side behaviours, comprised of 23 activities, that are being practiced by the big four MNOs in the UK. The identification of these categories and activities are based upon service users' perceptions. The researcher implemented a mixed methods approach to answer the research questions. While the quantitative data was analysed using SPSS, the qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis using NVivo software.

This chapter will focus on the practical implications and making recommendations regarding how to eliminate the identified dark sides of CRM. The objective is to answer the following research question:

- What recommendations can be made regarding the use of transparent and fairer CRM behaviours?

Based on the discussion in the last chapter, it has been recognised that it is perceived inequality, unfair treatment and the lack of service recovery strategies that mainly hinder the relationship between the MNOs and both their potential service users and their existing service users. The lack of information integration, flaws in the communication process and the lack of employee empowerment were clearly observed. Many dark side behaviours were observed to be caused by a lack of strategies around knowledge management and organisational learning. It is therefore crucial for the MNOs to acknowledge the need to implement necessary resources and efforts to train, educate and empower both offline and social media customer-facing employees and to integrate their communication channels.

Furthermore, MNOs were also seen to be failing to convert the significant amounts of data coming to them in the form of reviews, complaints and feedback from service users. In an era where firms invest millions of pounds in research and development, MNOs have the opportunity to analyse the data that is readily available via their online communities and social media platforms; however, the findings of this research reflect

otherwise. The MNOs are failing to handle complaints effectively, which is resulting in harm to their customer relationship, as well as their reputation as a brand, through negative word of mouth. The researcher therefore recommends them to revisit their knowledge management strategy.

The idea of knowledge management is incorporated in one of the processes; namely, the information management process, and Payne and Frow (2013) have explained it in terms of addressing issues related to privacy invasion and information misuse. The researcher understands that there is a need for the MNOs to focus on their knowledge management process, as it is an individual process that is related more to organisational learning through the data and information collected from service users. Based on the findings of this research, the researcher agrees with the statement by Buttle: “many companies claim to be customer-centric, [but] few are” (Buttle, 2004, p. 45).

Further, the issue of the significance of customer data and value co-creation has been extremely popular amongst researchers, but the practical implications appear limited (Wünderlich et al., 2015). Some researchers have also identified frameworks through which to co-create customer value through the use of customer data (Hoffman and Novak, 2017; Kunz et al., 2017; Lim and Maglio, 2018); however, they lack empirical evidence and actionable information for effective practice (Lim et al., 2019).

One of the objectives of this research is to recommend a framework that can ensure the use of transparent and fairer CRM behaviours. Thus, the researcher will expand an existing framework developed by Payne and Frow by adding one more process into it (2005, 2013). The framework was introduced as a guideline by which to aid service providers in moving away from dark side behaviours towards a more ‘enlightened’ practice of CRM. The researcher has recommended the need of an additional process, the *service quality management process*, particularly to address the dark behaviours resulted as a consequences of service failure and failure in service recovery.

The section below discusses the recommended framework and how each process can be implemented towards addressing the dark behaviours identified by this study.

6.2 Recommended Framework

This study would like to propose an extension to the enlightened CRM strategy developed by Payne and Frow, 2013. They developed a process framework that can be implemented to manage customer relationship management activities more strategically. In their later study about how to address the dark sides of CRM activities, they developed a forward-thinking process based CRM strategy framework that incorporates the five key cross-functional processes defining a holistic use of CRM processes and how the framework can guide the service providers away from the 'dark side' towards a more 'enlightened' practice of CRM (Payne and Frow, 2013). The five key processes are identified as being part of an interlinked structure by which to address dark side behaviours.

Frow and his fellow researchers created this framework as a tool by which to address and overcome the 10 forms of dark side behaviours that were identified in their study of service providers' dark side behaviours in relation to CRM (Frow, Payne, Wilkinson and Young, 2011). The study was undertaken by the four authors through an individual literature review, which was followed by a day long workshop with experienced CRM practitioners and interviews with CRM, marketing and IT executives.

The need for multiple process integration in relation to CRM has been highlighted in several past studies, including that of Boulding. More specifically, Boulding and his fellow researchers' definition can be used as a philosophical grounding for the journey towards implementing a successful customer relationship management. It states that "CRM relates to strategy, managing the dual-creation or value, the intelligent use of data and technology, the acquisition of customer knowledge and the diffusion of this knowledge to the appropriate stakeholders, the development of appropriate (long-term) relationships with specific customers and/or customer groups, and the integration of processes across the many areas of the firm and across the network of firms that collaborate to generate customer value" (Boulding et al. 2005, p. 6). Their definition highlights the power of collaborative strategy in establishing a successful long-term customer relationship.

Based on the findings of this study, the big four MNOs in the UK are lacking value driven dialogues with their customers, failing to integrate customer touch points, handling their social media communications extremely unilaterally, displaying negligence towards the severity of negative word of mouth, and so on. The most important aspects that have been ignored are employee empowerment, knowledge management and the organisational learning and service quality management process.

Figure 6. 1 Towards an enlightened CRM strategy by Payne and Frow (2013)

To address the additional dark side behaviours identified by this study, the researcher finds it necessary to add an additional process into the framework: the service quality management process. As described in the previous chapter, some of the dark side activities are clearly the consequences of service failure and failure in service recovery strategy; therefore, the researcher has identified the need to implement a service quality management process. Additionally, it has been observed that the MNOs are lacking value driven dialogues and collaborative experiences with their service users; which reflects that MNOs are missing on organisational learning process.

Figure 6. 2 An extension to the enlightened CRM strategy, created by the author

Themes	Sub Themes	Recommended Process
Behavioural Discrepancy	Favouritism	Strategy development process
	Loyalty Penalty	Strategy development process Multi-channel customer/ experience process
	Exploitation of Vulnerability	Strategy development process Multi-channel customer/ experience process
Data Exploitation	Data Misuse and Mishandling	Information management process
	Privacy Invasion	Information management process
Deceptive Tactics	False Advertising	Value creation process
	Information Asymmetry	Value creation process Multi-channel customer experience process
	Lack of Transparency	Value creation process

	Misleading Practices	Value creation process
	Procedure Complexity	Value creation process
	Fine Print Misuse	Value creation process
Employee Incompetency	Misinformation and Forced Selling	Performance assessment process
	Lack of Product Information	Performance assessment process
	Employee Negligence and Irresponsibility	Performance assessment process
	Dishonesty and Violation of Psychological Contract	Information management process Performance assessment process
Financial Exploitation	Billing Shock	Value creation process
	Mid-contract Price Rise	Value creation process
	Price Discrepancy	Value creation process
Service Quality Failure	Poor Customer Service	Service quality management process
	Inadequate Service Value	Service quality management process
Consumer Dark Behaviour Intentions	Anger and Use of Foul Language	<i>Addressing the dark side behaviours of service providers will solve the consumer dark behaviours.</i>
	Negative Word of Mouth	
	Withdrawal from the Relationship	

Table 6. 1 Strategic processes addressing the dark side behaviours in this study

The framework developed by Payne and Frow (2005, 2013) has established and identified the strategic processes involved in resolving the specific dark sides of CRM; however, they have not extensively discussed how each process can resolve them. The tools and instruments involved in each process are yet to be discussed through further research.

Payne and Frow themselves stated that the classification of their framework is not exhaustive and that there is room for the identification of new dark side activities; this

research, therefore, has tried to fill that gap (Payne and Frow, 2013). It has identified new dark side behaviours that are being practiced by the UK MNOs. It has further identified the dark side behaviours being practiced by service users; they engage in these behaviours after becoming aware of being taken advantage of by their service providers. The main addition that this study makes to this framework is the introduction of the service quality management process; the findings reveal that most of the dark side activities are perceived in relation to service failure and MNOs' failure in implementing service recovery strategies. The researcher therefore argues that the use of the service quality management process can address the related dark side behaviours and enhance the customer relationship and its management effectively.

1. Strategy development process

The strategy development process is the primary step to any business. In order to ensure the success of CRM implementation, the interrelationship between customer strategy and business strategy is vital; therefore, the strategy development process involves a thorough evaluation of business strategy that also includes corporate vision and goals. The development of a customer strategy is based around business strategy, vision and competition. Based on the industry analysis and competitiveness, the firms should define their target customer segment. CRM activities are determined based on the characteristics of the customer segment. MNOs may have loyal customers, some vulnerable segments, new customers, and so on. While formulating any strategy, firms need to consider each segment equally so that none of the segments feel unequally treated or unfavoured in one way or another.

Payne and Frow suggested that the strategy development process can resolve dark side behaviours like 'spillover' effects, which include invasive promotion. Out of the 23 dark side behaviours identified by the researcher in this study, this process can address the dark side activities related to behavioural discrepancy, including favouritism, loyalty penalty and the exploitation of vulnerability.

2. Value creation process

Value co-creation is the core function of customer relationship management. Value creation as a process focuses on firms identifying the value that can be derived from being in a relationship with customers, and vice versa. It is therefore important to

monitor and track what value the company is providing to its customers and what value the customers are providing to the company. Most importantly, it is vital for the service providers to track whether the value–exchange is being managed well. Based on the findings, the service providers are failing to maximize the lifetime value of their customers. Loyal customers are feeling that they have to pay a loyalty penalty, while the vulnerable customer segment is being taken advantage of through hidden terms and conditions, complex processes or simply through behavioural ignorance.

The value creation process should therefore be directed towards addressing dark side behaviours, including the loyalty penalty and the exploitation of vulnerable segments. As suggested by Payne and Frow (2013), the value creation process addresses dark side activities that include financial exploitation, customer lock-in and dishonesty. Based on this study, this process will also address additional dark side activities, such as billing shock, mid-contract price rises and price discrepancy. This process encourages practices that are mutually rewarding to both service providers and service users.

3. Multi-channel/customer experience process

This process focuses on determining what combination of channels are appropriate based on the firms customer segment. They need to define strategies towards achieving highest level of customer experiences through interactions within those channels. Most importantly, when there are multiple channels involved in customer communications, firms need to outline “how to create and present a single unified view of the customer” (Paye and Frow, 2005, p. 172). Likewise, the information that the service users receive through each channel are also not unified. The information asymmetry caused by lack of channel integration results in a significant amount of relationship failure as well as the negative word of mouth that can scare away potential customers.

Based on the findings, it is further evident that communication integration is largely missing. Channel integration is the most important process in a successful customer management strategy, and the evolution of technology has made it even more important. It is also important to note that both physical and virtual integration is crucial, despite the fact that this study has predominantly focused on online settings. As stated

by Nguyen (2012), if any CRM system has been implemented, it must be adequately interconnected to internal processes and departments; each process co-ordinated towards developing the relationship with existing customer. This study has observed a lack of channel integration amongst the UK MNOs, which leads to confusion in customers. Payne and Frow (2013) suggested that an effective multichannel process can resolve the dark side practice of customer confusion. This study identifies that the dark side practice of information asymmetry will also be resolved through this process.

4. Information management process

The information management process generally focuses on collecting, transferring, storing and using the data collected from various customer touch points. After transforming customer data into insightful knowledge, the organisation develops relevant marketing strategies based on the knowledge. Customer data handling is the part of this process; therefore, the dark side behaviours such as data misuse, data mishandling and privacy invasion will be addressed through the better implementation of the information management process. Likewise, activities like customer confusion and manipulation—which arise as a result of false advertising, misleading information and dishonesty—will be abolished through the strategic use of the information process.

The basic idea behind collecting customer data is to transform them into information and implement them back to add value to the customer. Customer knowledge management is more important than ever, as customers have shifted from being passive receptors of products and services to powerful knowledge partners (Desouza and Paquette, 2011); therefore, information management and customer knowledge management is an opportunity for the firms and service providers to capitalise on the data received in the form of complaints and feedback. The feedback and complaints of service users are the best source of knowledge and learning for service providers.

Some level of customer dissatisfaction and complaints are inevitable, probably due to the nature of the customer or their desire for variety; however, the ability to handle these properly with the goal of improving the relationship is what knowledge management focuses on. In this study, service users were observed to be furious with their service providers, and especially for neglecting their complaints; as a result, many

service users were seen to be acting aggressively, using foul language and even terminating their contract.

The knowledge management process focuses on converting complaints and feedback received from customer touchpoints into the knowledge that can develop long term solution. Creating a learning culture within the organisation is vital. Organisational learning will also be enhanced by the integration of the information management process and performance management process.

5. Service quality management process

Service quality is the key to customer satisfaction and loyalty, and it results successful customer relationship management. Based on the findings, UK MNOs are falling behind in terms of delivering sufficient service quality and which is causing their CRM strategies to fail as a whole. The researcher therefore notices that there is a gap with regard to the strategic CRM process and hence introduces the service quality management process in order to address the problem.

To elaborate on how to achieve an effective service quality management process, the researcher finds the implementation of the SERVQUAL model to be crucial. This is because most of the dark side behaviours are the consequence of a lack of trust, empathy, credibility and responsiveness from employees. Several studies have proved the viability of the SERVQUAL model (Zeithaml et al., 1990) as an instrument by which to measure customer satisfaction and loyalty, which ultimately leads to successful customer relationship management. The SERVQUAL model can also be used as a performance assessment tool that measures tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

The implementation of a service quality management process will address dark side activities including poor customer service and inadequate service value.

6. Performance assessment process

The performance assessment process generally focuses on tracking and monitoring the success of CRM implementation. It incorporates the necessary steps taken in order to ensure that the objective of CRM implementation is being delivered as

planned and resulting in satisfactory outcomes. Should there be any insufficient results or barriers in achieving the CRM's goal, necessary measures should be taken to avoid further damage.

Performance assessment also incorporates the concept of organisational learning, which is one of the shortcomings of the UK MNOs as observed in this study. Employees seem to be neglecting their professional behaviour. In addition, this study highlights the need for employee empowerment and training in relation to employee behaviour and service delivery. A lack of sensitivity and empathy from customer service staff were two of the most highlighted behaviours. The implementation of KPIs and performance appraisal are some of the tools with which to make the performance assessment process effective.

In order to achieve a broader impact, management can introduce a balanced scorecard, which is one of the most accepted performance measurement systems out there. This channels organisational functional processes and sets performance measures according to each functional area. A balanced scorecard is a performance metric implemented to recognise, develop and control internal business functions and their outcomes, both financial and non-financial. This strategy framework was developed almost three decades ago by David Norton and Robert Kaplan (Norton and Kaplan, 1992, 2009) and it serves as “a strategy map and an enabler of policy implementation” (Hoque, 2014, p. 21). Over the years, the scorecard has been refined and developed and it has become more of an inclusive strategy map that measures, tracks and administers the performance of overall organisational processes, and it is especially useful in helping organisations to cope with today's technologically disruptive world. As stated by Norton and Kaplan (1992), the balanced scorecard offers an answer to the lack of integration. It serves as a spool for the organisation's efforts; by defining and communicating priorities to managers, employees, investors, even customers.

Payne and Frow's study suggested that this process will particularly address the dark side practices of relationship neglect and ecological impacts. Likewise, based on the findings of this study, the researcher recognises that an enhanced performance assessment process can address all the dark side behaviours related to the lack of

process and communication integration, as well as the ones that are the result of employee incompetency. These include misinformation and forced selling, lack of product information, employee negligence and irresponsibility, and dishonesty and the violation of the psychological contract.

Despite the fact that each process is established specifically in order to resolve a particular dark side behaviour, some of the dark side behaviours can be addressed through the use of more than one or a combination of strategic processes. This is similar to the way in which some of the dark side behaviours are interrelated.

Payne and Frow (2013) suggested 'processes towards enlightened CRM practices' however they haven't explained the details on what activities and tools are involved within each individual process particularly in solving the dark sides. The researcher identifies an opportunity for future research to explore the instruments that can be used in resolving or eliminating dark side practices. For instance, the researcher has advised service providers to use the SERVQUAL model as an instrument by which to measure and monitor the service quality being delivered to service users. Any shortcomings can be identified and resolved accordingly, which will help eliminate further damage to the customer relationship. Likewise, placing key performance indicators, and even inter-departmental SWOT analysis, can be an effective tool by which to monitor performance assessment.

Furthermore, this research has been conducted in OBCs on social media platforms, including Facebook and Twitter, and has identified that some of the dark sides of CRM were not just practiced by the MNOs to exploit the service users intentionally but were associated with their failure to adopt a comprehensive strategy by which to manage customer relations and value co-creation through customer engagement over social media. The data revealed that not many customer service agents were well educated about their employer's services (MNOs) and, on many occasions, it also looked as though the communication lacked functional integration. One of the commenters mentioned that they had contacted customer service several times and had to repeat their issues as many times as they spoke to new customer service staff. This clearly reflects that the customer was not passed over to, or was not able to access, the relevant department. Similarly, another respondent said, "[I] spoke to their customer

service and cancelled the contract. Was clearly told there is no outstanding amount to be paid"; however, the customer was still receiving bills. This also reflects that the front-facing staff and their communication integration are severely flawed. All these failures resulted in the build-up of frustration, which not only ruins one relationship but can have greater affects if the results of such incompetence are visible on social media platforms.

Today's companies are too often found to be investing in tools and emerging platforms without thinking of a comprehensive strategy that aligns with their customer-centric business model. Recently, introducing social media into businesses has been a bandwagon that most businesses are jumping onto, but without them comprehending the extent of the factors, functional departments and processes involved, and without them realising what changes must be incorporated when introducing such technology. Failures in change management within organisations can lead to the failure of their overall strategies.

This study concluded that the dark side practices within MNOs were partly due to a lack of process integration, which can lead to value destruction; therefore, along with adopting the 'enlightened strategic framework' (Fig. 6.1), the researcher highlights the need for MNOs to focus on customer-centric strategies.

To overcome any pitfalls of CRM, whether traditional CRM or social CRM, the establishment and maintenance of customer-centric strategy is key; however, this seems to be lacking within UK MNOs as per the findings of this research. Service incompetence was one key dark side practice highlighted by service users, and it includes the incompetence of employees in dealing with customer touchpoints. Technological advancements and ever popular digital social media platforms are giving customers ever increasing power within the buyer–seller relationship, which can be detrimental if firms fail to listen to and understand expectations or engage with customers. As stated by Andzulis, Panagopoulos and Rapp (2012), the adoption of any social media tool or platform must be treated as a dynamic process within the firm's CRM strategy. Firms must understand that although implementing social tools may not involve as high a financial input as putting a traditional CRM system in place, the impact of the improper and unsolicited use of social media platforms or social CRM

can destroy a firm's overall relationship with its customers. To avoid such pitfalls and possible dark sides in the customer relationship that are associated with such shortcomings, the researcher recommends that MNOs should implement the framework below.

Fig. 6.3: Overcoming pitfalls with customer-focused strategy (adapted from Rapp and Oglivie, 2015, p. 68)

It goes without saying that today's digital world has made consumers more powerful and demanding than ever, while, simultaneously, a firm's social media presence is no longer the one-way system through which to extract customer data and information that it once used to be. It instead involves the co-creation of value through interactions and engagement; hence, the establishment of a customer-centric CRM strategy is fundamental. Rapp and Oglivie introduced a strategy (Fig. 6.3) that can overcome the pitfalls and dark sides associated with CRM conducted over social media.

Understand: Understanding customers' expectations is fundamental in CRM, not only in the acquisition phase but as a constant process, as expectations are subject to change. Failure to differentiate the gap between customers' wants and expectations can create a sense of unfairness amongst customers. This study showed that MNOs are seen to be pushing information and adverts on their social media pages while ignoring the mammoth numbers of pending queries that are yet to be addressed. Such failures on the part of service providers seem to infuriate consumers and make them feel of secondary importance, which is evident through the comments they make on the posts created by the MNOs. The failure to listen and respond to service users can significantly damage customer relationships. As Greenberg (2010) stated, customers do not simply engage via social media for the sake of interaction; they rather expect value in return for the time they have invested in such interactions and the MNOs' access to their data and personal information.

Integrate: Firms must analyse and ensure that their social strategies, social presence and objectives integrate with their current CRM strategy. The findings of this study have suggested that MNOs' failure to integrate social communication resulted in inconsistency in the information provided, patchy communication that frustrated customers and the overall destruction of value rather than value co-creation. Such a lack of effort, combined with inconsistency and mismanagement, can lead customers to question the overall authenticity of the relationship (Greenberg, 2010). The service users were observed to be complaining about the lack of information management and were frustrated at having to repeat their questions and problems to several employees on each follow-up call or message on social media platforms. As stated by Rapp and Ogilvie (2015), MNOs must address how their current CRM capabilities can be extended and enhanced with any new addition of social media platforms. What processes will be affected by the introduction of new social media platforms, and will the change impact the overall organisational culture? If it will, what measures can be brought in to ensure a smooth transition? The lack of communication does not only result in perceptions of unfairness and prove damaging to customer relationship value, trust and satisfaction; it also creates chaos within internal processes.

Allocate: When the requirements and resources are not fully projected, distributed or aligned with the process involved in maintaining a successful CRM system, organisational capabilities and competence are questioned. As per the findings, service users were aware of the misalignment and disjoint in communication processes, which led to them becoming disappointed. Furthermore, service users also questioned employees' incompetence and lack of knowledge about the service and were found to be practicing negative word of mouth that could be destructive to CRM and brand reputation (Nguyen and Mutum, 2012). Therefore, before adding any new social platform into social CRM, firms must analyse and allocate necessary resources to address the lack of bridging technology and competent staff or any other resources, as this can result in customer frustration – this does not only cause the objectives of social CRM to fail; it also destroys firms' CRM. Agnihotri et al. (2012)'s study suggests that success in social CRM critically relies upon organisational support and asserts that a substantial adjustment in resources must be made if firms are to meet new demands.

Train: Based on the findings of this study, it is crucial for MNOs to analyse the extent of product and service knowledge that their social media handlers and customer service employees have. It is evident that some service staff are severely lacking in basic knowledge about the MNOs' offerings, which resulted in the perception of dark misinformation and information asymmetry. Furthermore, employee education regarding ethical considerations is vital, and service users found that some employees were coming across as rude, ignorant and lacking in empathy. As relationships are based on emotional ground, employees' failure to address emotional elements while communicating with service users can result in damaging consequences.

It is evident that any kind of organisational change or new strategy implementation requires the evaluation of existing and required resources and the identification of gaps. This applies in the introduction of social CRM systems, social media platforms or any new technological tool in CRM (Agnihotri et al., 2012). Firms must recognise how intensive the new tools are and what sets of skills are required for the implementation of these.

Monitor and Adapt: For any strategic implementation to succeed, continuous monitoring and adaption is crucial, as implementation is not a one-step process. Technological advancements must be tracked, as they are ever emerging; thus, keeping an eye on updates and the availability of better alternatives or more efficient tools in the market can offer a competitive advantage. Similarly, as stated by Rapp and Ogilvie (2015), firms must continuously monitor whether the customer's expectations are being met, whether employees are proficient in their role or need any additional support and whether there is a margin for improvement in any of the CRM processes involved. Furthermore, evaluating social analytics and the performance of social media platforms is equally imperative.

In addition to adopting these strategic considerations to appropriately address the dark side behaviour of 'service quality failure', categorised as poor customer service and inadequate service value, the researcher proposes that MNOs should implement the SERVQUAL model, which serves as a tool to understand the gap in service delivery and, when identified, is a tool with which to capitalise on and close the gap. Past studies have implied that the failure to understand and adhere to these dimensions of

SERVQUAL leads to service users having perceptions of unfairness (Parasuraman et al., 1988), which are also viewed as being dark behaviours in CRM (Nguyen et al., 2017). Such dark practices, particularly in relation to the service delivery, lead service users to engage in negative word of mouth or even to terminate their relationship with the service provider, which is evident in this analysis.

As acknowledged in the literature review, Parasuraman et al, 1994, explained that unlike the nature of products, which can be objectively measured using numbers and scores, service quality is an abstract concept that has the unique features of being intangible, heterogenous and inseparable from production and consumption. Therefore, Parasuraman et al. proposed that understanding consumers' perceptions of service quality is imperative for successful CRM implementation.

The importance of service recovery strategy and complaint management has been introduced by adding the 'service quality management process' to the enlightened CRM strategy framework (Fig. 6.1) originally created by Payne and Frow (2013). However the researcher recommends focussing on and dealing with the dark sides associated with service quality failure in a distinct manner, and, as a result, the researcher proposes that MNOs should implement the SQERVQUAL model, which serves as a performance assessment tool with which to measure tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy; that is, the elements that determine the service quality of the service provider. The researcher not only suggests examining service users' perceptions of service quality but also those of service managers and employees as has been recommended by past studies (Shekarchizadeh et al., 2011; Sangeetha and Mahalingam, 2011). MNOs can construct a separate SERVQUAL questionnaire to understand perceptions of service quality from the viewpoint of employees and service users separately and triangulate the differences.

The service quality perceptions of customers depend on how well the firm manages to support the customers' processes and respond to their specific interactions, which will make the customers more enthusiastic about continuing their relationship with the firm. In other words, the better the firm services its customers, the more favourably the customers will perceive the quality of the relationship, the more value will emerge from

the customers' processes and, in the final analysis, the more successful the firm's marketing will be.

This study clearly identified the failure in service quality, service delivery and service recovery as dark sides of CRM therefore regular monitoring of service quality using SERVQUAL model is advised, as SERVQUAL will help in identifying which dimension of service quality is lacking or ignored and will guide firms towards the development of strategies aimed at resolving such shortcomings. MNOs must acknowledge that their service encounters with service users, both pre- and post- purchase, will shape service users' opinions on whether the service provider delivers a quality service that makes the service user want to continue to be in a relationship with the firm.

6.3 Solutions to Service Users' Dark Side Behaviours

In response to the perceived dark side behaviours practiced by service providers, service users are also found to be practicing some dark side behaviours in return. In the past studies, misbehaving customers were identified as being 'jaycustomers' (Lovelock, 1994), and further research was carried out on their characteristics, motivations and consequences of their misbehaviours (Harris and Raynolds, 2005; Park and Kim, 2016). Jaycustomers has been defined as those customers who purposefully act in an abusive manner with an intention to harm the firm, employees, other customers or the brand as a whole (Harris and Raynolds, 2005); however, the focus in this study is on the customers and service users who practice dark side behaviours as a response to the dark side behaviours of their service providers.

According to Stone (2016) on analysing the dark sides of CRM, he stated that the rage and anger from the customers is reasonable, as they are resulted by a firm's failure in anticipating problems and even after anticipating them, firm's failure to effective and timely solutions. Customers want to be heard, when they have any issues or problems with the service itself or the service providers.

Service users have identified that dark side behaviours are the result of employee negligence, lack of employee knowledge and the practice of dishonesty, which seems to be the consequence of a lack of employee empowerment. Hence, the researcher

argues that there is a need to implement organisational learning strategy based on the observation of employee's performance assessment.

Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge the service users' dark side behaviours are cumulative reaction to several dark activities from the service providers, except for the one whose intentions are to harm the firm. So, when the firms address their dark practice, it will ultimately discourage customers to practice dark behaviours too. For instance, when employees are empowered with enough product knowledge, activities such as mis-selling and mis-informing customers will decrease, which will decrease service users' use of dark side practices, including negative word of mouth and displaying aggression in online communities.

Likewise, the implementation of an appropriate complaint management strategy will lead to increased customer satisfaction that results in a profitable long-term relationship. Overall, the enlightened practice of CRM through the use of the cross-functional processes framework will eventually eliminate service users' dark side behaviours.

6.4 Theoretical and practical contribution of the study

The dark sides of CRM, as widespread they are, remain an area that academics and researchers have not studied enough. There is a very limited amount of literature available on the topic, which was a challenge to the researcher while carrying out the literature review. However, on the brighter side, it provided an opportunity for the researcher to make a deeper contribution to theory and the conceptualisation of the dark sides of CRM.

As discussed in literature review, the first and foremost thing that the researchers and practitioners need to be able to differentiate between CRM concepts, CRM strategies and CRM software. The terminologies and concepts are extremely interrelated, but they cannot be interchangeably used. A lack of understanding with regard to this issue has led to the failure of CRM implementation projects costing millions of pounds. It is therefore crucial for practitioners to make their managers and employees understand these differences before implementing any CRM strategy. Theoretically, the findings of this study has added in conceptualising CRM in a larger picture. It is rather a strategic approach focuses on practices that are focused on converting data into customer knowledge, that helps to retaining the existing customers. Likewise, it also integrates customer touchpoints and internal business processes in order to manage customer relationship and create dual value co-creation.

To highlight the major theoretical contributions, this study has added to CRM literature and, more specifically, to literature on the dark sides of CRM by identifying prevalent dark side behaviours. Out of very limited studies on the dark sides of CRM, Payne and Frow identified 10 dark side behaviours based on an empirical literature review. In a response to their call for future researchers to examine this topic, this study has brought to light the prevalent dark side CRM activities being practiced by the UK's MNOs.

This study also greatly contributes on the conceptualisation and overview of 'what is dark about the dark-side of business relationship' (Abosag, Yen and Barnes, 2016). Over around last decade, the term 'dark-side' in the context of business relationships has been quite popular in academia. Despite the popularity and growth

in the number of studies, there are relatively little critique in this field. Some scholars have identified factors like role conflict and ambiguity, opportunism and power as key attributes that influence on the 'dark side' in value co-creation activities. Similarly, Perception of unfairness, consumer's realisation of being victim to opportunism and manipulation and so on are discussed by Samaha et al. (2011) as potential 'relationship-destroying factors'. Therefore, it's necessary to identify mechanisms, patterns and antecedents in relations to what makes a relationship activity 'dark'.

Furthermore, this study has made a significant effort in expanding an existing framework, by Payne and Frow (2013) that was developed to address the dark sides of CRM. The researcher has added one more process in the framework, to address the CRM dark sides that were instigated due to the service quality failure of MNOs.

Although the provision of differential treatment based on individual needs and one-to-one service customisation is the key idea behind CRM, service providers need to carefully formulate strategies that wouldn't be perceived as unfair by the service users. Such perception of unfairness is what leads the service users to perceive CRM activities as being 'dark' ones.

6.5 Practical implications of the study

As aforementioned, this research contributes in increasing awareness for both consumers and practitioners with regard to comprehending the ethical issues around CRM and activities related to CRM implementation. In his paper, N'Goala (2015) mentioned the potential boomerang effects of unethical CRM practices, which include disloyalty, negative word of mouth, decrease in customer value, financial loss, etc., and in parallel emphasised how ethical CRM practices can pay off in the long run. Therefore, it is crucial for both parties to understand what is ethical and what is not. This is particularly the case for companies, who must understand how they can better execute their relationship tactics without deception and manipulation and address CRM decision making in such a way that it is both ethical and overcomes the dark side of CRM.

Furthermore, while customers are increasingly made to expose their information, businesses are ripping off the benefits of those personal information without being

transparent on what they are using those data for. With the increased availability of data, which is ever increasing thanks to businesses' social media presence and customers' engagement with online brand communities, companies are tempted more than ever to exploit their customers and behave opportunistically. Despite the fact that past studies have observed the exploitation of information asymmetry, increasing opportunism, manipulations and other forms of distrust and questioned the 'ethics' involved in CRM decision making, not much has practically changed for the better. Therefore, this research focused primarily on increasing awareness.

Similarly, past studies have identified when CRM and relationship management decision making can go ethically wrong. Sher (2011) outlines that CRM becomes immorally manipulative when organisations breach their customers' independence, infringe customers' trust, exploit customers' limitations and vulnerabilities or simply abuse the power of being able to hurt customers' emotions associated with the brand. Businesses must look into their strategic decision making in order to avoid such manipulation and immorality in their CRM, as it can have a cost both in terms of the acquisition and retention of customers. It is also important for practitioners to understand that unfairness does not always relate to price. Unlike the financial aspects, there are several emotional harms that customers perceive in relation to CRM activities being practiced by firms. These include negative experiences with the service, customer service employees' ignorance, the unauthorised dissemination of private information, privacy invasion, and so on. This research, therefore, tried to identify and address different ethical and strategic issues that are prevalent in the UK MNO industry with an objective to discourage such practices.

While reviewing the literature on dark sides, it was found that the study conducted by Frow et al. (2012) introduces the intended and unintended CRM activities and classifies them as 'dark' and 'poor or ineffective, respectively. However, there is the possibility that these activities will look alike from the customers' perspective; thus, the consumers may react in similar ways regardless of the intentions of the seller. The poorly functioning CRM practitioner needs to develop managerial skills to improve their implementation of CRM, while dark side practitioners may already have excellent implementation skills but require changes in their strategic orientation, ethical values and/or in the culture of their organisation. This study provides clarification on the

importance of constantly analysing and monitoring their CRM activities; as some of the CRM activities may not be practiced with malicious intention however service users may be perceiving them as being unfair. Service providers can also periodically measure service quality through surveys by using the SERVQUAL tool which provides deeper insights into the dimensions of service quality. Furthermore, past research has clearly stated that maliciously motivated service providers can abuse customers, as CRM technology can equip them with powerful resources to do this (Frow et al., 2012). This dark side behaviour may occur not only when suppliers are maliciously motivated to abuse customers, but also when they mistake customer exploitation for CRM. Frow et al. (2013) stated that some of these behaviours are clearly the result of opportunism and the greediness of service providers, while some are the consequence of unawareness. Aligned with this, most of the dark side activities identified in this research are the result of obliviousness with regard to the related functions of CRM and, most importantly, MNOs' ignorance in relation to aftersales service delivery. Therefore, this research serves as a warning for MNOs and other service providers not to deviate into dark practices and reminds them that the implementation of the enlightened strategic framework will result in a more enlightened and holistic approach to CRM.

The key practical contributions made by this study can be summarised into the following points:

1. The study provides insights for service providers on the necessity of managing the factors that can make service users feel deceived, misled or manipulated into locking into a relationship. It is crucial for CRM managers and customer relationship decision makers to understand the perceptions of their service users and the dark sides that are prevalent in their industry today.

2. As stated by Neale and Fullerton (2010), knowing what customers in general believe to be ethical or unethical can help service designers focus on the aspects of the technology or design most vulnerable to customer deviance. The SERVQUAL model could be one key and easy tool that could be implemented by MNOs. This study provides clarification on the importance of constantly analysing and monitoring their CRM activities; as some of the CRM activities may not be practiced with malicious

intention however service users may be perceiving them as being unfair. Service providers can also periodically measure service quality through surveys by using the SERVQUAL tool. This will provide deeper insights into the dimensions of service quality.

3. This study encourages service providers to be vigilant and to continuously monitor employees' activities, both on social media platforms and in terms of providing them with enough training, so that they feel empowered to provide a better quality of service. This is because quality service is the key to retaining loyal customers; that guarantees profitability through long term relationship.

4. This study directs service providers to work closely with governing bodies and to take advice on an on-going basis. For example, governing bodies like Ofcom and CMA are in place to monitor and continuously promote fair practice in the UK telecoms industry. Collaborative work will help service providers to avoid engaging in unfair practices in relation to data and refrain for any kind of data misuse.

5. Concerns of implementing CRM and possibility of exploiting customers' vulnerabilities instead of developing a balance of power and win-win situations have been well discussed by past studies (Wong, Chan, Ngai, & Oswald, 2009) but with addition and innovation in technologies, more forms of information asymmetry, vulnerability, privacy concerns, and potential causes of distrust are emerging. As per the findings and evaluation, it is due to the weak support for CRM from the strategic level that emphasises good relationship-building practices, perhaps. Therefore, the implementation of the enlightened CRM framework suggested by the researcher could prove to eliminate the dark sides and rather achieve win-win situation through CRM.

6. It has been found that poorly practiced CRM often focuses on transactional profitability rather than on building or maintaining existing relationships. The dark side behaviours identified in this study may not always occur solely as a result of the malicious intentions of service providers, with regard to a desire to abuse and exploit service users, but also from their mistaking customer exploitation for CRM. The researcher has therefore recommended the use of an enlightened strategic framework to address and eliminate dark side behaviours. The holistic use of CRM processes

can help guide service providers away from the 'dark side' and towards a more 'enlightened' practice of CRM.

7. This study has found that there are some gaps in the communication channels within the MNOs, which is causing dissonance and resulting in customer dissatisfaction which eventually leads to relationship termination. Therefore, it is crucial for MNOs to examine their internal communication channels and the effective integration of these.

8. The research finding shows that there was a lack of employee training and autonomy amongst customer service employees, who are one of the closest contact points through which to observe and build customer relationships. Employee empowerment and organisational learning must be addressed in order to avoid any dark sides of CRM associated with service delivery failure.

9. Furthermore, consumers' awareness of the manipulation and deceptive dark practices engaged in by their service providers can cause the service users to retaliate and practice dark behaviours to damage the service providers. According to past research, service users are often found to be lying about their personal data and providing incorrect personal information, such as their name, age, email, phone number, and so on, which will have a negative impact on future CRM decisions made based on customer knowledge (Lancelot-Miltgen, Mimouni Chaabane and Pez-Pérard, 2019). This research found that service users are inclined to abuse frontline employees, use foul language on social media and OBC platforms, engage in negative word of mouth, and so on. Therefore, it is crucial for future researchers to investigate customers' dark side practices. This will not only give a balanced view on the dark side of CRM but also make businesses more vigilant about acquiring credible customer data; this is because the most essential element in CRM implementation is for firms to acquire customer knowledge through the data that they share and to use it to create added value (Nguyen, 2012). It is certain that if consumers move towards supplying inaccurate data, it can hinder the whole objective of using this data and result in CRM failure.

10. The findings of this research indicate that service quality and integrated communication were the key instruments by which to enhance and/or maintain long-term relationships that lead to long-term profitability. MNOs are seen to be falling behind in relation to integrating communication. It was observed that service users were promised that they would be called back within a certain number of hours; however, the MNOs failed to reach out despite the customers making several attempts to establish contact. This seems to result in frustration amongst service users, who were made to feel of secondary importance.

11. MNOs must monitor and conduct routine analysis of their current CRM practice and functions around the practice to identify whether there are any strategic changes required; identification of any gap can help avoid any dark CRM activities. Further, this will also allow practitioners to identify any managerial skills and training required in a timely fashion, or even to transform any strategic orientations and introduce changes in the ethical values and/or culture of their organisation (Frow et al., 2012).

12. Data are one of the firms' most important assets, and therefore every effort must be made to prevent public outcry that will lead to regulations being implemented that will limit marketers' abilities to collect data. Incorporating fairness and trust may give firms an edge. As a result, future applications of CRM should integrate understanding of consumer (un)fairness and, where possible, manage it in order to avoid such damaging outcomes.

13. Lastly, regarding MNO's social platforms and OBCs, it is evident that the rise of social media and customers' use of such platforms has made service providers incorporate social CRM strategies: most customer interactions happen over social media and in online brand communities nowadays. Thus, they are one of the main customer touchpoints in today's digital age. Just as the rewards associated with the incorporation of social CRM and OBCs are increasing, so too are the complexities and pitfalls increasing in parallel; thus, if organisations fail to ensure the implementation of the correct organisation culture, managerial support, insufficient number of employees, relevant training, and so on (Myron, 2013), this will result in the failure of those CRM efforts. Rapp and Oglive (2015) have proposed strategic considerations that can combat the dark sides of social CRM. When resources are not allocated,

aligned and integrated with the rest of the CRM strategies, there is a high chance of failure. Hence, the researcher would like to

6.6 Limitations of this Research and New Research Directions

Dark side behaviours are an area of CRM that require extensive research due to the fact that the practice is prevalent, and a very limited amount of research has been carried out. It has also been identified that dark side practices are encouraged because of a lack of awareness amongst service users; therefore, visibility that is achieved through the work of academics and research is more crucial than ever. While conducting this research, the researcher came across several limitations that can act as an opportunity for future researchers.

First and foremost, the dark side behaviours are not divided into intentional and unintentional dark behaviours in this study. Future researchers are urged to explore into intentions; the division is crucial so the recommendations can be narrowed down. It has been observed that some of the service providers' activities seem to be deliberately aimed at transactions and profit maximisation; however, some seem to be completely unintentional and the result of organisational process failure. It is difficult to discern whether the service users' perceptions are specific to the dark side behaviours practiced deliberately by service providers. Hence, the researcher calls for future researchers to differentiate the intentions of dark side behaviours so that strategies can be implemented with a narrow focus.

Based on the definitions, characteristics and categorisations used in past research and the available literature, this research has investigated consumers' perceptions of the activities that look 'dark'. However, the researcher would like to call future researchers to explore and examine the processes involved in the development of such perceptions; that is, to examine at what point customers or service users realise that the activities practiced by their service provider are 'unfair' and 'dark'. Research conducted in 2019 identified that a sense of pressure, sense of injustice and sense of a loss of control are the possible feelings that consumers have about CRM activities that can possibly be identified as 'dark' (Lancelot-Miltgen, Mimouni Chaabane and Pez-Pérard, 2019, p. 221). Although this study has introduced the possible emotions experienced in relation to consumers' perceptions of dark activities, no attempts have

been made to describe consumers' emotional processes in detail. Hence, it is necessary for future research to explore the antecedents and processes involved within consumers' emotional journeys in greater detail.

Payne and Frow's research encouraged future researchers to look into other potential dark side behaviours and this study has added to understanding in relation to this issue. Furthermore, the dark side behaviours identified by Payne and Frow were rather general; through empirical research, this research has identified nine new dark side behaviours that are being practiced by service providers. In addition, three different types of dark side activities that are being practiced by service users have been identified. Although these dark behaviours are the consequence of users realising that service providers have been taking advantage of them in the name of CRM, they are still unacceptable. It is possible that there are other activities that are as yet unidentified that future research can explore and identify.

Payne and Frow also called for future researchers to identify the industry that is most likely to engage in such dark side practices. This research has proved that MNOs in the UK are one of the industries that are practicing dark side activities in relation to CRM. The researcher would also like to identify and research into other industries so that the practice can be generalised even more.

Some of the dark side behaviours are interlinked with the concept of service failure and the failure of service recovery strategies. The researcher would like future researchers to engage in a deeper examination of these elements in relation to customer relationship management.

Similarly, with regard to the recommended framework, as was the case in Payne and Frow's framework, the classification and division of the processes and the activities within each process is not explanatory enough. The framework does not adequately explain the effectiveness of each process in eliminating dark side behaviours. Therefore, future researchers are urged to explore this area and to identify specific strategies within the process as well.

Additionally, this study has identified the 'dark' activities used in practice based on the extant literature available; however, it did not fully consider the processes by which dark side practices emerge or the interrelationships between them. From an academic point of view, it is crucial for researchers to identify the elements of CRM activities and define the element that makes an activity dark, as awareness of sources of problem is crucial for any solution. In their study of business relationships, 'What is dark about the dark side of business relationships?', Abosag, Yen and Barnes (2016, p. 5) stated that "the notion of [a] 'dark side' suggests 'problems', 'challenges', 'difficulties', and 'drawbacks' related to structural issues that exist in business relationships", which can also be widespread in customer relationships. The term 'dark side' was introduced in the B2B literature in the mid- to late- 1990s and further work has continued around this theme well into the new century (Anderson and Jap, 2005; Barnes, 2005). This study concludes that it is crucial for MNOs to understand that investing in better technology or focusing on the positive elements of relationships alone is not enough: they must understand and take action against the negative perceptions, actions and behaviours of their service users.

This research has been undertaken unilaterally; the researcher has identified dark side behaviours based on the perceptions of service users. It is also important to look into service providers' perceptions of these practices. As mentioned in the literature review, some of the dark side activities are the result of a lack of organisational processes, and the service providers themselves are not aware that their activities are being perceived as dark behaviours. Therefore, understanding that is gained from a dual perspective is important. This research focuses on understanding the dark side of CRM entirely from the perspective of service users; thus, the findings of this research are also from this perspective. As mentioned in the previous chapters, the activities being practiced by businesses may not look unethical and dark when looked at through the lens of service providers and strategic decision makers; therefore, it is necessary for future research to look at this area of CRM from businesses' perspectives. By doing so, we can achieve more balanced and equitable results.

Given the extent of unethical and unfair practices that are emerging along with advancements in technology and the increased popularity of the internet around the globe, it is high time that CRM and marketing scholars expand their research into

internet marketing ethics and marketing to vulnerable consumers. Additionally, developments in technology and tools have facilitated invasive data collection, targeting, retargeting, and so on, all of which are facilitated by the internet. Thus, it is even more crucial to ensure that these tools are ethically bound. Businesses are keen to ensure that they are legally bound; however, the ethical element is what keeps the buyer-seller relationship intact.

This research has highlighted the activities that are perceived by service users as being from the dark side of CRM; however, efforts have not been made to understand what goes on behind the development of such unfair feelings. For example, at what point do service users realise that the activity is unfair? It is advised that future researchers should look into the emotional and behavioural aspects of customers' emotions, the thought processes behind such emotions and the development of perceptions of unfairness.

This study has identified dark side behaviours based on service users' perceptions; however, the forms of dark side behaviours and the classification scheme for dark side behaviours are not examined and developed exhaustively. More forms of dark side behaviours may remain to be identified and others may emerge in the future, mainly due to the emerging technology involved in CRM and social media platforms. Empirical research is needed to identify any further forms of dark side behaviours and to test, and possibly extend, the existing classification of dark sides.

As with the majority of studies, the design of the current study is subject to limitations. There are two major methodological limitations in this study that could be addressed in future research. Firstly, regarding the quantitative method used, i.e., a survey, the sample size of the quantitative data is not big enough, which made it difficult to find significant relationships from the data. A sufficient sample size is crucial in order to conclude a valid research result; however, the researcher only received 188 responses to the survey. As a result of the sample size being too small, it was difficult to identify significant relationships from the data. It is therefore advised that future researchers should include a larger set of data. Normally, statistical tests require a larger sample size to ensure that the sample is considered representative of a population and that the statistical result can be generalised to a larger population.

Similarly, the quality of the measures used in analysing quantitative data is limited here; firstly as a result of the researchers' limited knowledge of the tool used to analyse the data, and secondly as a result of the quantity of responses gathered. Additionally, it was felt that some of the questions in the survey questionnaire were negotiable and they could be omitted. Secondly, regarding the qualitative method used, the lack of a significant number of past studies using Netnography was another limitation that the researcher had to face.

Methodologically speaking, this research was carried out using mixed methods research. Netnography, the qualitative method implemented in this research, played a major methodological role. Qualitative data were collected through the observation of the online communities of UK MNOs. Conducting research in an online setting is comparatively popular these days; however, Netnography itself has not gained enough visibility in the research methodology arena—especially considering that the concept has been in existence for more than 25 years now. Netnography is a research methodology in itself, as well as a data collection instrument, and the rawness and richness of data that it offers reflects its strength. It is crucial for more researchers to implement Netnography and give the practice much needed visibility.

With regard to the quantitative study, it was conducted in an online setting using an online survey. Despite the fact that the researcher had expected a high number of responses to the online survey, only 188 respondents participated over the course of five months. This may have been the result of a lack of incentives offered by the researcher; some researchers offer monetary or non-monetary incentives to encourage participation in their research. Generally, in a survey, maximizing response rates is critically essential to achieve the most generalizable and unbiased results (Griffin et. al., 2011) hence, the researcher would call for future researchers to carry out data collection on a larger scale, possibly through the use of monetary incentives rather than relying on organic results alone. The dark side behaviours identified in this study are largely based on qualitative data and some are cross validated with the findings of the online survey. Had there been a larger number of respondents, the quantitative data could have added more significance. The researcher feels that the findings of the quantitative phase lack statistical significance to some extent.

In relation to the research methodology, and given the fact that the researcher is not an expert in the field, it was extremely difficult for them to comprehend the use of some methodological tools and instruments, such as SPSS and NVivo. The capability and vagueness of such tools can often be intimidating and be discouraging for beginner researchers. Therefore, universities and institutions are advised to provide enough guidance and training in relation to how to implement methodological tools effectively. As per the researcher's experience, it is important for researchers to understand the processes involved in ethics, data collection and analysis software from the very beginning of a research project.

With the benefit of hindsight, the following are some of the personal limitations that the researcher came across while undertaking this research:

- a. The researcher recognised that there is a lack of sufficient training in terms of research methodologies and the analysis tools offered by the university. Only a few basic training sessions were offered by the university, which the researcher felt were inadequate.
- b. As a result of being a Tier 4 international student, having to take on part-time work while managing living and full-time study combined was a challenge at times.
- c. As an international student, the researcher found that the lack of time, limited financial resources and paper-work associated with managing visas and travel were key limitations when it came to the researcher participating in local and international academic conferences.
- d. The mental stress experienced as a result of the global coronavirus pandemic (COVID19) was one of the major challenges faced by the researcher in the final stages of working on this thesis. Given the fact that the researcher was in the last phase of the research at this point, it was even more mentally challenging to manage their health and the research simultaneously.

6.7 Conclusion

In summary, there is a need for more research to be carried out in order to understand what kinds of behaviours will be perceived as dark side behaviours by service users, so that service providers can recognise and control the damage they cause in relation to relationship management.

This study has provided insights into the perceptions of service users regarding the activities carried out by their service providers in a hidden way that can cost the entire buyer–seller relationship. Using the collective findings from the observation data and data from the online survey, the researcher has identified seven forms of dark side activities that are prevalent amongst UK MNOs. The researcher has recommended the use of a framework that was introduced by Payne and Frow (2013) in order to address the dark side activities that they identified through empirical research. Crucially, the researcher has added one more process to the framework. The researcher recognises that there is a need to introduce an individual process for service quality management due to the fact that most of the dark side activities identified were in one way or the other related to service failure. Therefore, the implementation of a service quality management process will ensure service quality and enable companies to implement service recovery strategies effectively.

The researcher urges academics to study aspects of unfairness in CRM and the dark side behaviours prevalent in the service industry that are carried out in the name of CRM. This call is not just to increase the visibility of these behaviours and to make service users aware of them, but to warn firms about the misuse of CRM and the repercussions of doing so. Service providers who exploit existing relationships and customer data, engage in service negligence, and so on need to understand the consequences are beyond short term revenues.

Visibility of darker side of CRM practices, will also give service users confidence and knowledge of how important it is to be aware of what is happening to their personal data, how they are being used by the service provider, whether they are being treated fairly and whether their relationship with service provider is being exploited. Customers knowledge will eventually discourage service providers from mismanaging and

mishandling customers' data and the customer relationship on the whole. Likewise, if some of the dark side activities engaged in by firms are unintentional, firms must recognise the need to modify their behaviours so that the relationship with their service users will improve and bring about mutual gain. As we well know, CRM—if implemented correctly—will result in long-term relationships delivering win-win results to both service users and service providers.

Lastly, for any CRM strategy and its implementation to be successful, firms require to integrate a company-wide, cross-functional and customer-focused business processes.

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Appendices

Online survey questionnaire

Dear Participants,

Data collected through this survey will be used purely for an academic purpose while participant information will remain completely anonymous. For detailed information, please read the participant [Information Sheet](#).

All the data and records will be used and analysed only to achieve the objectives of this research.

The findings of this research will be written up in a part of my doctoral thesis. Parts of the study will also be submitted for publication in order to contribute academically and for managers' practical implications on the related field.

Thank you for considering to participate on my research.

Proceeding forward means you have read and understood the participant information sheet, and you confirm to participate in the study. If you do not wish to continue, please close your internet browser.

* 1. Age

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Under 18 | <input type="radio"/> 45 54 |
| <input type="radio"/> 18 24 | <input type="radio"/> 55 64 |
| <input type="radio"/> 25 34 | <input type="radio"/> 65+ |
| <input type="radio"/> 35 44 | |

* 2. Gender

- | | |
|------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Male | <input type="radio"/> Other |
| <input type="radio"/> Female | |

* 3. Occupation

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Student | <input type="radio"/> Unemployed |
| <input type="radio"/> Employed | <input type="radio"/> Retired |
| <input type="radio"/> Self employed | |

* 4. Which mobile network are you in?

- Three Vodafone
 O2 Other
 EE

Other (please specify)

* 5. How long have you been with your mobile network provider?

- Less than a year 5 - 10 years
 1 - 5 years More than 10 years

* 6. Are you satisfied with your current mobile network and its customer services?

- Very satisfied Dissatisfied
 Satisfied Very dissatisfied
 Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied

* 7. Which plan are you on?

- Pay as you go
 Monthly Plan

* 8. Do online reviews impact on your purchasing decision?

- Yes No

* 9. Have you ever given an online review for your mobile network provider?

- Yes No

* 10. Do you discuss about or compare the price of your mobile network plan with someone else (friends and family)?

Yes

No

* 11. How did you purchase your current mobile network plan?

Online

Over the phone

In store

Other

* 12. What information do you look on while buying the mobile plan?

Price

Service Package (how many minutes, texts and data is included)

Contract Period

Quality of service

Brand and Specs of Handset

Other (please specify)

13. Would you recommend your mobile network provider to your friends or family?

Yes

No

If No (please specify)

* 14. Have you ever come across any activity of your network provider that you would term as hidden, something that you weren't informed about while purchasing the plan?

Yes

No

If yes (please specify)

* 15. Have you experienced any unfair behaviour/activity from your mobile network provider?

- Yes No

If yes (please specify)

* 16. If you come across any unfair treatment, how do you react?

- Do nothing Leave negative review/comments
 Reach out to customer support Ask friends and family to NOT use the Network
 Switch the network

Other (please specify)

* 17. While purchasing your mobile plan, do you read the terms and conditions or the privacy policy?

- Always Rarely
 Usually Never
 Sometimes

* 18. How often do you receive calls or be contacted by your service provider?

- Weekly Frequently towards the end of contract
 Monthly Never

* 19. Do you check your mobile phone bills before making the payment?

- Always Rarely
 Sometimes Never

* 20. Are you aware about the use of your personal data by your mobile network provider?

Extremely aware

Very aware

Somewhat aware

Not so aware

Not at all aware

Participants information Sheet

Research Ethics - Participants Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

'Exploring perceptions of service users towards service provider's dark behaviours based on their Customer Relationship Management practices'

2. Invitation

You are cordially invited to be a part of this study. Before you make any decision, it is vital for you to understand why this research is being undertaken and what it involves. Please read the following information carefully. Do not hesitate to ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take your time to make your decision whether or not you wish to be a part of it. Thank you for taking time to read this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

This research project aims to identify the hidden behaviours of service providers in the name of CRM and perception of service users towards such behaviours. Once identified, strategies will be recommended to reduce and eliminate such hidden practices.

4. Why have I been chosen?

The research seeks to understand the perception of mobile service users towards their service providers behaviour. And as you are one of the mobile service users, understanding your view towards your service provider would give me an insight on your service provider's relationship management behaviour.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is your call to choose whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the consent form. You have all right to withdraw anytime without giving any reason.

6. What are any possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

You being a part of this study will only take time out of your day, but every effort will be made to minimise inconvenience and to ensure your comfort in the interview process.

Many people value the opportunity to talk about their experiences. This might be the one for you too.

7. How do you assure confidentiality of data?

Information which is collected about and through you during the interview will be firmly confidential. Also, every measure will be taken to assure your anonymity.

10. What happen to the data?

The interview data and records are utterly for this research purpose and they will be used and analysed to achieve the objectives of this research.

11. What will happen to the findings of the research study?

The findings of this research will be written up in a part of my PhD thesis. Parts of the study will also be submitted for publication in order to contribute academically and for managers' practical implications on related field.

Thank you for dedicating your valuable time to read this information sheet.

Contact Details

Researcher	Supervisor
Samjhana Humagain University of the West of Scotland [REDACTED]	Daba Chowdhury University of the West of Scotland [REDACTED]

Consent Form

Research Ethics - Consent Form

Full title of Project: Exploring the perceptions of service users towards service provider's dark behaviours based on customer relationship management practices

Researcher Details: Samjhana Humagain
Doctorate of Business Administration, Researcher
University of the West of Scotland

- a. I confirm that I have been well informed about the objectives of this study based on the information sheet provided and I agree to be a participant.
- b. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation.
- c. I recognize that my participation is completely voluntary and I can withdraw at any time, without giving any reason/explanation.
- d. I agree on my interview being recorded for the purpose of this study and/or any related further studies.
- e. I agree to let the researcher use my quotes in an anonymised form wherever required in the publication. The use of data in research and publications has been well explained.

_____	_____	_____
Name of the Participant	Date	Signature

_____	_____	_____
Name of the Researcher	Date	Signature

Name of the Supervisor